

“INVESTIGATING DETERMINANTS OF ONLINE CUSTOMER REPURCHASE
INTENTION AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING SALES IN NIGERIAN
ONLINE COMPANIES”

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of the University of the West of Scotland
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“INVESTIGATING DETERMINANTS OF ONLINE CUSTOMER REPURCHASE
INTENTION AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING SALES IN NIGERIAN
ONLINE COMPANIES”

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DECLARATION

This paper is being submitted in partial completion of the requirements for the degree of Doctorate in Business Administration. It is not being simultaneously submitted in candidature, has not been submitted or accepted for any degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any different institution.

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ABSTRACT

The development of the internet has increasingly created opportunities for companies to stay competitive by offering consumers fast and convenient ways of making purchases within the online retail environment. Whilst online shopping is widespread in western society, it has not fully penetrated the African market. In Nigeria, there are challenges regarding internet penetration. In fact, online platforms have brought about a lot of competition, and as such, online vendors and managers must be prepared to engage with online retailing. Considering this, the aim of this study is to examine the factors that influence consumer repurchase intentions and propose a framework that can help online vendors develop more effective marketing strategies that will lead to increased sales.

The study participants were those that engage in, offer online purchasing activities and those who operate online businesses. A survey was carried out and insights were obtained from a stratified random sample of 100 members of an online forum focused on internet shopping located in Delta state, Nigeria who participate actively in an online forum focused on internet shopping. Perceptions with regards customer repurchase intentions, marketing and increased sales were also obtained from in depth interviews with four (4) entrepreneurs. More so, further insights about internet shopping in Nigeria are drawn from secondary data sets covering a 10-year period. Qualitative data was analysed using content and thematic analysis. Using NVivo, the researcher generated word clouds to aid the content analysis. Emerging themes were then explored using thematic analysis. The quantitative results were analysed using SPSS, and here, descriptive, associative, and predictive analytical techniques were used.

It was found that there is an association between perceived value, privacy concerns, trust, systems availability and functionality, and online customer purchase intentions. Further, it was found that there was an association between online repurchase intentions, and other contextually based factors. It is revealed that the knowledge of customer repurchase intentions can help business operators create appropriate marketing strategies thereby increasing sales. However, some of the quantitative results obtained contrast with what is suggested by some of the literature. The qualitative findings reveal local understandings of online repurchase intentions by online vendors. Results of secondary data analysis reveal a strong relationship

between the number of intent users and sales revenues generated by online retailers such as Jumia in Nigeria.

An outcome of the study was the development of a framework that can help online business vendors develop more effective marketing strategies within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention that may lead to increased sales. Further, the study also made some managerial contributions, and suggested courses of action that can be taken by online vendors to help their businesses capitalise on the opportunities provided by the growth of online shopping.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This introductory chapter introduces the study. It starts by giving a background to the research project. Then the research problem statement is outlined. The research aim, main questions and objectives are then stated. Thereafter, the significance of the thesis is outlined. The scope of the research as well as research assumptions are presented. Further, definition of key terms, and a brief outline of the methodology is provided. Finally, the chapter is concluded by stating the structure of the study.

1.1 Background and Motivation

The development of internet has increasingly generated opportunities for companies to stay competitive by offering consumers fast and convenient ways of making purchases within the online retail environment (Vakulenko, Shams, Hellström, and Hjort, 2019). In today's world, one of the most rapid ways of buying goods and services is through the internet (Grunert and Ramus, 2005; Dahana, Miwa, and Morisada, 2019). Whilst online shopping is widespread in western society (Beckers, Cárdenas, and Verhetsel, 2018), it has not fully penetrated the African market (Pentz, du Preez, and Swiegers, 2020). For instance, Google launched the "Next Billion Users" project to encourage users to get connected to the internet (Oyedemi, 2020). The intention was to help overcome the challenges regarding internet penetration, and this affects consumer's interactions with the online retailing environment (Amankwah-Amoah, 2019). Studies also report that there is a dearth of information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria (Odusanya and Adetutu, 2020), and this affects the spread of internet adoption (Opesade, 2020). In fact, studies also report of aregional disparities of the digital divide in Nigeria (Sam, 2019). For instance, Adeleke (2020) analyzed the spatial distribution of Internet usage in Nigeria and identified its key determinants using data on the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory from 2016 to 2018. Studies also found that across Nigeria between the north and south and its urban and rural areas, Internet usage followed various economic and social contours (Adeleke, 2020; Adebayo and Beton Kalmaz, 2020). Factors such as market size, employment, income, access to electricity, urbanization, gender (female), age (60 years and above) and telephone density were significant factors in Internet usage (Odusanya and Adetutu, 2020).

On the other hand, western society has a high internet penetration (Pandita, 2017; Lu and Yu, 2020), and this has helped to increase online shopping activities (Barska and Wojciechowska-Solis, 2020; Yildirim, 2020). As such, a lot of shopping in Nigeria is undertaken within traditional brick and mortar stores (Ogbo, Ugwu, Enemuo, and Ukpere, 2019). However, the literature suggests that there is an increasing interest in online shopping in sub-Saharan Africa, and this is a growing trend (Olasanmi, 2019). Scholars suggest that the growth in online retailing influences customer repurchase intention (Ling, Chai and Piew, 2010; Tandon, Mittal, and Manohar, 2020). Further, this has helped to penetrate new market segments, and attract new customers (Har Lee, Cyril Eze and Oly Ndubisi, 2011; Alalwan, Baabdullah, Rana, Tamilmani, and Dwivedi, 2018). Others suggest that customer repurchase intention is a phenomenon that will get more attention in the coming years as an increased number of companies will want more information on the factors that make customers engage in online repurchases (Martin, Mortimer and Andrews, 2015).

Although, new customers are important to companies, they are harder to maintain than existing and loyal customers (Lin, 2010; Othman, Harun, Rashid, Nazeer, Kassim, and Kadhim, 2019). Within this context, it is important to identify the key factors of repurchase intentions within the Nigerian online shopping environment. Though Nigeria has a large population, and growing consumer class that is attractive for e-commerce (Olaleye, Adeyeye, Efuntade, Arije, and Anifowose, 2020), the literature shows that there is a lag behind in the e-commerce revolution, as consumers are more inclined to traditional ways of shopping than engage with e-commerce (Ezennia and Marimuthu, 2020). Whilst consumers are inclined to traditional ways of shopping, there is a prevalence of using social media for daily personal, corporate, and public interactions (Ezeah, Asogwa, and Obiorah, 2013; Omotosho, 2020). In fact, social media has the capabilities of educating, informing, and entertaining the audience (Schivinski, Muntinga, Pontes, and Lukasik, 2021). Yet, consumers are still inclined to traditional ways of shopping than engage with e-commerce.

Therefore, there is a need to understand factors that cause consumers to purchase and repurchase products and services within the online shopping environment because online transactions help to reduce costs for the business, and thereby contributing to competitiveness (Etzioni, 2019; Min, 2019). Knowledge of these factors will help managers make informed strategic marketing decisions. Given the growing trends of online shopping, and the

globalisation of business activity, this topic is timely in that it will help Nigerian marketers to understand the importance of engaging with technological innovations in a competitive business environment. And yet, there is a dearth of studies that focus on online repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context. Most studies focus on online repurchase intentions within western society, and much to the neglect of the African society. More recently, Wang, Nnaji, and Jung (2020) focused attention on cyber security breaches in Nigeria, and found that the lack of advanced technologies to prevent and address cyber security breaches and the unsatisfactory level of legislative compliance, together, appear to be the primary factors that have reduced cyber security capability in the banking sector. Whilst the issues surrounding cyber security have been tested in the banking sector (Okoye, Omankhanlen, Okoh, Ezeji, and Achugamonu, 2019; Ukpong, Udoh, and Essien, 2019), there is a dearth of studies that focus on other online retailing environments.

The literature reports of disparity levels of access to broadband internet in Nigeria (Umezuruike, Oludele, Kuyoro, and Izang, 2015; Titilope, 2020). This means that there are those households with access to modern information communication technology, and those without access (Tayo, Thompson, and Thompson, 2016). There are also those with restricted access. This indicates a gap internet accessibility. At this point, it is important to point out that information communication technology (ICT) includes any communication device or application such as radio, mobile phones, computers, network hardware and software, videoconferencing, and so forth (Ratheeswari, 2018). In this context, for online purchases to take place, these devices are important, together with their associated application packages (Wali, Cyprian, and Nkpurukwe, 2020). The literature suggests that there is a digital divide with some households having access to the digital devices and their application packages, whilst others have restricted access, and others have no access at all (Díaz Andrade and Techatassanasoontorn, 2021). This means that those without access cannot actively engage in the digital economy (Middleton, 2017; Chen and Kimura, 2019). Whilst the internet has revolutionised the way socio-economic activities are conducted globally (Ameen, Tarhini, Reppel, and Anand, 2021), a lack of internet penetration means the continued existence of traditional ways of shopping, that includes visiting the physical store.

This is a source of personal motivation for this research. The researcher has previous experience in online retailing and has developed a keen interest for this area. One intended goal for the future is for the researcher to launch an online company. This is drawn from personal

experiences of shopping online whilst studying in the UK and seek to understand experiences within a Nigerian context. Moreover, the researcher is from Nigeria, and has observed that there is a dearth of research on online repurchase intentions focusing on consumers in the Delta state. Whilst the Delta state is experiencing an increase in online activities, it is not clear whether this activity is for social interactions or online purchases. Ultimately, the researcher has a keen personal interest to launch a career in the Delta state and provide other entrepreneurs with information that can make their online business better.

1.2 Research Problem Statement

The demographic distribution in Nigeria shows that 49% and 51% of the entire population to be females and males respectively (Omenugha, 2018). Of the 185million people in Nigeria, 51% are young between 0 and 19 years old. Secondary data reveal that 17.5% of Nigerians are between 35 and 60 years old, while 20% fall between 20 and 35 years of age (Omenugha, 2018). Given that most of the country's population is relatively young and engage more with online shopping activities. Yet, the literature suggests that consumers fail to purchase goods and services on online platforms because of distrust, bias, and subjective views on social media (Jiang and Wang, 2006; Shashank and Devaraj, 2018). On the contrary, several global brands such as House of Fraser, Marks and Spencer, Debenhams, and many more, have seen their sales performance within the traditional brick and mortar stores declining, with some closing some of their branches (Labrecque, Swani, and Stephen, 2020; Xia, Pan, Zhou, and Zhang, 2020). This suggests that the online platforms have brought about a lot of competition (Frenken and Schor, 2019; Khan, 2019), and as such, an evolving online entrepreneur, manager must be prepared to engage with online retailing in order to survive in this competitive business environment (Hall and Williams, 2019). Considering this, it is important to understand the factors that influence online repurchase intentions because repeat sales helps the company to grow (Cantrell, Huang, Greenberg, Willett, Hair, and Vallone, 2020). Given that the young people engage more with technological devices and developments (Lupton, 2020; McGinnis, Harvey, and Young, 2020), and social media (Goodyear and Armour, 2019), then there is even greater need for online vendors to use the online platforms to attract customers (Tandon, Aakash, and Aggarwal, 2020; Zhang and Wang, 2021; Hussain, Li, and Li, 2021). Moreover, it is equally important to understand the generational and regional disparities in online shopping intentions (Taipale, 2019) because this will help companies to target their products and services more effectively.

Despite the prevalence of online shopping, use of smartphones and mobile applications in Nigeria (Titilope, 2020), there is still a wide gap between areas where the implementation of technology is high and areas completely lacking such means and applications (Adeleke, 2020). Out of the 185million people in Nigeria, only 23million people own and use smartphones daily (Ali, 2019). There are however 84 million internet users, and these engage with online activities or business daily (Titilope, 2020). This illustrate that there is a huge potential market for Nigerian online businesses.

Previous studies suggest that customer repurchase intention directly affects sales (Lee *et al.*, 2009; Ali and Bhasin, 2019). Others suggest that there is a direct link between customer repurchase intention and competitiveness of the business environment (Kim *et al.*, 2012; Tandon, Kiran, and Sah, 2017). However, given the competitiveness of the Nigerian business environment, it is important for online vendors to understand the Nigerian consumers. And yet, there is still a dearth of studies that focus on online repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context.

In Nigeria, whilst there is a rising number of internet users (Omosho, 2020), engagement with online shopping still presents a lot of challenges (Olasanmi, 2019). Although an increasing number of retailers are developing, and adopting online platforms to sale their goods and services (Gabriel, Ogbuigwe, and Ahiauzu, 2016; Anyanwu, Nelson, and Salawu, 2018), there is evidence to suggest that many Nigerian consumers are sceptical about online shopping (Adepoju, Oluwasina, and Awah, 2020) because of many factors including cultural, regional, gender, cybersecurity (Oyedemi, 2020), and so forth. Though the use of social media like Twitter, YouTube, and Facebook is prevalent in Nigeria (Okoroma, 2018; Armstrong and Butcher, 2018), there is still scepticism about online purchasing.

1.3 Research Aim/Questions/Objectives

This section presents the aim, objectives, and research questions.

1.3.1 Research Aim

The study's aim is to examine the factors that influence consumers' intentions and propose a framework that can help entrepreneurs and managers develop more effective strategies of marketing that can in turn lead to increased sales. The focus is on consumer repurchase intentions within Nigeria's online retailing environment, specifically amongst people in Delta state, Nigeria.

1.3.2 Research Questions

1. What are the gaps in knowledge within the literature surrounding customer repurchase intention?
2. What are the determinants of customer, repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context?
3. What is the role of social media on customer repurchase intention?
4. How does the knowledge of customer repurchase intention enhance company sales?
5. How can entrepreneurs and managers develop more effective strategies of marketing within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention?

1.3.3 Research Objectives

1. To critically review the literature surrounding customer repurchase intention.
2. To analyse the determinants of customer, repurchase intentions within the Nigeria context.
3. To determine the role of social media on customer repurchase intention.
4. To evaluate how the knowledge of customer repurchase intention and the development of internet shopping can enhance company sales of companies in the Nigeria context.
5. To propose a framework that can help entrepreneurs and managers to develop more effective strategies of marketing within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention.

1.4 Significance of the study

This study will contribute to the growing empirical customer repurchase intention literature and offers insight into factors that affect customer intention within the Nigerian context (Omotayo and Omotope, 2018; Olaleye, Sanusi, Mark, and Salo, 2020), specifically, Delta state. Insights from the study will also help managers to develop effective marketing strategies, and consequently increase sales. Given that global brands now penetrate different markets, and use the online platforms to penetrate new markets (Tuten, 2020; Tran, 2021), it is important for marketing managers to develop informed strategies that will help them to compete effectively and retain their customers and attract new ones. Therefore, knowledge of customer repurchase can help online companies in Nigeria to compete more effectively.

In fact, this study is located at the intersection of traditional “*brick and mortar stores*” and the “*click and collect*” purchasing practices. Previous research suggests that the “*click and collect*” models seamlessly merge digital and physical consumer channels (Tubridy, 2017; Gielens, Gijsbrechts, and Geyskens, 2020). By coordinating the efforts of e-commerce and physical

stores (traditional methods) time and expense associated with transporting an item to the customer is reduced (Pernot, 2020). It must be pointed out that the “*click and collect*” model is widely used in Europe (Milioti, Pramadari, and Kelepouri, 2020), and is gaining increasing attention from North American retail giants. “*Click and collect*” has significant advantages for both Nigerian customers and online vendors. Given increasing online shopping (Izogo and Jayawardhena, 2018; Schmid and Axhausen, 2019; Guru, Nenavani, Patel, and Bhatt, 2020), it is important for managers to adopt some of the most effective marketing practices to be competitive.

As such this research will add to the existing scientific knowledge in this field as studies relating to the determinants of customer repurchase intention in Delta state, Nigeria has barely been examined. Moreover, the relationship showing how potentially company sales can increase due to implementing appropriate strategies of marketing is minimal in the body of research related to this study.

Online shopping has become an ever-increasing phenomenon in the world today (Bandara, Fernando, and Akter, 2020). Therefore, developing countries like Nigeria must not lag from the opportunities provided by online shopping. There is a need to understand factors affecting online repurchase intentions within the Nigerian shopping environment. The knowledge of these factors will help firms in making successful strategic marketing decisions, as well as develop online resources that will help the firms to be more competitive. Given the growing engagement with online shopping activity in Nigeria (Ogbuji and Udom, 2018), understanding consumer repurchase intentions is important. In fact, knowledge of consumer repurchase intentions can help to develop strategies that will improve sales growth (Xiao, Fu, and Liu, 2018), as well as help firms to develop competitive strategies (Fazal-e-Hasan, Ahmadi, Kelly, and Lings, 2019).

By utilising technological advancements in their businesses, Nigerian online shoppers benefit from added convenience, reduced levels of perceived risks (Ogbuji and Udom, 2018). However, there are challenges with gaining trust (Gabriel, Ogbuigwe, and Ahiauzu, 2016; Izogo and Jayawardhena, 2018). Online vendors benefit in terms of reduced delivery costs (Olaleye, Salo, and Ukpabi, 2018). For instance, using the “*click and collect*” model, customers assume responsibility of getting purchased items from the shop to home. This presents an opportunity for company products to reach a wider audience, paid online, and ensure business growth and sustainability. Those who fail to engage with technological

developments in retailing face the risk of joining several businesses that have been outsmarted by online retailing activities. As such, this study is significant to help local businesses in Nigeria develop online marketing strategies that will help to build trust, retain customers, and encourage customer repurchase intentions.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on consumers that are in Delta state, Nigeria. The study participants are those that actively participate in online internet shopping forum, who were more likely to engage in online purchasing behaviour. The focus was on those customers who use the internet for shopping and to understand what prompts them to repurchase online. Insights obtained from a survey with 100 customers. Insights are also obtained from in depth interviews with four (4) entrepreneurs to understand their knowledge of this phenomenon. All these respondents are in Delta, Nigeria. As such, insights in this study pertains to users of online shopping within the context of Delta, in Nigeria. However, the insights obtained may be applicable to other parts of Nigeria, as well as other African countries. Lastly, to gain good insight of internet shopping and customer repurchase intention in Nigeria, secondary data was gathered also for more accurate results.

The topic has been chosen for its relevance to the Nigerian content of online purchasing. In fact, online purchasing is increasingly becoming common across many countries. For instance, a lot of services and products are now marketed online, and transactions take place virtually (Guru, Nenavani, Patel, and Bhatt, 2020). This is a topic of interest across many industries (Bandara, Fernando, and Akter, 2020). Further, the study helps to advance the researcher's career, and insights will help to make practical and academic contributions, and these are outlined in more detail in chapter 7.

1.6 Definition of Key Terms

Customer repurchase intentions: This is defined as the process of decision-making customers go through when deciding to return to a shop or website to buy products and services (Chua et al., 2006).

Online shopping: Online shopping pertains to the shopping behavior of consumers within a website or an online store utilised for the purposes of online purchase (Monsuwé, Dellaert, and De Ruyter, 2004).

Technology Acceptance Model: stipulates that perceived usefulness of technology & perceived ease of use are forecasters of user attitude towards adopting the technology, ensuing behavioral intentions and real practise (Masrom, 2007).

Perceived value: Perceived value is a customer's general evaluation of the use of a product built on perceptions of what is received and what is given (Wu, Chen, Chen, and Cheng, 2014).

Perceived usefulness: is defined as the extent to which a customer believes that shopping online will make the performance of their business or online transactions better (Urvashi et al., 2017).

Brand: According to, The American Marketing Association, (2019), a brand is a term, symbol, name, design, or any other feature that categorises a seller's commodity or service as separate from those of other vendors.

Brand reputation: discusses the way a brand (be in a company or an individual) is perceived by others. A favourable brand reputation reveals that consumers feel at ease with purchasing your products or services because they trust it.

Privacy: privacy is the amount of protection given to customer information (Hoffman *et al.*, 1999). This depicts a user's worries around likely loss of privacy (Xu et al., 2011).

1.7 Research Context and Assumptions

In the advanced countries, the utilisation of online platforms for buying and selling goods has become a standard (Bolton, Parasuraman, Hoefnagels, Migchels, Kabadayi, Gruber, Komarova Loureiro and Solnet, 2013). For example, approximately 99% of South Korean Internet users make purchases online (Kim, Chung, and Lee, 2011). Similarly, in the United Kingdom, 89% of adults used the internet at least weekly in 2018, up from 88% in 2017 and 51% in 2006 (Ofcom, 2019). In Africa, the Nigerian internet shopping setting, and the e-commerce sector, maintain the top position as the principal player in e-commerce sector in the African continent estimated at \$13 billion and rising at a speedy pace of 25% annually (Omenugha, 2018). This is so, due to the growing number of people with access to the internet. Nigeria was reported as of 2013, to be the nation with the major internet connectivity in the African continent with an estimated 56 million internet recorded users (Omenugha, 2018). And as of 2018, the figure of internet users in Nigeria is on the increase. This progress is further echoed in the scores of online orders place on the websites of key online retailers which grew from just about a 1,000 orders each day in 2012 to more than 15,000 orders per day in 2018. Considering this, the

country of Nigeria possesses boundless potentials of implementing online shopping, and thus warrants further investigation in terms of online customer repurchase intentions.

Yet, in Nigeria, some customers still purchase wholly from traditional shops, thereby slowing the pace of online shopping. Given the ever-increasing level of virtual communication such as Facebook, email, twitter, blackberry messenger and diverse social media channels, it is imperative that entrepreneurs and managers must develop more relevant strategies if they are to grow and sustain their businesses.

Consequently, the context of the research are consumers and entrepreneurs that engage in online shopping. These are in Delta, Nigeria. It is assumed that customers shared their honest opinions about their repurchase intentions. It is also assumed that the entrepreneurs shared their honest experiences about the online shopping environment.

1.8 Structure of the thesis

The structure of the study was informed by the research aim and objectives, as illustrated in figure 1.1. The outline of each chapters is outlined here in turn.

Chapter 1: The first chapter presents the study. It provides a detailed background and rationale of the study. This is subsequently followed by outlining the problem statement with the intention of positioning the study within the Nigerian context. Thereafter, the study aim, objectives and research questions are set. These are used as the pillars that will guide the study. Key terms to be used in the study are also defined. A short outline of the methodology is also stated. The chapter ends by providing an outline of this research.

Figure 1.1: Structure of the thesis

Source: Author's own construction

Chapter 2: This chapter 2 reviews the literature surrounding customer repurchase intention. Here, the intention is to identify gaps in knowledge, and help to position the study at the intersection of academic debates. Limitations of existing theoretical understandings are also outlined. Following from a comprehensive literature review, testable hypothesis is generated. Further, a conceptual framework is created to help to position the study at the intersection of the gaps in knowledge identified.

Chapter 3: This chapter explains the research philosophy, research approach and strategy that was adopted. It also discusses and justifies the methods that were employed to help execute the research appropriately. The research population, sampling, and data analysis plans are also discussed. Ethical issues are also explained in detailed, and the researcher outlines how ethical principles were observed. Issues surrounding reliability, validity, and representativeness of the sample are also discussed.

Chapter 4: The fourth provides an analysis of the data sets. It starts by engaging with reliability tests for the quantitative data sets. This is then followed by descriptive, associative, and predictive analysis. Quantitative results are presented using charts and tables. Within this section, generated hypothesis is tested. Some are accepted and others rejected. This is then followed by an analysis of the qualitative results using content and thematic analysis. Qualitative results are presented using visualisations such as word clouds, coding matrices, and the like. This is then followed by using chunks of data to help illustrate issues that arise.

Chapter 5: This chapter showcases the results of the study within the context of the literature. Firstly, it analyses the demographics of the Nigerian consumer by drawing insights from both the primary data and the secondary data sets. The impact of different factors on purchase intentions are then discussed. Thereafter, a contextually based model is developed that can assist online vendors in Nigeria in developing strategies that can increase their customers' intentions to repurchase.

Chapter 6: This conclusive chapter, first makes a summary of the study and states the main conclusions. It provides discussions how each of the objectives, as stated in chapter 1, were achieved. Theoretical and managerial contributions of the study are also outlined. Recommendations are then made, and study limitations acknowledged. Areas of future research are also outlined.

1.9 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter had presented the study. It has offered a detailed background and basis for this thesis. The internet revolution has meant that businesses now engage with social media, and online platforms to advertise, sale products, and services, and enhance their performance. Whilst there is an engagement with online platforms by Nigerian consumers, there is a hesitancy to conduct online transactions because of cyber security fears. This has meant that the online repurchase intentions face some challenges. But there is continued use of social media for interactional purposes, and as a vehicle for social exchange. It appears there is a

cultural preference for buying from physical stores, rather than buying from the online environment. Considering this, the Delta state has been chosen as a site for investigating the factors that influence consumers' intentions within Nigeria's online retailing environment. An understanding of these factors can help business in Nigeria to develop strategies that can help to build consumer confidence in online retailing, and thereby reducing costs, and making enterprises in Nigeria to be competitive. The study of consumer repurchase intention within the online environment is positioned within the Nigerian context. The next chapter critically reviews the literature.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the concept of customer repurchase intentions. It also draws attention to the debates surrounding online shopping and traditional brick and mortar or brick and click stores. A discussion of the Nigerian online shopping environment is also discussed. The technology adoption model, together with its elements is also discussed. The chapter also discusses issues surrounding trust, privacy, and perceived ease of use, as factors for customer online repurchases.

In the current competitive business environment, understanding the intent of customers to repurchase goods and services has become increasingly important to most firms (Kim et al., 2012). Additionally, in the past, firms have observed the relevance of discovering variables that make customers want to repurchase goods and services (Sarkis et al., 2010). According to Lee et al. (2009) good and consistent customer repurchase system is a major concern for most companies wishing to retain customers and gain competitive advantage. Hence, grasping what satisfies customers or instigates them to repurchase goods and services is crucial.

Furthermore, the role of social media on customer repurchase intention is one area that needs attention as social media can influence the way customers feel about repurchasing items online. Additionally, insight into the role of customer repurchase intention on online firm's sales performance and the link between CRI and market competitiveness in online firms will be reviewed. Finally, the gaps in literature are analysed to help position the current study more strongly at the intersection of gaps identified in the literature. The chapter ends by developing a conceptual framework that helps to position the current study at the intersection of gaps identified in the literature.

2.2 Development of online retail/shopping

The development of the internet has resulted to a surge in electronic shopping worldwide (Jusoh and Ling, 2012; Gera, Fatta, Garg, and Malik, 2021). E-commerce has provided companies and organisations around the world with the equal opportunity of serving customers, offering products and services to them, and creating value for customers (Aden et al., 2006; Ladhari, Gonthier, and Lajante, 2019). The growth of online shopping around the world has

leaped beyond bounds with almost every firm having an online presence to maintain competitive advantage (Lee et al., 2011; Haque and Mazumder, 2020).

Online shopping is a process where consumers search, browse, compare, and eventually buy goods and services using the web platforms (Ling, Chai and Piew, 2010; Zhai, Cao, and Zhen, 2019). The use of internet to purchase products has seen significant growth in recent years with figures indicating higher levels of expenditure by consumers in numerous countries like the United States, China, Japan, Nigeria and many more (Jiang and Wang, 2006; Juntongjin, 2021). Previous studies reveal that 71 per cent of UK consumers and 61 percent US consumers found shopping online on countless websites during the holiday seasons [Wipro Digital, 2014]. Today the internet has become so prevalent and popular that consumers make orders for items and get them delivered on the same day. In fact, the internet has now become an alternative method of purchasing goods and services (Kuo, Hu and Yang, 2013).

Although, internet users have devoted their time to getting involved in online activities like gaming, social networking, and web browsing; digital shopping has predominantly become a normal activity in several parts of the world (Jiang et al., 2013). The change occurring around the world today with regards to online retail/shopping has seen firms who run the strictly .com enterprises for example eBay. Firms that operate both brick/click type of online shopping which involves physical shops and online presence like Zara group, for instance, have been found to perform well (Srinivasan, 2015). Previous studies suggest that the internet has progressively turned many businesses into global ones and helped to facilitate sales and growth (Hume, 2008).

Online shopping, with focus on retail helps customers access electronic stores (e-stores) where they find and select products, proceed to make payments through payment portals like PayPal, with the use of credit or debit cards, as well as money transfers/cash on delivery and get goods delivered to their doorstep (Ha and Janda, 2008; Tandon, 2020). Unlike brick and mortar store, several benefits are found when shopping online as they include easy access to items, vast options to choose from, varied payment methods, and convenience delivery of goods and services (Jiang, Yang, and Jun 2013). The brick/click shopping is where companies have shops both online and in physical (brick and mortar store). Subsequently, the customer can purchase items either online or in store, try them on in the store, return them in store or online, have a feel of what the products are like in store or use the 3D virtual clothing technology.

The literature suggests that online stores offer shoppers a wide range of products to choose from, service information, time saving advantage, privacy, convenient shopping, and competitive pricing (Katole, 2011). The growth in internet usage has encouraged scholars to focus on understanding factors that drives and motivates people to engage with online shopping (Blake, et al., 2003; Do, Nguyen, and Nguyen, 2019). Equally, other scholars have focused more on the risks associated with online shopping (Niemeier, Zocchi and Catena, 2013; Alharethi, 2016; Aadhar, 2020).

Table 2. 1: Summary of key studies on online shopping

Author (s)	Date	Study focus	Key Findings
Robinson, H., Dall'Olmo, R., Rettie, R. and Rolls-Willson, G.	2007	Motivations and perceptions of UK online grocery shoppers	Most respondents considered online shopping as a complementary, rather than as an alternative mode of shopping for groceries, with users continuing to make purchases in traditional stores, as well as online
Ha, H.Y. and Janda, S.,	2008	Proposed and evaluated empirically a model of online customer satisfaction and its key antecedent and consequent constructs.	Found that: -perceived value may both directly and indirectly (via disconfirmation) affect not just satisfaction, but it may also indirectly affect attribution via disconfirmation
Kim, J. and Forsythe, S.	2010	The study investigated functional and hedonic roles of dynamic product imagery (DPI) by applying a modified Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	-provided empirical support for TAM in the context of DPI acceptance for online shopping across seven product categories. - two additional constructs – technology anxiety and innovativeness – showed significant effects. -A significant difference was found between the over 50 age group and the other two groups (18–30/31–50) in the acceptance process.
Delafrooz, N., Paim, L.H. and Khatibi, A.	2010	Focused on students' online shopping behavior	It was found that: -utilitarian orientation, convenience, price, and a wider selection influenced consumers' attitudes towards online shopping.
Hernández, B., Jiménez, J. and José Martín, M.	2011	Analysed whether individuals' socioeconomic characteristics – age, gender and income – influence their online shopping behaviour	It was found that: - socioeconomic variables moderate neither the influence of previous use of the internet nor the perceptions of e-commerce - socioeconomic variables do not condition the behaviour of the experienced e-shopper.
Jiang, L., Yang, Z. and Jun, M.	2013	The key convenience dimensions of online shopping	Uncovers the key dimensions of convenience and their associated sub-dimensions specific to the context of online shopping
Kuo, Y.F., Hu, T.L. and Yang, S.C.	2013	Explored the effects of consumer inertia and satisfaction on repeat-purchase intention among female online shoppers, and examined whether positive word-of-mouth and alternative attraction moderate the above relationships	Found that: - both consumer inertia and satisfaction positively influence repeat-purchase intention -consumer inertia is more influential than satisfaction -positive word-of-mouth negatively moderates the relationship between consumer inertia and repeat-purchase intention, Positive word-of mouth positively moderates that between satisfaction and repeat-purchase intention; -alternative attraction does not moderate any of the above relationships significantly

Clemes, M.D., Gan, C. and Zhang, J.	2014	The study focused on empirical analysis of online shopping adoption in Beijing, China	-identifies and ranks seven important decision factors: perceived risk, consumer resources, service quality, subjective norms, product variety, convenience, and website factors. - All of these decision factors impact on Chinese consumers' adoption of online shopping
Katta, R.M.R. and Patro, C.S.	2018	Focused on identifying the factors influencing online shopping behavior and the reasons for preferring online shopping compared to shopping in conventional stores	Found that Accessibility and convenience are the key drivers for a major shift to online shopping
Do, T., Nguyen, T. and Nguyen, C.,	2019	Focused on the key factors affecting the intention of customers to purchase online, in Vietnam	-Found that demographic factors can affect online shopping intention, such as age and income, It was found that Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Transaction Security have a positive relationship with online purchase intention.
Ladhari, R., Gonthier, J. and Lajante, M	2019	The study focuses on to segmenting Generation Y female online shoppers according to their psychographic, demographic, and behavioral characteristics.	Found four approaches to online shopping: trend shopping, pleasure shopping, price shopping, and brand shopping. The study identified six shopping profiles: price shoppers, discovery shoppers, emotional shoppers, strategic shoppers, fashionistas, and shopping fans.
Tandon, U.,	2020	Focused on understanding the predictors of online shopping in India	-It was found that social media, reverse logistics, and POD mode of payment had a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction
Gera, N., Fatta, D.D., Garg, R. and Malik, S	2021	The study examined online shopping determinants in India.	It was found that 'ease of use and convenience' is the most relevant factor for online shopping.

Traditionally, consumers went into stores to purchase goods and services. Whilst in there, they inspected the goods first-hand. This was then followed by buying what they had physically seen. On the contrary, the internet provides an opportunity to save time, and get access to a wide range of products and services before making a purchasing decision (Robinson, Dall'Olmo, Rettie and Rolls-Willson, 2007; Katta and Patro, 2018). Whilst these shopping approaches have proved successful, they all have pros and cons.

Despite the presence of these benefits, it is argued that the internet, more so the online shopping presents numerous problems too. Previous studies suggest that purchasing goods not seen physically but virtually could create high levels of disappointment for consumers (Holt et al., 2004; Farah, Ramadan and Harb, 2019). Scholars also point out that there are several types of online shoppers, with different shopping styles (Eriksson, Rosenbröijer, and Fagerström, 2017; Lim and Kim, 2020). For instance, there are personal shoppers, professional shoppers, student shoppers, thrift shoppers and many more. With the increase of internet shopping, and

consequential increase is cyber security issues, it is important to understand the impact of online shopping risks on intentions to buy items online.

Whilst there are many studies on the development of online retail shopping, the studies presented in table 2.1 present a specimen of the growing trend of academic interest in this area. It merges that there are different factors influencing online shopping, and these vary by country, region, and context. Whilst studies have been conducted in other parts of the world such as India, Vietnam, Europe, and so forth, and Scopus database presents over 5537 articles in this area, this study is more interested in the development of online shopping in Nigeria. Therefore, careful selection of articles had to be done to make the study more focused.

2.3 Emergence and growth of online shopping in Nigeria

The internet is described as a rich, ever evolving, complex and multi-layered environment which aids the connection of people, goods, and services together (Jagboro, 2003; Farahat, Tolba, Elhoseny, and Eladrosy, 2019). The emergence of the internet in Nigeria has provided numerous opportunities for individuals who utilise its different activities (Omosho, 2020; Oyedemi, 2020). It has now become an indispensable tool for executing various activities like research, data storage, communication, and retail not just in Nigeria but across the globe (Zhou and Zhang, 2007; Oyedemi, 2020). In fact, the internet has revolutionised the socio-economic activities carried out in Nigeria (Ezennia and Marimuthu, 2020).

Nigeria, like most third world countries have had a rather slow start with regards to the use of the internet, as a result of lower rates of internet penetration (Umezuruike, Oludele, Kuyoro, and Izang, 2015; Agboje, Adedoyin, and Ndujiuba, 2017). However, due to the improvement in the internet infrastructure, internet penetration has gradually improved. This has resulted to the growth of online retailing activities (Udo, 2011; Shanmugam, Wang, Bugshan and Hajli, 2015). However, there is equally an increase in internet fraud (Pratt, Holtfreter and Reising, 2010; Bello and Griffiths, 2021). This has resulted in trust issues. At times, deliveries for goods purchased online are delayed, and at times, poor products delivered, thereby affecting consumer confidence (Liao and Keng, 2013).

The literature suggests that a huge number of retailers in Nigeria have developed online selling platforms (Aminu, 2013; Omosho, 2020). This is consistent with an internet penetration rate of 52 per cent for Nigeria (World Internet Statistics, 2017). As a developing country, Nigeria's growth has been rising due to increased use of online shopping platforms. Other factors that

have caused a low internet penetration rate in Nigeria include poor infrastructure, security risks, cultural issues, illiteracy and so on (Udo, 2001; Odusanya and Adetutu, 2020). Some scholars suggest that the major factor for internet usage and penetration is the income of Nigerians, data protection and internet connectivity (Ayo, 2006; Odusanya and Adetutu, 2020). The political unrest in some parts of the country due to terrorism has also affected the way people use internet.

Of the over 180 million people in Nigeria, 10 million use the internet for shopping (Agwu and Carter, 2014). Some people in Nigeria spend a lot of money on data just to be connected to social networks and struggle greatly with shopping online. The literature suggests that there is a low level of computer education amongst people in Nigeria, and this leaves individuals with no understanding on how to use the internet (Olatokun, 2017). Yet, the Nigerian ecommerce industry recorded in revenues \$1.9b in 2016 and this is expected to reach \$3.9b in 2020 (Adedeji, 2016; Omenugha, 2018).

In Nigeria, existing research on the acceptance of internet has focused on determinants of the use of internet, e-banking in developing country (Ayo and Adewoye, 2010; Ayo, Oni, Adewoye and Eweoya, 2016), effects of electronic banking facilities (Lee et al., 2009; Odumeru, 2012; Inegbedion, 2018), and so forth. According to Nigerian country commercial guide (export.gov, 2017), despite the struggles ecommerce in Nigeria has faced in the past years, in recent times, it is seen to have done better and is now widely used in primary sectors and industries to sell products and services. Furthermore, many of Nigeria's online infrastructural projects have attracted the attention of facilitators from Europe and Asia and this has seen the increase in general internet service in Nigeria with e-commerce among them. Mckinsey (year?). For instance, ecommerce spending in Nigeria is estimated at about Twelve billion (\$12b.). There is a projection that it will soar to about seventy-five (\$75b) in terms of revenue annually by the year 2025. Other kinds of growth in ecommerce are recorded in fraud prevention as the Federal Government signed a bill into law to help combat fraud in ecommerce.

Whilst there is a growing number of studies on online shopping within the Nigerian context, there is a dearth of studies that focus on online repurchase intentions (see table 2.2). Apart from Omotayo and Omotope (2018), Most studies have focused on e-banking, teaching, and learning, and so forth. There is a need for studies that focus on online customer repurchase intentions.

Table 2. 2: Summary of key studies on online shopping in Nigeria

Author (s)	Date	Study focus	Key findings
Ayo, C.K. and Adewoye, J.O.	2010	Reviewed the state of e-Banking implementation in Nigeria and evaluated the influence of trust on the adoption of e-Payment using an extended technology acceptance model (TAM). Investigated organizational reputation, perceived risk and perceived trust in the management of banks as a factor for enhancing customer loyalty.	Found that: - perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are not only antecedent to e banking acceptance, they are also factors to retain customers who use of e-banking system such as organizational reputation, perceived risk and trust
Odumeru, J.A.	2012	Focused on the underlying determinants of acceptance e-banking	Found that: -The acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria is significantly influenced by Age, Educational Background, Income, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Risk and Perceived Enjoyment
Aminu, S.A.	2013	examine the challenges of online shopping in retail industry in Nigeria	Some challenges were found to militate against adoption of online shopping in Nigeria's retail industry. These include cultural barriers, infrastructure challenge, security concern, perceived risk and inadequate regulatory framework.
Agwu, E. and Carter, A.L.	2014	Investigated the extent of the adoption and usage of the mobile phone banking services among banking customers in Nigeria	Found that phone banking was more established than internet banking and ATM services, but ATM services had a wider reach.
Ayo, C.K., Oni, A.A., Adewoye, O.J. and Eweoya, I.O.	2016	Investigated factors affecting e-banking usage based on electronic service (e-service) quality, attitude and customer satisfaction	Found that: -perceived e-service quality had a strong influence on customer satisfaction and use of e-banking -competence of e-service support staff, system availability, service portfolio, responsiveness and reliability, were found to be most significant in rating e-service quality
Falode, B.O., Amubode, A.A., Adegunwa, M.O. and Ogunduyile, S.R.	2016	Focused on online and offline shopping motivation of apparel consumers in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria	It was revealed that the respondents preferred to shop offline than online shopping platforms.
Olatokun, W.M.	2017	Investigated the availability, accessibility and use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) among women academics in six universities in South Western Nigeria	Found that: -the use of ICT facilities such as computers, printers, Internet, individual websites, photocopiers, telephones and mobile phones was relatively high among the respondents compared to the use of scanners, facsimiles, videoconferencing, and teleconferencing. -women academics used the ICT facilities for various tasks notably for statistical analyses, word processing, Internet browsing and searching for information, electronic communications, and preparation of course materials.

Omotayo, F.O. and Omotope, A.R., 2018	2018	Focused on the determinants of continuance intention to use online shops among students of two federal universities in Nigeria.	It was found that: -perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, subjective norms, perceived enjoyment, perceived site quality, convenience, prior experience, shopping habit and trust determined continuance intention to use online shops by the students.
Olaleye, Adeyeye, Efuntade, Arije, and Anifowose, O.,	2020	Focused on the impact of e-quality services on consumer satisfaction and loyalty in Nigeria.	A statistically significant positive relationship was found among consumer satisfaction, loyalty, e-service quality, and their dimensions.

Whilst these studies revealed increased activity in terms of online shopping within Nigeria, there is scepticism on repurchase intentions because of different factors including cultural, infrastructural, cyber security, an inadequate regulatory framework, and so forth. These concerns impact upon online customer repurchase intentions, and the ability of Nigerian enterprises to transact with a global audience. The study highlighted in table 2.2, and other related, fail to provide a framework that can help entrepreneurs and managers to develop more effective strategies of marketing within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention.

2.4 Concept of Customer repurchase intention (CRI)

Customer repurchase intention or behaviour is beneficial to e-businesses. Jiang and Rosenbloom (2005), postulates that repurchase behaviour is connected to customer loyalty and they highlight that the importance of loyal consumers or customers. Repurchase behaviour is a result of customer loyalty (Hellier, Geursen, Carr and Rickard, 2003; Suhartanto, Helmi Ali, Tan, Sjahroeddin, and Kusdiby, 2019). In fact, engaging in repurchase behaviour entails increased motivation for customers to search for items and information, resist competitor's promotions, spread the word about the brand they are passionate about, buy more and spend more frequently (Rosenberg and Czepiel, 1983; Meyer-Waarden, 2008; El-Adly, 2019). In this vein, Yang (2012) suggests that customer repurchase is about how consumers make up their minds to buy items online repeatedly due to its usefulness.

Understanding consumer traits and why consumers shop online includes understanding their personality characteristics, traits, demographic and lifestyle (Malhorta et al., 2004; Fan, Wang, and Zhang, 2021). The knowledge that consumers have certain shopping behaviour is one aspect and the second is knowing which factors prompt those behaviours to be displayed (Asiedu and Dube, 2020). There is evidence of generational differences in shopping behaviours (Eastman, Iyer and Thomas, 2013; Marriott and Williams, 2018; Kim and Ammeter, 2018). For instance, the older generations have different shopping styles from the younger ones and the knowledge of this can help in comparing their repurchase instigators.

Customer repurchase occurs because of several factors. In fact, the repurchase of goods and services is good for the economy (Dider and Hart, 2006; Cheng, Fu, Sun, Bilgihan, and Okumus, 2019). If customers are dissatisfied with their online experiences, then this can damage the sales performance of any company. This means every organisation with online shopping platforms must carry out research and development constantly to monitor customers online shopping needs and meet them. Furthermore, the understanding of customer profiles plays a huge role in determining how well firms set up their online platforms to suit customers' needs.

Purchasing goods and services via the internet which is now known as online retail/shopping is one of the most popular ways of shopping. Identifying why consumers make the choice to shop online and make repurchase decisions is pivotal to online firm's success (Lin, 2008; Marriott and Williams, 2018). Though this concept has received fair amount of research, it is still lacking in analysing the determinants that encourage customers to repurchase items online within the context of Nigeria. The literature on CRI is fragmented, and several variables were identified to ascertain what leads to repurchase. The literature points to five factors that have influenced customers to repurchase goods and services. These are exogenous factors which include consumer traits, consumer attitude and intention towards shopping, situational factors, product characteristics, trust, and previous online shopping experience (Udo, 2001; Park, Jeon, and Sullivan, 2015).

These set of factors that are said to prompt repurchase intentions are the major ones that propel consumers around the world to use the internet as a medium for shopping. These factors were found missing in the TAM factors as those ones were lacking in the areas of exogenous characteristics. The knowledge of what factors encourage customers to repurchase goods and

services online is vital for every online retailer. Examining how the expanded TAM which integrates eight proposed variables consisting of enjoyment, value, trust, brand and reputation, system availability and functionality, fulfilment, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and privacy may influence CRI in Nigeria.

Several studies have been carried out to explore factors that influence individuals to repurchase goods and services within the online environment. Several theoretical models have been created to review this social construct and amongst them are the Technology Acceptance model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Sussman and Gifford, 2019; Conner, 2020) which are two of the most commonly used models by researchers around the world in a bid to obtain better understanding of customer repurchase intention and online shopping behaviour (Kim and Forsythe, 2007; Carfora, *et al.*, 2019).

2.4.1 Customer repurchase – online, face to face

Over the past decades, studies have been carried out to identify factors that instigate customers to repurchase items online or instore (Lee *et al.*, 2009; Ilyuk, 2018). The benefits of customer repurchase are enormous for firms as this means firms will have better competitive advantage over their rivals and stand a chance in the challenging business environment (Fenech and Cass, 2011). Scholars have also explored factors that inspire the thought process for customer repurchase decisions (Pavlou and Fygenon, 2006; Jin, Li, and Cheng, 2018).

Customer repurchases take place both online and instore (Hult, Sharma, Morgeson III, and Zhang, 2019). Considering face to face repurchase, customers have gone to shops to see and buy items they want, and have return based on several needs being met. The advantages of brick and mortar store are numerous and they include the ability to physically inspect first-hand the products on display, ability to ask shop assistants queries about the product and ability to engage with other customers and find out their thoughts on products before proceeding to buy them (Otto and Chung, 2000; Vojvodić, 2019).

Brick and mortar stores will always have these advantages and more, but the disadvantages of physical stores still remain, and they include, time, lack of convenience, sold out items or missing items, stress from walking around the shop (Tsai and Huang, 2007; Pauwels and Neslin, 2015). However, customers are prone to repurchase items from physical stores for several reasons like ability to see the goods, trust, value, and general satisfaction (Kacen, Hess and Chiang, 2013).

Online shopping on the other hand, provides a more improved way of shopping and this is seen in the ease at which customer can shop in the comfort of their own homes (Pauwels and Neslin, 2015). In fact, with online shopping, customers can buy from anywhere around the globe, pay through diverse channels using a credit card, view a variety of items and make comparisons before buying (Thulani, Chitakunye, and Chummun, 2014; Vadwala and Vadwala, 2017). There are no physical queues for paying or searching for items. Thereby saving valuable time (Fue et al., 2009). There are also different reasons to be weary when shopping online and these factors are what could deter customers from purchasing or repurchasing items. Despite this, the use of the internet for shopping of goods and services has witnessed a great increase (Keen et al., 2015).

More and more businesses have been faced with the challenge of incorporating e-commerce into their already existing business model (Pool, Parnell, Spillan, Carraher and Lester, 2006; Cristobal-Fransi, Montegut-Salla, Ferrer-Rosell, and Daries, 2020). This provides an opportunity to serve more customers 24/7, to stay relevant and competitive (Moliner et al., 2007). Although several businesses have found difficulty with establishing an online presence, they have maintained their physical stores. However, with a rising number of online shoppers, the patronage of physical stores is on the decline (Burke, 2002).

2.4.2 The effect of social media on Customer Repurchase Intention

Social media is a unique tool that allows for communication between people, sharing content swiftly and efficiently (Lin, Yan, and Chen, 2017). At the basic level social media allows connection and interaction with other people (Appel, Grewal, Hadi, and Stephen, 2020). Unlike other forms of communication, the main drive is media. Previous studies suggest that websites and applications create and share content or to participate in social networking (Mergel, 2013). These websites and applications allow users to create and share opinions, digital photos, videos, and other content with an online audience in real time. There are multiple social interactions via distinct social networks online. These platforms have facilitated information sharing and different networks have unique methods of connection and networking. Some popular methods social networking sites include Instagram/Twitter, friends on Facebook and Connections on LinkedIn where users can interact, share, and modify content (Bechmann and Lomborg, 2013). These networks are maintained by the social media organization. Social media services are largely accessed via web-based technologies on computers and increasingly mobile devices. The emergence of Web 2.0 has increased the interconnectivity between individuals online and

provides the room for collaboration between brands and consumers online. The rise of social media has presented to consumers newer opportunities to engage with brands and network with other users of brands. Many users can now share and access information (Chen et al., 2011a).

Consumers have access to different sources of information from experience with a brand facilitated by reviews, recommendations, and endorsement from other consumers. Platforms like Amazon.com have facilitated this online social environment where customers are able to rate certain products and leave reviews (Huang and Benyoucef, 2013). Many users also apply multiple social media tools like online forums and communities like Tripadvisor.com to interact with other users online. These forums provide opportunities to share and distribute information about a related brand or product to multiple consumers, as well as offer valuable advice to others (Gamboa and Gonçalves, 2014). In fact, online platforms have also produced viral impact that offer great exposure to different products and services. This contributes to the formation of positive attitudes towards products and services, and ultimately lead to purchase intentions.

Social networking websites have demonstrated the effectiveness for social interactions and information sharing (Iankova, Davies, Archer-Brown, Marder, and Yau, 2019). Fue et al. (2009) suggests that the effect of social networking sites in e-commerce is a successful tool for marketing purposes. Reviews for example are one of the important features that arose from social media (Gamboa and Gonçalves, 2014). Consumers generate huge value for companies and other consumers from the reviews left on products and services (Nambisan, 2002). Recommendations are another important feature that influences purchase intentions. Ridings and Gefen (2004) point out that recommendations highlight interest in a product.

The interconnectivity of consumers via social media reviews or recommendations and networks, increases the trust in a brand and reduces perceived risk (Mathur, 2019). These advancements have also announced a new inflow called social commerce pulled out of e-commerce. Social commerce provides room for the purchase of products from third-party companies within social media networks (Ridings and Gefen, 2004). For example, Facebook provides the opportunity to browse and compare products on its social network. This provides consumers with the opportunity to make purchases directly on its platform without the need to go on the company's website. It also enables communication between brands and consumers pre-sale and post-sale from its instant messaging service. Similarly, Twitter also provides the

opportunity to learn about a product in a tweet and make the purchase on its online site. Some of the key studies in this area are summarised in table 2.3.

Table 2. 3: Summary of key studies on effects of social media on online repurchase intention

Author (s)	Date	Study focus	Key findings
Lu, H.P. and Hsiao, K.L.	2010	Focused on the influence of extro/introversion on the intention to pay for social networking sites (SNS)	-perceived value significantly influenced the intention to pay SNS subscription fees while satisfaction did not. -extroverts thought more highly of the social value of the SNS, while introverts placed more importance on its emotional and price value
Tsai, J.Y., Egelman, S., Cranor, L. and Acquisti, A.	2011	Focused on the effect of online privacy information on purchasing behavior	-when privacy information is made more salient and accessible, some consumers are willing to pay a premium to purchase from privacy protective websites
Weisberg, J., Te'eni, D. and Arman, L.	2011	Focused on past purchase and intention to purchase in e-commerce	-past purchasing predicts intentions to purchase -trust and social presence act as partial mediators
Chiang, H.S.	2013	Continuous usage of social networking sites	It was found that the reasons why people continuously use SNSs vary with different innovation diffusion stages. In particular attitude toward SNSs had the strongest direct effect on continuous intention while the impact of social norms was not significant in the different innovation diffusion stages.
Yu, J., Zo, H., Kee Choi, M. and P. Ciganek, A.	2013	Focused on user acceptance of location-based social networking services	-A positive influence exists for each type of perceived value on satisfaction with hedonic value having the strongest relationship. -Hedonic value is positively correlated with behavioural intention to use LB-SNS and positive word-of-mouth while social value affects positive word-of-mouth. -Utilitarian value did not influence either behavioural intention to use LB-SNS or positive word-of-mouth. -User satisfaction has a significant influence on both behavioural intentions to use LB-SNS and positive word-of-mouth
Teng, S., Wei Khong, K., Wei Goh, W. and Yee Loong Chong, A.	2014	Examining the antecedents of persuasive eWOM messages in social media	This study found that argument quality, source credibility, source attractiveness, source perception and source style are critical antecedents of persuasive eWOM messages. The PLS results suggested that source credibility (trustworthiness), source perception (usefulness, social ties) and source style (visual cues, number) are main characteristics of credible eWOM messages in relation to users' intention to accept and use online reviews. The variance of information acceptance and intention to use were also explained in the findings
Balakrishnan, B.K., Dahnil, M.I. and Yi, W.J.	2014	Focused on the impact of social media marketing medium toward purchase intention and brand loyalty among Generation Y	-the online marketing communications, specifically, E- WOM, online communities and online advertisement are effective in promoting brand loyalty and product purchase intention through company website and social media platforms. - social media marketing medium has become an important marketing tool to reach emerging younger generation consumers. - cyber world play an important role in modern marketing, enabling marketers to reach customers faster and more efficiently.
Mouakket, S.	2015	Focused on factors influencing continuance intention to use social network sites. Used the example of Facebook.	-perceived usefulness, satisfaction, habit, enjoyment, and subjective norms explain 54.8% of the variance in continuance intention. -show that the effect of satisfaction on continuance intention is both direct and mediated by habit.
Hsiao, C.H., Chang, J.J. and Tang, K.Y.	2016	Focused on the influential factors in continuance usage of mobile social Apps	-the continuance usage of social Apps is driven by users' satisfaction, tight connection with others, and hedonic motivation to use the Apps. -full mediation effects of satisfaction and habit were found between perceived usefulness and intention to continue use.
Bulut, Z.A. and Karabulut, A.N.,	2018	Focused on how eWOM aspects influence consumer repurchase intentions.	It was found that 2 eWOM receiving factors, eWOM quality and eWOM quantity, have positive influences on e-trust and ORPI.

Mathur, M.,	2019	Focused on the ramifications of perceived cybersecurity risk and how marketers can avert its negative marketing outcomes	Found that social media marketing capabilities enable firms in mitigating the adverse impact of cybersecurity risk in declining firm reputation and value.
Park, J., Hyun, H. and Thavisay, T	2020	Focused on consumer engagement in social media WOM and luxury purchase intention	It was found that social media WOM positively influences consumer luxury purchase intention.

Unlike traditional approaches of marketing, social media provides consumers with an interactive platform to connect with unknown individuals online in real time. Through these interactions, emotional attachment between brands and consumers is developed. When individuals join online communities, they seek social support, care, and friendship from members of that group (Gamboa and Gonçalves, 2014). These interactions help brands achieve relationship marketing targets and objectives (Barhemmati and Ahmad, 2015). Further, the emotional ties aid the purchase of products and services offered by companies. In a recent study, it was found that highly engaged consumers bring 23 percent more revenue to brands because of the emotional attachment. Thus, consumers bring in more spending on every purchase and the frequency of store visits increased (Shashank and Devaraj, 2018). This engagement with brands also leads customers to be actively involved in providing constructive feedback towards products and services.

Phillips and Noble (2007) argue that from the increase of social media platforms, the traditional mass media has become less effective as a marketing tool. The rise of innovative communication technology has transformed the attitude of potential consumers from being passive contributors to lively manipulators and influencers. As a result, consumers have become more inquisitive about acquiring information about products and their features before purchases are made. Forbes (2015) suggests that to stay ahead, companies must utilise the influence of social media to engage customers and enhance their products and brands. This indicates the relevance of social media marketing in providing information to other users, thereby shaping consumer preferences and purchase intentions.

Whilst studies reveal that repurchase behaviour is a result of consumer loyalty; this loyalty must not be taken for granted. It has always been assumed that consumer loyalty means continued engagement with the companies' products and services (Brodie, Ilic, Juric, and Hollebeek, 2013). However, loyalty may be lost if it means continuance with company's products and services within the online environment. There is still need for studies that analyse

the determinants that encourage customers to repurchase items online within the context of Nigeria. Although several businesses have found difficulty with establishing an online presence, they have maintained their physical stores. Whilst online platforms have also produced viral impact that offer great exposure to different products and services (Adeola, Hinson, and Evans, 2020), there is scepticism regarding online purchases within Nigeria. However, Nigerian consumers have a good presence on social media for social interaction purposes. This is used for social interactions and information sharing, and less for executing transactions because of cybersecurity concerns. Although cybersecurity is important for any organization, firms have little understanding of the ramifications of perceived cybersecurity risk and how marketers can avert its negative marketing outcomes (Mathur, 2019). It is also important to understand that social media marketing capabilities enable firms in mitigating the adverse impact of cybersecurity risk in declining firm reputation and value (Grover, Chiang, Liang, and Zhang, 2018).

Given the growth in use of mobile devices, and increasing attention paid to social media marketing (Poushter, Bishop, and Chwe, 2018; Chugh and Ruhi, 2018), there is a need to understand the role of social media on customer repurchase intention. Contending with this, Kim, Ji, Oh, Hwang, Park, and del Pobil (2020) point out that smartphones have become an integral part of our daily lives, and this has led to the rapid growth of the smartphone market. The growth in the smartphone market, and other mobile devices entails increased use of social media (Tabassum and Ahmed, 2020).

Studies have investigated the role of electronic word of mouth (EWOM) on customer repurchase intention (Aakash and Aggarwal, 2019; Ho and Chung, 2020). For instance, Aakash and Aggarwal (2019) found that EWOM are positively related to repurchase intention. Studies have also report that mobile apps' customer engagement positively affects customer equity, and this enhances the repurchase intention of existing customers (Ho and Chung, 2020). Some suggest that social media is used to build trust, and the interactional activities are important for customer repurchase intentions (Du, Xu, Tang, and Jiang, 2020).

Scholars have focused attention on the impact of social media on offline and online purchases (Bigne, Andreu, Hernandez, and Ruiz, 2018). The literature reports that interpersonal offline influences (e.g. friends, relatives, and family) have a significant effect on online repurchase intentions and WOM (Bihne et al., 2018; Yin, Wang, Xia, and Gu, 2019). However, this had no effect on e-WOM. This is important in that these offline influences help to be trust for

specified online purchases. It was also found that external offline influences (e.g. media and experts) only affect consumer intentions to recommend future purchases but had no effect on online repurchase intentions or WOM. These findings amplify the importance of interpersonal offline influences that direct traffic to specific online platforms (Marín-López, Zych, Monks, and Ortega-Ruiz, 2019). These offline interpersonal interactions can also be amplified on social media platforms (Page, 2013). What is important is that social media interactions enhance trust, which further increases repurchase intentions (Chong, Lacka, Boying, and Chan, 2018). Studies also reveal that social media marketing and price promotion have significant effects on customer satisfaction (Hanaysha, 2017). It follows that when a customer is satisfied with a product or service, they tend to re-use the respective product or service (Agnihotri, Dingus, Hu, and Krush, 2016). In so doing, the customer contributes to the sales and performance of the business. In this sense, this helps to increase online repurchase intentions (Charoensukmongkol and Sasatanun, 2017).

Though the use of social media is on the increase within Nigeria (Omotosho, 2020; Isah, and Ogundele, 2020), there are concerns that the use of social media is not reflected by online repurchase intentions (Wali, Cyprian, and Nkpurukwe, 2020).

2.4.3 The role of (CRI) upon online firm's sales performance

It is important to understand the extent to which CRI determinants can affect sales. Company sales are affected by several elements. Understanding the effect of CRI on sales performance may aid firms to use online platforms as a source of competitive advantage for their businesses. Previous studies suggest that customer repurchase intention on the online platforms plays a role in the success of a business (Bulut and Karabulut, 2018). Other factors affecting purchase intentions include to consider include service quality, equity and value, customer satisfaction, past loyalty, expected switching cost and brand preference (Hellier, 2003). The service quality of an online business can play a major role in determining the likelihood of a customer returning to an online store or referring potential customers (Mensah and Mensah, 2018).

Present research suggests that in a transaction-based environment, elevated emotions such as customer delight represent a more powerful predictor of repurchase intentions (Meyer, 2017). Equity and value also play a role in online sales performance. Scholars also suggest that a brand's online presence, particularly their social presence, can be an asset that builds brand equity, adding value to the consumer and the brand (Smith, 2016). This is increasingly important because of the growth and reach of social media. It provides a tool for brands to

interact with customers. This fosters growth and the opportunity for customer repurchases because of a personal relationship with the brand established. Customer satisfaction is the frontline of a business. An online store with a great frontline further promotes possibility of customers returning to make a purchase. According to Bai et al., (2008), customer satisfaction has a direct and positive impact on purchase intentions. Online stores have been known to offer loyalty programs to customers for several reasons including long term customers reward, repeated purchase, among others. The loyalty rewards are usually in form of discount codes, gift cards, and others. This allows the customer to know that the merchant appreciates their business, hence making them return for more purchases (Yuan, Lin, Filieri, Liu, and Zheng, 2020). Switching costs are the conveniences or inconveniences that a customer incurs for switching to a different brand. It can be in the form of reduced shipping cost, lower costs, and so forth.

This can improve a customer's loyalty and tendency to repurchase from a merchant. If the switching cost is high, the customer is likely to repurchase from a known merchant. If the switching cost is low, or a high one-time payment and the new merchant provides better service the customer has a high tendency to switch (Nguyen, de Leeuw, and Dullaert, 2018). Branding can range from design uniqueness, quality, quantity, and so forth. This can be fostered by social media relationship with customers. Previous studies suggest that around 59% of shoppers prefer to buy new products from brands they are familiar with, 21% purchase a new product because it was from a brand they liked (Xu et al., 2011). In this sense, branding is interlinked with sales performance and customer retention.

Previous studies suggest that recommendations will aid companies plan better. This is important when there are concerns about customer repurchase intentions. Trust in the recommendations will be developed over time. This is a result of collecting data from internet shoppers, analysing it, and then developing new understandings that can add value to the overall sales performance of the company. Previous research suggests that word of mouth is more effective than other types of marketing (Seiler, Yao, and Wang, 2017). Whether compared to traditional advertising, media mentions, or promotional events, word of mouth is more useful in creating new users and customers (Hess, 2008). Some of the key studies in this area are summarised in table 2.4.

Studies have focused more on the effect of repurchase intentions on firm performance within the physical stores (Han, Quan, Gil-Cordero, Sánchez, and Yu, 2021). There is a need for more

studies the relationship between organisational performance, and online repurchase intentions. Moreover, there is a dearth of studies in this area within the Nigerian context.

Table 2. 4: Summary of key studies on effect of CRI on a firm's performance

Author (s)	Date	Study focus	Key findings
Schlosser, A.E., White, T.B. and Lloyd, S.M.	2006	Focused on converting web site visitors into buyers. The intention was to understand how web site investment increases consumer trusting beliefs and online purchase intentions	It was found that: - trusting beliefs are most strongly related to online purchase intentions: ability. -These effects were strongest when consumers' goals were to search rather than to browse and when purchases involved risk
Bai, B., Law, R. and Wen, I.	2008	Focused on the impact of website quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intentions	It was found that: -website quality has a direct and positive impact on customer satisfaction -customer satisfaction has a direct and positive impact on purchase intentions.
Sparks, B.A. and Browning, V.	2011	Focused on the impact of online reviews on hotel booking intentions and perception of trust.	It was found that: -Consumers seem to be more influenced by early negative information, especially when the overall set of reviews is negative. -Positively framed information together with numerical rating details increases both booking intentions and consumer trust.
San Martín, S., López-Catalán, B. and Ramon-Jeronimo, M.A.	2012	Factors determining firms' perceived performance of mobile commerce	It was found that: -the perception of performance by firms engaging in m-commerce depends on the extent to which firms' activity fits mobile business, technological competence and customer value for the firm
Cui, G., Lui, H.K. and Guo, X.	2012	Focused on the effect of online consumer reviews on new product sales	It was found that: - the volume of reviews has a significant effect on new product sales in the early period and such effect decreases over time. -the percentage of negative reviews has a greater effect than that of positive reviews, confirming the negativity bias.
Kim, S. and Park, H.	2013	Effects of various characteristics of social commerce (s-commerce) on consumers' trust and trust performance	It was found that: -all the characteristics of s-commerce (except for economic feasibility) had significant effects on trust. -trust had significant effects on purchase and WOM intentions.
Rishika, R., Kumar, A., Janakiraman, R. and Bezawada, R.	2013	The effect of customers' social media participation on customer visit frequency and profitability	It was found that: -customer participation in a firm's social media efforts leads to an increase in the frequency of customer visits. -participation effect is greater when there are high levels of activity in the social media site and for customers who exhibit a strong patronage with the firm, buy premium products, and exhibit lower levels of buying focus and deal sensitivity. -the above set of results holds for customer profitability as well.

Kim, W.G., Lim, H. and Brymer, R.A.	2015	Focused on the effectiveness of managing social media on hotel performance	It was found that: - overall ratings are the most salient predictor of hotel performance, followed by response to negative comments. -the overall ratings and the higher the response rate to negative comments, the higher the hotel performance
Liu, Y., Li, X. and Dong, M.C.	2019	Focused on account managers and customer repurchase intention	Found that account managers' functional customer orientation can directly increase customers repurchase intention
Han, H., Quan, W., Gil-Cordero, E., Sánchez, J.P.C. and Yu, J.,	2021	Focuses on the process via which travelers show their willingness to repurchase in the context of airport retail store	it was found that the perceived performance, utilitarian value, hedonic value, and satisfaction evaluation of airport retail stores play a crucial role in determining traveler willingness to repurchase

2.5 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989) was developed to study and identify what make individuals repurchase items online. To predict more reasons why people, purchase goods and services online, the TAM theory was augmented and new variables like privacy and security were added (Vijayasarathy, 2004). Similarly, more variables like technology anxiety and innovativeness were also added. Razaee et al. (2014), conducted a study on Malaysian consumers, and then extended the TAM theory by adding perceived trust, value, privacy concern and internet literacy. Additionally, Smith et al., (2011), studied how culture could play a role in influencing customer to shop online by using the TAM model. Within the literature, the TAM model has been used to predict consumer repurchase intentions to shop online (Lin, Fang, and Tu, 2010; Chen, 2012; Ali, Poulouva, Akbar, Javed, and Danish, 2020). Others have used an extended technology acceptance model to test consumer purchase intentions (Wang, Wang, Wang, Wei, and Wang, 2020). The constructs on this model have been tried and tested by different scholars over the years (Brusch and Rappel, 2020; Saprikis, Avlogiaris, and Katarachia, 2021), and this makes this model appropriate to explore consumer repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context.

Subsequently, the parsimonious nature of TAM has been identified as a limitation by Tong et al., (2010). However, some studies have validated the existing dimensions of TAM but have not extensively exhausted all the possible factors that are associated with customer repurchase intentions (Wallace and Sheetz, 2014; Samarasinghe and Silva, 2019; Scherer, Siddiq, and Tondeur, 2020). These eight existing independent variables will be analysed to identify how well they encourage customers to repurchase items online and new ones will be introduced covering more and providing a clearer understanding of other elements that can instigate customers to repurchase goods online with Nigeria as a case study. Finally, testing the influence

or impact of each one of these determinants on customers in Nigeria will aid in understanding how well they should be taken into consideration in the future (Lee *et al.*, 2009).

2.5.1 Perceived value

Perceived value is the result of marketing activities and when it pertains to relationship marketing (Moliner *et al.*, 2007; Dam, 2020). Previous research reveals that perceived value has a link with customer satisfaction (Hume, 2008; Juliana, Djakasaputra, and Pramono, 2020). Therefore, buyers may cognitively mix their perceptions with what they had to give up and what they get to in a bid to receive a specific service (Ha and Janda, 2008; Salehzadeh, and Pool, 2017). Hume (2008) proposes that perceived value is important in relation to customer repurchase intentions. Therefore, within the Nigerian context, it is important to determine if a purchased item or service that offered a good level of value, will encourage repurchase behaviour. Following from this, it is hypothesised that:

H1. Perceived value influences customer online repurchase behaviour.

2.5.2. Perceived ease of use

Perceived ease of use is more concerned with the degree to which consumers believe that their online shopping experience will be easy, free of any hassle and effortless (Chiu *et al.*, 2009; Suleman, 2019). People that use the internet for shopping range from novice to expert. In this context, the deal breaker for consumer repurchase with any online firm might just be the extent to which the website or online platform is easy to use or access (Liu, Chen, Sun, Wible, and Kuo, 2010; Sheppard and Vibert, 2019). If customers find it difficult to use, or the description is not clear to understand or search too long for their desired product or service it may affect their repurchase behaviour. In this sense, the design of websites is a crucial component of the customer experience because this may have an influence customer repurchase behaviour.

Wen *et al* (2013) describes perceived ease of use as the degree to which a person believes that using a system would be free of effort. In relation to online shopping, this means that whenever a person feels at ease when using an online store for a business transaction, that customer will be more inclined to return for another transaction. Urhavi *et al.*, (2017) breaks down the meaning of “ease of use” in an online shopping world. They explain that an online store is easy to use when a customer finds it easy to do the basic activities in these websites. Activities such as easy search for products, easy checking out process, easy ability to modify items in shopping carts, easy checking out process and easy tracking process or even easy cancellations of items ordered. When an online store has all these features, it makes shopping easier for the customer

and gives the customer more chances to feel fulfilled and satisfied. These factors are critical for the online shopping experience.

Urhavi et al., (2017) suggests that when there is ease of use in an online store, other features become easier. Hence, he coined several terms such as “ease of search”, “ease of ordering”, “ease of modification”, “ease of payment”, “ease of tracking”, and “ease of cancellation”. The significance of these phrases means that when these features become easier, then it makes customers feel at ease when conducting online transactions (Vlaescu, Carlbring, Lunner, and Andersson, 2015; Grover, Kar, Janssen, and Ilavarasan, 2019). This enhances the chances of customer repurchase behaviour.

Consistent with the work of Urhavi et al., (2017), Wen et al (2013) highlighted that some of the many benefits that has been linked with online shopping in relation to perceived ease of use are the ease of information search, ease of ordering (at any time and at any location) and the overall ease of use of the online store’s website. Chao-Min *et al.*, (2009) defined perceived ease of use as the extent to which a customer believes that shopping online will be stress free and free of effort. They believe that when an online shopping web site is perceived to be easier to use, it is more likely to induce a perception of usefulness. Davis *et al.*, (1989) suggests that significant improvements in an online web site also becomes very vital and instrumental in contributing to increased performances of the website. This in turn, has a positive effect on the perceived usefulness of the website.

For Chao-Min *et al.*, (2009), the perceived ease of use is also considered as a factor of post-adoption expectation. In this sense, perceived ease of use is expected to have a positive effect on customer purchase intentions. In fact, Chao-Min *et al.*, (2009), found that perceived ease of use is positively correlated with a customer’s intentions to return for further purchases. Similarly, perceived ease of use was also positively correlated to perceived usefulness. In summary, perceived ease of use is important because a person who finds an online website easy to use would always find it easy to conduct a transaction. Customers that are satisfied with the website ease of use are thus more likely to refer others, thereby increasing traffic for this website. Following from this, it is hypothesised that:

H2. Perceived ease of use influences customer online repurchase behaviour.

2.5.3 Company's brand and reputation

A company's brand and reputation define how customers perceive a firm's business model regarding customer welfare (Hess, 2008; Faramarzi, and Bhattacharya, 2021). A brand distinguishes businesses from its competitors. The American Marketing Association defines a brand as a name, term, design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies one seller's good or service as distinct from those of other sellers. A brand is necessary for quality and assurance in building trust (Yoon, 2002). In fact, brands are a good indicator of reliability for customer choice (Degeratu *et al.*, 2000; Yoon, 2002; Kostyra, Reiner, Natter, and Klapper, 2016). Trust is a psychological state comprising the intention to accept vulnerability based on positive expectations of the intentions or behaviours of another (Rousseau *et al.*, 1998, p. 395).

Brand strength is a key measurement tool of the demand on a business. Scholars suggest that a brand is a significant driver and determinant of online trust (Degeratu *et al.*, 2000; Yoon, 2002; Bulut and Karabulut, 2018). Consumers are becoming more aware of brands and their value and are driven to attach trust values to brands with greater strength (Yukov Bart 2005; Lude and Prügl, 2018). A customer's perception of a brand's ability to perform requirements to a desired standard, deliver on expectations and provide honest communication contributes to the perception of trust in that brand (Yannopoulou, Koronis and Elliott, 2011; Ebrahim, 2020). This has implications on improving the brand's strength and creating preference with the customer. Brand preference is the extent to which customer favours a business over another in their consideration set.

Brand strength is a key determinant of customer repurchase intention through trust. For example, smaller book retailers suffer compared to rival brand Amazon.com that has a much greater brand strength and therefore enjoys a greater level of trust (Pan *et al.*, 2003). Depending on the price of the product or service, brand strength plays an even more crucial role. Bart (2005) advocates that the importance of brand strength relates directly to the value of the items. Items such as financial services, computers and other high involvement/high-ticket items see a higher reliance on brand strength to trust the quality, performance and information provided by a business.

Businesses are becoming more aware that the personal evaluations of their brands can greatly influence customer perceptions of their products and services. Businesses are now able to increase customer satisfaction evaluations from improved brand strength targets. If customers have negative predisposition towards brands, their trust and satisfaction in that brand could be

damaged. The strength of brand preference has a direct positive effect on customer repurchase intentions. Brand preference is linked directly to brand satisfaction levels and repeat purchase intentions. Customers put in effort to reduce the risk of service use (Murray, 1991; Buttle and Maklan, 2019) by buying from brands with great strength and repeat the purchase from brands that have provided satisfaction (Yannopoulou, Koronis and Elliott, 2011; Sürücü, Öztürk, Okumus, and Bilgihan, 2019).

Reputation on the other hand can be described as the customers' perceptions on how businesses treat their customers and cater for them and their welfare (Hess, 2008). Reputation is also evaluated to be the extent to which customers believe a business is honest and concerned about customers (Doney and Cannon, 1997; Buttle and Maklan, 2019). The reputation of a business greatly influences the customers' predispositions towards a business and this in turn directly affects trust (Quelch and Klein 1996; Lohse and Spiller 1998; Alalwan, Dwivedi, Rana, and Algharabat, 2018). The main sources of information used in reputation development are from direct experiences (Sabater and Sierrathe 2005). When customers lack first-hand information and experience about a business, the reputation development is run based on second-hand knowledge and impressions from third parties (Gefen, 2000; Ravasi, Rindova, Etter, and Cornelissen, 2018).

Businesses are insulated from negative circumstance when they have excellent reputation and are perceived by customers to have great customer care (Hess, 2008; Etter, Ravasi, and Colleoni, 2019). In fact, Hess (2008) suggests that brand reputation has a buffering effect that cushions businesses. In this context, it is highly likely that businesses with outstanding reputation will enjoy greater repurchase intentions.

H3. Firm reputation influences online repurchase intentions

2.5.4 Privacy

Privacy helps to ensure that online shopping is secure and free from cybercrime (Chiu et al., 2009; Tawalbeh, Muheidat, Tawalbeh, and Quwaider, 2020). According to Hoffman et al., (1999) privacy is the amount of protection given to customer information. It is mainly concerned with consumer data and the rights consumers have over their data. The processing of information has made using the internet complex and needing of privacy (Atlam and Wills, 2020). Consumers constantly struggle with how their personal data is accessed and used online. In Nigeria, numerous cases of fraud and cybercrime have been reported and it is evident that

privacy may be a factor affecting customer repurchase intentions when considering online retail shops (Miyazaki and Fernandez, 2001; Usman, 2018).

Studies suggests that people are increasingly concerned about the way their personal information is used. This deep concern consumers have about privacy affects the willingness to engage with online purchases (Liao, Liu, and Chen, 2011; Cottrill, Jacobs, Markovic, and Edwards, 2020). In e-commerce, these concerns have been expressed as (1) the unauthorized gathering and sharing of personal information and behaviours to third parties with marketing related interests, (2) control over the use of personal data, (3) knowledge of privacy practices, and (4) the use of personal information (Malhotra *et al.*, 2004; Miyazaki and Fernandez, 2001). To further assert the importance of privacy, Schlegelmilch and Öberseder (2010) argued that one of the three main e-commerce ethical issues is privacy.

Privacy reflects a user's concerns about possible loss of privacy (Xu *et al.*, 2011; Wottrich, van Reijmersdal, and Smit, 2018). The prevalence of technology has fuelled an increase in concern over privacy as technology makes it easier for information to be digitalised providing an easier dissemination method where internet users can search and collect information about individuals online. It is often the case that digitised information cannot be deleted and so certain individuals have their information existing in the digital world always (Malhotra *et al.*, 2004). The growth of technology has made more online consumers aware of the lack of privacy protection by some e-commerce brands and makes them increasingly aware of the possibility of invasion of their privacy.

The targeting of certain individuals from privacy slippage and information exploitation because of the vast threats that targets consumers online also increases the risk associated with the disclosure of personal information online (Xu *et al.*, 2011; Bryce and Fraser, 2014; Youn and Shin, 2020). Consumers hesitate to use some offered services on the internet due to the risks associated with the disclosure of their personal information and privacy. Hoffman *et al.*, (1999) suggests that one of the main reasons' consumers purchase or repurchase from a store online is due to the lack of trust in the safety of their information because some online vendors sell their private information to third parties without express permission from the user.

Collier and Bienstock (2006) suggests that a customer's concern with privacy stems from the lack of assurance in the privacy and protection of credit card information. If this information is not secured, it may be leaked to potential hackers of less secure brands. These concerns regarding internet privacy have been scaled into two streams (Hong and Thong, 2013), viz,

interaction management and information management (Hong and Thong, 2013). The significance of privacy concerns is conveyed by Udo (2001), who suggests that protection of privacy is the greatest concern of internet purchasers. In fact, Udo (2001) found that there is a strongly correlation between the reluctance to repurchase online to doubts over privacy protection. This influenced consumer willingness to repurchase online.

To mitigate this, Culnan (2000) advocates the posting of brand privacy policies and displaying of privacy seals to communicate their use of information and personal data. Accordingly, to improve a consumer trust in the fair handling and security of their data, Ye and Zhong (2011) recommends stringent mechanisms for access control to consumer data and information. This adds a layer of credibility to brands repurchase intentions. Wang *et al.*, (2003) examined this relationship and concludes that brands deemed credible had a positive effect on consumer repurchase intentions. Similarly, studies have also found that the certification of fair data use can outweigh consumers' concerns about information sharing (Culnan and Armstrong, 1999; Dinev and Hart, 2006). Consumer's privacy concerns play an important role in their repurchase intentions. Previous research suggests that consumers' observations regarding privacy have an important and positive consequence on customer repurchase intentions (Bart *et al.*, 2005, Roman, 2007; Song and Luximon, 2021).

H4: Privacy concerns influence customer repurchase intention

2.5.5 Trust

Trust is perceived as a category of certain beliefs which deal mainly with the competence, integrity, and benevolence of another party (Suh and Han, 2003; Rehman, Ali, Syed, Khan, and Ali, 2018). Previous research suggests that for web-based vendors, trust is a crucial element for the widespread adoption of electronic commerce (McKnight and Choudhury, 2002; Kim, Nam, and Kim, 2019). As indicated in the previous paragraph on privacy, there have been several cases of unethical use of customer information online and this has affected consumer confidence in terms of competence, integrity, and benevolence of Nigerian e-commerce companies. Some of the outcomes of this lack of trust include the development of the 'pay-on-delivery' business model that allows consumers to pay for products and sometimes even services at the point of delivery (Ayogu, 2017).

Although this has helped reduce the risk of exposure for consumers, such practices go against the standard e-commerce growth models thereby impeding the expected growth of network effects. This point is further corroborated by a parallel study on the impact of trust on the

interaction between SMEs and banks in Italy where access to finance is considered as a key growth factor in the start-up ecosystem. Howorth and Moro (2005), argue that trust reduces complexity and is the 'lubricant' in exchanges, being a building block of social capital. Where trust is lacking, accelerated growth and ubiquitous adoption of e-commerce would mostly remain a dream. Similarly,

Gefen, Karahanna and Straub (2003) posit that online trust is built through the belief that the merchant has no benefit in defrauding the customer; the belief that the platform has in-built safety mechanisms; the platform's interface being typical and standard; and the platform's consistent ease of use. At first glance, it is observed that the key elements highlighted by their study comprise intangible beliefs. These include self-reinforcing with repeat purchases, and tangible features, both of which, can be objectively experienced by consumers. Nonetheless, these factors are well aligned with those mentioned earlier as factors that influence customer repurchase intention.

In a similar vein, Molla and Licker (2001) found that customers require a certain level of security. This is important to secure sensitive data provided on online platforms. Thus, trust is of essence. Molla and Licker (2001) suggest that security and privacy are key trust issues affecting the future of e-commerce. In emerging economies like Nigeria, with consistently growing penetration of mobile devices and the internet, one would also expect a corresponding growth in e-commerce user adoption (Forenbacher, Husnjak, Cvitić, and Jovović, 2019). This however has not been the case (Han and Noh, 1999) as customers are still significantly reluctant to trust e-commerce payment systems. Thus, trust may be a key factor influencing customer repurchase intentions for e-commerce. It is hypothesised that:

H5: Trust may largely influence online repurchase behaviour.

2.5.6 Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness is defined by Urvashi *et al.*, (2017) as the extent to which a customer believes that shopping online will make the performance of their business or online transactions better. They believe that customers generally form behavioural intentions towards online shopping based on a mental assessment on how their shopping performance can be made better. Like the work of Urvashi *et al.*, (2017), Chao-Min *et al.*, (2009) defined perceived usefulness as the degree to which a person believes that using a system would improve the performance of his or her job. Perceived usefulness is an important predictor of behavioural intention in TAM and is the leading factor that affects the attitude towards online purchases.

Burke (1996) suggests that perceived usefulness is the main requirement for mass market technology acceptance. This is dependent upon the customers' expectations about how technology can enhance and make their lives easier. Wen *et al.*, (2013) posits that perceived usefulness has a significant effect on consumers online shopping intentions. Findings from their study suggests that perceived usefulness correlates with the general utilitarian nature of consumers online. Drawing from their findings, Wen *et al.*, (2013) point out that online vendors should integrate new features that will improve the efficiency of online shopping. In fact, they also point out that a search mechanism can not only provide extensive relevant information, but also enables the comparison of different products which in turn helps its users to make the best decisions in the best way possible.

Wen *et al.*, (2013) stated that the realization that the intention to shop or do a transaction is not the same thing as actually purchasing the product. This realization is important because a survey they carried out with the Chinese online market showed that about 50 percent of online customers do not actually finish their purchases and abandon the shopping carts (China Business Daily 2008). This indicates that the online customers might be experiencing some issue or problem, and as such, abandon their shopping carts (Mulpuru *et al.*, 2010; Ventre and Kolbe, 2020).

The issue with online customers abandoning their carts before purchases highlights the problems that online vendors face in understanding what could be the possible reasons for the frustrations and lack of conviction to place a purchase (Mulpuru *et al.*, 2010; Mou, Shin, and Cohen, 2017). The opportunity for online vendors to recuperate sales is lost. In this context, there is greater need to keep abreast with competitor prices, clarify shipping expenses, and ensure that timely deliveries are made. Further, there is even greater need to ensure that out of stock situations are prevented. There is a greater need to determine the causes and reasons customers abandon their online shopping carts. This will help to resolve issues that cause customers to abandon their carts, thereby, encouraging customers to complete their online purchases.

Szajna (1996) found that perceived usefulness is a very solid and consistent indicator of usage intentions over time. Ease of use was found to have a declining effect, which inevitably gets to be non-important at a later point in time with repeated usage. This has incited the IS researches to drop the ease of use construct when studying later-stage usage or continuance. Gefen *et al.*, (2003) suggest that perceived usefulness strengthens an online shopper's

intentions to continue using a particular web site such that “when a person accepts a new information system, he or she is more willing to alter practices and expend time and effort to use it”.

Talal (2011) suggests that just as perceived usefulness is the strongest indicator of intention in TAM, it continues to be a more solid indicator of continuance intention than satisfaction when TAM combined with ECT. The relative dominance of usefulness clarifies its role as a significant driver in continuance decisions about comparisons of utilitarian value over hedonic value. Previous studies suggest that perceived usefulness has a significant positive relation with customer satisfaction (Liao, Chen, and Yen, 2007; Morgan-Thomas and Veloutsou, 2013; Singh and Sinha, 2020). Following from this, it is hypothesised that:

H6. Perceived usefulness of the website may influence online repurchase intentions.

2.5.7 Enjoyment

Riska *et al.*, (2016) defines perceived enjoyment in an online shopping world as the level of satisfaction a customer would feel during the online shopping experience. This enjoyment is derived from a specific website’s capability of bringing them joy and good customer experience. Chao-Min et al (2008) defined enjoyment as the extent to which the experience of shopping online is perceived to be enjoyed or interesting or fun to the individual engaged in the act of shopping. In fact, when customers enjoy the online shopping experience it keeps them more interested because they are intrinsically motivated. This encourages them to either stay on the page or engage in repurchase behaviour.

The literature suggests that there is a strong correlation between a customer’s enjoyment and the customer’s intention to shop online (Hong and Thong, 2013). Scholars also point out that if a customer enjoys the experience of shopping online, he/she would be inclined to return to the online store to do more shopping instead of physically going to the store (Hong and Thong, 2013). On the contrary, if a customer has a poor experience with shopping online, the chances of that customer returning for another purchase or even shopping with that store entirely might be reduced (Hong and Thong, 2013; Oghazi, Karlsson, Hellström, and Hjort, 2018). It is every business ‘aim to ensure that customers are satisfied with their products and services either in store or online. This means that it is of utmost significance that every business has an online presence for customers to be able to make purchases. Within this, the customer’s experience or feeling of pleasure or enjoyment whilst engaging in online shopping is important (Howorth and Moro, 2005; Kim, Yoo, and Yang, 2020).

Therefore, a good-looking and customer friendly website is of importance. This can be used to attract customers and ensure that customers have fun whilst shopping on the online platform. Riska *et al.*, (2016) suggests that it is very important for online shop owners to make the processes for the online shopping on their websites very easy and less complicated. The intention is to ensure customer's enjoyment and improve online shopping intentions (Hwang, and Oh, 2020). Following from this, it is hypothesised that:

H7. Enjoyment prompts customer repurchase intention

2.5.8 Fulfilment

According to Riska *et al.*, (2016), fulfilment can be described as the level to which an online store owner's promises about delivery of service or product is fulfilled. This is one of the critical factors that affects a customer's judgement, and often used as a measure to determine whether a product or service meets customer expectations. These expectations can be in terms of quality and quantity. Therefore, whenever a customer places an order for a product from an online store, a psychological contract between the customer and the online vendor stating that the online vendor would deliver the product or service as promised has been signed. Similarly, if this contract is broken and not met, it leaves the customer unfulfilled or dissatisfied (Riska *et al.*, 2016).

Saunders and Thornhill (2003) suggest that if the expectations of a customer are not fulfilled by the vendor, it breaks trust. This might result in the customer not returning for further purchases. This suggests that there is a correlation between fulfilment and trust. In this vein, Bart *et al.*, (2005) point out that a customer who deals with an online vendor mentally feels the same way as dealing with the vendor in person. This means that a customer would be willing to put his/her trust in the online store as the same way in which he would be willing to put trust on a vendor that is met physically. Similarly, if this trust is broken, it reduces the chance of customer repurchase intentions.

Consistent with Bart *et al.*, (2005), Roman (2007) suggests that fulfilment is one of the key ethical factors that develops and maintains customer loyalty to a store. In fact, it is said that customer loyalty is essential for the success of a business (Bart *et al.*, 2005; Suhartanto, Helmi Ali, Tan, Sjahroeddin, and Kusdiby, 2019). However, loyalty would only come if the customers are fulfilled with the service or product (Woratschek, Horbel, and Popp, 2020). It is from fulfilment that trust is earned. This suggests that there is a positive correlation between

fulfilment and a customer's trust in an online vendor (Riska *et al.*, 2016). Following from this, it is hypothesised that:

H8. Consumer fulfilment may largely influence online repurchase intentions

2.5.9 System availability and functionality

System availability and functionality are key measures of e-commerce success (Delone and McLean, 2004; Wang, Wang, and Liu, 2016). The system availability and functionality can be evaluated using measures such as 24-hour availability, page loading time, user interface, system stability and architecture (Han and Noh, 1999; Cui, Mou, Cohen, and Liu, 2019). These are the quality indicators. Previous studies suggest that there is a significant disparity between the features prioritised by web design experts and those prioritised by consumers (Turban and Gehrke, 2000; Johnson, 2020).

In a country like Nigeria, which does not rank very high on the global scale of customer service, e-commerce companies must ensure that the first interaction users have with their platforms are positive enough to encourage a revisit. Cao *et al.*, (2005) used the IS success model to investigate the factors that impact upon website quality. They found that to include system quality, information quality, service quality and attractiveness. These factors of system availability and functionality were also found to be major influence upon customer repurchase intentions.

When customers shop online, they prefer stores which are easy to navigate, provide support, and have previous customer reviews (Moula and Licker, 2001; Meng, Dipietro, Gerdes, Kline, and Avant, 2018). This can be attributed to trust. If a customer shops online, they need to be sure that their money is being spent where they can get their goods in a timely manner and in good condition. Considering that the merchant who is eager to sell will always upsell his/her products, the only way to be sure is from reading reviews from customers who have previously purchased from that customer (Ridings and Gefen, 2004; Maslowska, Kim, Malthouse, and Viswanathan, 2019). Another important aspect to consider is the ease with which a customer can navigate a website to find a product. Most customers usually do not want to spend most of their time surfing through a website, just like people do not want to go to grocery stores and spend endless hours looking for products (Ridings and Gefen, 2004).

The ease with which an e-commerce store can be navigated is important as this provides shopping convenience for the customer. Finding a product easily also means saving them time

which can be used to browse other products. Customers also find it very useful if the site where they are spending their money has support which can help them in: locating a product, providing information regarding an out of stock order, providing information on acceptable payments, help customer in locating a product, provide information regarding price matching (Qaoili, 2010), and so forth. The support provided by the e-commerce store can be in the form of phone support, email, and other support related mechanisms. The timeline for the response can also be a factor in a customer's shopping experience. The time it takes to respond to a customer query can determine whether a customer purchases a product.

As an online merchant it is important to ensure that your online store is always available to your customers. If a customer repeatedly experiences inconveniences like page unavailable, server error, product not available, card not accepted and more (Yang, 2012; Wagner, Schramm-Klein, and Steinmann, 2020), then, there is increased likelihood of failing to make a sale. Customers are also less likely to return to that store or refer friends or family. This can give the impression that the website is not secure, and no customer would like to run through the risk of inputting their card details there.

Providing multiple payment channels for internet shoppers is essential and should be standard on a website. Some individuals do not have the luxury of certain payment methods, and others do not like some of the payment methods. As a merchant, being able to provide customers with multiple payment options during checkout is important. Some of the available options include PayPal, VISA, Mastercard and more (Gefen *et al.*, 2003; Liao and Yang, 2020).

Customers have different perceptions about payment methods. They believe that some payment methods are more secure than others. Some customers do not like to put in some of their information online for fear of security breaches and theft. Also, some customers in certain locations do not have certain payment options available in their location. These factors are essential in the functionality of a website. Considering this, a website should have multiple payment options (Delone and McLean, 2004; Brand, Schwanen, and Anable, 2020).

As per The Telegraph, "The average person has five social media accounts and spends around 1 hour and 40 minutes browsing these networks every day, accounting for 28pc of the total time spent on the internet" (Telegraph, 2015). Taking this into consideration, it is important that an e-commerce business has its products available on multiple sales channels. This includes but is not limited to Facebook, Wish, and many others.

Previous studies suggest that that young adults use their smartphones roughly twice as much as they estimate that they do (Aden *et al.*, 2006; Odgers and Jensen, 2020). In fact, these young adults used their phones an average of five hours a day. This is roughly one-third of their total waking hours (huffingtonpost, 2015). It is essential for an online store to be available for users to access on their mobile devices. The ease of accessibility of a business from a mobile device is essential.

Of the five hours people spend on their mobile device 33.33% of the time is spent on social media (Singla and Arora, 2015). This statistic amplifies the importance of online availability of a business. Following from this, it is hypothesised that:

H9. System availability and functionality may instigate customer repurchase intention.

2.6 New determinants / Factors for Nigerian Online Firms

To create ideal strategies that can increase customer's intention to repurchase items online, it is paramount to understand the factors that can promote this drive. Discussed above are factors according to TAM model (Davis, 1989), that can influence consumers to purchase items online. However, despite explaining the relevance of the aforementioned factors, this study introduces new factors than can also motivate or instigate customers to buy goods and services on the online platforms. These are contextually based factors that are more relevant to the Nigerian online marketplace.

2.6.1 Contact

Contact is concerned with the availability of help, support and assistance provided to customers through online chat representatives, emails, social network platforms or telephones (Parasuraman *et al.*, 2005; Dilkes-Frayne, Savic, Carter, Kokanović, and Lubman, 2019). According to Collier and Bienstock (2006), the provision of various means of communications for customers to contact online vendors and receive answers to their queries is crucial for the customer experience. This helps to enhance service quality and user experience. Moreover, customers who do not receive answers to their questions or who do not have their queries resolved on time could easily become frustrated and switch to other products or services. Hence, providing enough information on the company website and creating functional methods of communication will be a good way to retain customers and encourage online repurchase (Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

2.6.2 After-Sales Customer Care and General Satisfaction

This factor refers to the way customers are taken care of after they have paid for items online and the general feeling of satisfaction derived by customers from the online shopping experience (Chen *et al.*, 2012; Carlson, Rahman, Taylor, and Voola, 2019). In attracting new customers and retaining old customers, customer satisfaction is one that must be carefully examined and applied by Nigeria online companies (Yiu *et al.*, 2007). The Nigerian key ecommerce players need to put a lot of emphasis on the after sales care because this can increase retention and determine customer intention to repurchase.

The after-sales care variables like, speedy delivery, customer product or service feedback and follow up, emails to customer with new items and invitations to buy again are important (Tandon, Kiran, and Sah, 2018). The literature suggests that there is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and customer repurchase intention (Tsai and Huang, 2007). As such, Nigerian online vendors must seriously consider after sales care.

2.6.3 Responsiveness

Responsiveness is linked to the ways of handling problems effectively through the ecommerce website (Parasuraman *et al.*, 2005). In terms of determining e-service quality, responsiveness is unarguably one of the most important factors (Yang *et al.*, 2004; Shafiee and Bazargan, 2018). In the case where customers have any questions or problems, when interacting with e-commerce vendors it is crucial that they receive enough time and adequate support (Semeijn *et al.*, 2005; Taherdoost, 2018).

The building of trust can occur because of timely response and communication from online vendors (Moorman *et al.*, 1993). More so, it is highly likely that uncertainty can be diminished or avoided because of speedy response from online vendors. Moreover, these e-commerce vendors need to deliver good customer service by acting benevolently (Gummerus *et al.*, 2004). It is factors as these that are often found to be missing in many Nigerian online businesses.

Previous studies suggest that online responsiveness to customers influence online repurchases (Lee, 2005; Rita, Oliveira, and Farisa, 2019). Hence, the e-commerce entrepreneurs in Nigeria need to consider this factor to ensure that their customers are satisfied and that they return consistently to use their website.

2.6.4 Word of Mouth

Word of mouth is one of the most effective ways of recommendation or marketing a business (Dost, Phieler, Haenlein, and Libai, 2019). This can be attributed to the fact that the customer

is being referred by a trusted source. In doing this the referee helps to bridge the relationship between the customer and the merchant. The customer no longer depends on the reviews posted on websites which can be made up. Getting a recommendation from a friend or family member to patronize a merchant gives a sense of confidence and security.

The use of social influencers (SI) is essential for recommendations. Using a product from an online store without a formal recommendation can give customers confidence to visit an online store. Since the advent of social media, advertising power has been growing with social media influencers because of their large reach. This can be effective because an influencer can reach multiple customers in different locations (Chu, Lien, and Cao, 2019). More so, this saves time and money of trying to set up different advertisements for customers located in places. Similarly, Hsu *et al.*, (2013) draw scholarly attention to the value of bloggers who recommend a product and suggests that bloggers' electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) is a promising marketing strategy that can help to increase sales.

Another service which is essential to internet shoppers with regards to recommendations is being able to contact customers who previously left a product review. Online merchants like Amazon provide this option to their customers. This avails the customer the opportunity to contact previous buyers to provide first-hand user experience with the product they are looking to purchase. This approach is risky because some customers might not give good reviews based on their state of mind when they receive a product (Hsu et al., 2013). Also, some customers tend to provide reviews on products because the merchant did not accept a request.

Given that online purchases can be a financial risk because of security breaches, recommendations play a big role in putting customers at ease before taking such risks. According to Meyer (2017), consumer participation in using an RA (recommendation agents) leads to more satisfaction, greater trust, and higher purchase intentions. Product reviews are also very important for internet shoppers. Previous studies suggest that it is important to understand consumer usage and attitudes towards online reviews (Lee, Park and Han, 2008). Recent statistical evidence suggests that 90% of consumers read online reviews. More interestingly, 88% of those who read reviews trust the online reviews as much as personal recommendations. In other words, more people read reviews as part of their pre-purchase research before buying a product or service (Rudolf, 2015). In fact, on average, a one-star increase on Yelp leads to 5 to 9 percent increase in business's revenue, one negative review can cost you 30 customers (Rudolf, 2015). Based on this information, recommendations of any

form, whether reviews, word of mouth, use of social media influencers, and so forth, play a significant role in the success or failure of an online business.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

The concept of customer repurchase intention has been around for some years now. Previous studies have identified customers' internet profiles, customer online behaviour and the reasons customers go online to repurchase items (Davis, 1989; Turban, 2002; McKnight and Chervany, 2001; Gelbrich, Gätke, and Hübner, 2017). Several models and theories have been developed to help understand online customer repurchase behaviour. For instance, the TAM is one model that explores variables like trust, enjoyment, e-service quality amongst others (Davis, 1989).

However, TAM has its own downside. For instance, important factors such as customer satisfaction, customer traits, internet literacy, situational factors, and customer traits, are all missing. Other models were developed to include elements like innovativeness, customer loyalty and switching cost. This study examines some of the already existing determinants of customer repurchase intentions, as modelled by other researchers. To this, the study brings in contextual understandings from Nigeria. The conceptual model below shows the link between variables and links the new ones to the endpoint which is customer repurchase intention. Ultimately, the diagram reveals how each of these elements are interconnected and illustrates the relationship between each of the elements.

Figure 2. 1: Conceptual framework

Extending the traditional TAM model, the conceptual framework for this study introduces constructs such as trust, as well as privacy concerns. These are relevant in the Nigerian context of online because of cybersecurity issues. Other additional useful constructs in the Nigerian context include enjoyment, consumer fulfilment, system availability, and system functionality. Drawing from the literature (Omotayo and Omotope, 2018; Olaleye, Adeyeye, Efuntade, Arije, and Anifowose, 2020), these constructs helps us to understand consumer repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context. The adaptation of the TAM model is consistent with previous studies that added other constructs to the model to help address constructs in different contexts (Liu, Chen, Sun, Wible, and Kuo, 2010; Munoz-Leiva, Climent-Climent, and Liébana-Cabanillas, 2017; Phuong and Vinh, 2019; Baby and Kannammal, 2020).

Following from the conceptual framework, the hypothesis to be tested in this study are as illustrated in table 2.5.

Table 2. 5: Alternative Hypothesis

Alternative Hypothesis
H1: Perceived value influences customer online repurchase behavior
H2: Perceived ease of use influences customer online repurchase behaviour.
H3: Brand reputation influences online repurchase intentions
H4: Privacy concerns influence customer repurchase intention
H5: Trust may largely influence online repurchase behaviour.
H6: Perceived usefulness of the website may influence online repurchase intentions.
H7: Enjoyment prompts customer repurchase intention
H8: Consumer fulfilment influence online repurchase intentions
H9: System availability and functionality influences customer repurchase intention.
<i>H10: Other factors influences repurchase intention (efficient delivery, contact etc)</i>

In developing the conceptual framework, insights were drawn from different authors, as illustrated in table 2.6.

Table 2. 6: Supporting literature for conceptual framework

Author (s)	Date	Work done
Yang, S., Park, J. and Park, J.,	2007	Used a modified-technology acceptance model (TAM) with two added antecedents such as information search motivation and perceived risk) to examine whether online shopping channels would be adopted by college students.
Lee, M.C.,	2009	Used an integrated approach of TAM and theory of planned behaviour and found that the intention to use online banking is adversely affected mainly by the security/privacy risk. It was also found that financial risk and is positively affected mainly by perceived benefit, attitude and perceived usefulness.

Liu, I.F., Chen, M.C., Sun, Y.S., Wible, D. and Kuo, C.H	2010	extended the external variables of the TAM model, as well as the Perceived Variables.
Lala, G.,	2014	Provided an overview on the emergence and development of the technology acceptance model (TAM) by Fred Davis, and summarised the evolution of TAM, its key applications, extensions, limitations and criticisms.
Munoz-Leiva, F., Climent-Climent, S. and Liébana-Cabanillas, F	2017	Developed a technology acceptance model that integrates the innovation diffusion theory, perceived risk and trust in the classic TAM model. The intention was to shed light on what factors determine user acceptance of mobile banking applications.
Phuong, T.T.K. and Vinh, T.T.,	2019	extended the TAM model by adding three factors: emotion, perceived enjoyment and perceived relevance
Scherer, R., Siddiq, F. and Tondeur, J.,	2019	Found that the role of certain key constructs of the TAM model, and the importance of external variables contrast some existing beliefs about the TAM.
Baby, A. and Kannammal, A.,	2020	Developed an enhanced version of the TAM model for the user-centric framework design of e-learning solutions.
Bae, S.Y. and Han, J.H.,	2020	Integrated an extended technology acceptance model (TAM). They introduced constructs such as trustworthiness of online reviews and integrated these into cultural consensus and cultural consonance theory.

Although several prior research projects have focused extending the TAM model to cater for different context-based factors (Phuong and Vinh, 2019), there is limited empirical work located within the context of the Nigerian online shopping environment.

2.8 Research Gap

Previous studies identify gaps in customer repurchase intentions literature and suggest that several potential areas need to be further explored (Gelbrich, Gäthke, and Hübner, 2017). The current literature on customer repurchase intention fails to draw attention to factors like after sale care, culture, infrastructural issues and price, as important considerations for online repurchases (Baby and Kannammal, 2020; Bae and Han, 2020). More so, previous research has not yet explored how these factors can improve sales performance. Most of the research is conducted within the context of western society (e.g. Gelbrich, Gäthke, and Hübner, 2017; Munoz-Leiva, Climent-Climent, and Liébana-Cabanillas, 2017), much to the neglect of emerging economies such as Nigeria specifically the internet shoppers present in Delta state, Nigeria. As such, there is still a lack in the literature about customer repurchase intention within the Nigerian context. Considering this, studies are needed to understand the link between the determinants of customer repurchase intention and improved sales performance within the Nigerian context. Therefore, there is increasing need to review existing models on consumer repurchase intentions and create space for contextual understandings on this subject. Previous studies use the TAM model, that is informed by studies conducted in western society, and much to the neglect of contextual understandings from emerging economies such as Nigeria.

2.9 Chapter Summary

The rapidly evolving world of internet and its functions has made it easy for consumers to shop online. People around the world have embraced the use of the internet to conduct shopping activities. Nowadays, consumers have access to an array of goods and services from all over the world and can shop from the comfort of their homes (Lin, 2008). The changing consumer trends have meant that more consumers engage with online shopping activities, and thereby reducing traditional offline shopping activities. Consequently, it has been discovered that there is an increasing number of determinants that propel customers to repurchase items within the online environment.

This chapter discussed in more detail the existing factors that instigate customers to repurchase items online and introduced new ones and related some existing ones to the Nigerian e-commerce sector. More so, the role of social media on customer repurchase intention was discussed. Additionally, changes in the sales performance of online companies were also discussed, as well as how online company sales performance can improve because of conspicuous application.

Moreover, a conceptual framework was developed to help provide a clear image of how these factors influence customer repurchase intention. The relevance of any research is in the gap it fills and the added value or knowledge it offers to the existing literature. To this end, this study contributes to the literature by focusing on customer repurchase intentions from a neglected area of study, that is, the Delta state, Nigerian e-commerce sector.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The previous chapter illustrated vital aspects of literature related to customer repurchase Intentions. It also discussed the variables that encourage customer repurchases within the online environment. Therefore, to answer the research questions, an appropriate methodology must be adopted. This chapter discusses the methodological issues and makes justifications on why particular courses of action were undertaken. This chapter explains the research philosophy, the research approach and strategy that was adopted. It also discusses and justifies the methods that were employed to help execute the research appropriately. The research population, sampling, and data analysis plans are also discussed. Ethical issues are also explained in detailed, and the researcher outlines how ethical principles were observed. Issues surrounding reliability, validity, and representativeness of the sample are also discussed.

According to Blumberg et. al., (2008) the purpose of the study should be founded on the question which is requiring investigation. Therefore, a comprehensive overview of the methodology employed is of paramount importance. Consequently, chapter 3 will examine the research philosophies and paradigms, discuss the most appropriate one for this study and justify the selected research design and the approaches adopted for this thesis. Additionally, the reliability and validity issues will also be discussed. Ethical considerations of the research and population sampling is also outlined in this chapter. The next section discusses the research philosophies.

3.2 Research Paradigm

Several management scholars have argued that a research paradigm is a vital structure which defines multiple hypothetical research philosophies (Bell and Bryman, 2011; Healy and Perry, 2000). In fact, a research paradigm is simply an instrument for defining complex and conflicting practices stemming from research communities (Thornhill, Saunders, and Lewis, 2015). Paradigms are globally recognised as scientific attainments that have provided problems and solutions to models developed by researchers (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). In fact, paradigms are achievements of scholars which are being acknowledged for a time being as a foundation for further development of that theory (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Paradigms are made up of accepted theories, specific problems, and methods on

research grounds. Similarly, paradigms are an embodiment of knowledge, practices and methods which include disruptive elements of change and novelty adopted by researchers (McNeill, 1990; Braun and Clarke, 2006; Hancock, 2007; Woods, 2019).

Previous studies suggest that paradigms act as identify crafting instruments for scholars (Thornhill, Saunders, and Lewis, 2015). Further, Singh and Bajpai (2008) suggests that grasping the idea of paradigms can aid in better understanding the research selections a writer is trying to make. Considering the current study, the selection of research that focuses on online customer repurchase intention is needed because of the growth in online shopping, and the need for firms to be competitive in a globalised business environment. Following from the research questions and understanding of research paradigms will help the researcher to identify the appropriate research strategy, design, and data collection methods. This methodological and conceptual model consisting of the theories and procedures will help to ensure that the research questions are answered appropriately and comprehensively.

However, it must also be understood that paradigms are susceptible to change due to dialectic triad of antithesis, thesis, and synthesis (Denscombe, 2014). Human knowledge as seen in the past years is in a constant state of change and development which means paradigms are likely to change frequently. Therefore, it is a misconception to assume that paradigms are static. They change with changes in the research environment. Despite the susceptibility of paradigms, they play a huge role in the research process. Scholars suggest that anchoring any research to at least one of the research paradigms will help to provide a clear foundation to the research (Fellows, 2010), as well as align the research questions more appropriately. The role of paradigms, like in this research, is to fully comprehend the views, beliefs closely linked to ontology, epistemology, and methodology (Creswell 2003; Ghiara, 2020). Given the nature of the research questions, this study was informed by both, positivism, and interpretivism. This was appropriate to help answer the research questions.

3.3 Research Philosophy and Justification

Guba and Lincoln (1998) suggests that there are four research philosophy used in research within the social sciences. These include positivism, constructivism, realism, and pragmatism. This research employs positivism paradigm to truly understand the research. A positivist research philosophy is based on collecting data using quantitative approaches (Tashakkori, Johnson, and Teddlie, 2020). The data sets are assumed to be measurable and quantifiable. In

this sense, the interpretation is objective (Irshaidat, 2019). Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991), suggest that positivism is the most widely used philosophical approach in business research.

Accordingly, Perry (2002), positivism is based on implicit or explicit assumptions that reality can be evaluated and measured by analysing it through a single way or value free mirror. Although this philosophy is popularly employed, other research has revealed that positivism despite its predominance in the business research world, falls short in handling of phenomena in social sciences (Primecz, 2020). It is highly dependent on quantifiable observations that produce statistical analysis (Glăveanu, 2019). Yet not everything is quantifiable. Quantification is based on pre-determined variables and understandings of reality (Irshaidat, 2019). Yet, in the real world, reality evolves, and it is not always possible to quantify everything (Tashakkori, Johnson, and Teddlie, 2020). In this sense, positivism is in line with empiricist view which is that knowledge is created from human experience (Creswell, 1994; Thornhill, Saunders, and Lewis, 2015). Thus, the focus is on testing already existing theoretical understandings. Despite the limitations of positivism, its results are generalisable, as it often involves large samples. Following from this, part of the current study utilises empirical data to generate a hypothesis that is subsequently tested (Crowther and Lancaster, 2008).

On the other hand, there is interpretivism. This is often assuming subjective reality (Fletcher, 2017), and is informed by qualitative data sets (Poucher, Tamminen, Caron, and Sweet, 2020). Here, theoretical understandings are not predefined (Hennink, Hutter, and Bailey, 2020), but emerge from the data. Interpretivism is often associated with smaller sample size and is more focused on establishing a deep understanding. For this reason, the interpretivist dimension was also utilised to help deepen understanding of the research topic. The subjective views and experiences were important to help answer the research questions.

3.3.1 Research Approach and Justification

Saunders (2003) suggests that the research approach adopted by researchers will aid the investigation of the research question. In fact, the approach is a process agreed on by which data should be collected and analysed (Croucher and Cronn-Mills, 2018). On the other hand, the research strategy is a basic plan that aids the researcher in obtaining answers to the research questions in a way that is systematic (Kumar, 2018). The research approaches include both qualitative and quantitative. The strategy and approach are so vital to the success of this research and they will be highlighted in the paper. As such, this section explains the research approaches adopted.

The inductive approach is where observations are made over time then turned into broader generalisations and eventually made theories (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018). The inductive approach is called the bottom up approach being that it observes to see if assumptions are true or not. Following from this, it proceeds to make generalisations/ patterns/ tentative hypothesis which in the end become theories. This was necessary to help develop understandings about online repurchase intentions that are culturally, and contextually nested. The intention was to develop a deep understanding of the Nigerian context, particularly that of the Delta state because of economic, geographical, and sub-cultural variations in the different states of Nigeria. In this sense, those understandings of online repurchase intentions that may not easily become apparent, but often taken for granted, are accounted for.

The deductive approach, in contrast, is a reasoning that works from the theory to the general then the observation before confirmation (Amaratunga et al., 2002; Thornhill, Saunders, and Lewis, 2015). It is the opposite of the inductive theory and it is sometimes called the top down approach (Harding, 2018). Here, there is a predefined theory, and the role of the researcher is to test pre-existing variables (Stephens, Dunn, and Hayes, 2018). The deductive approach sees conclusions being followed logically from the stated premises of that field or subject. In fact, deductive begins with the general assumptions and ends with the specific which has been tested and proven through research and data collection and analysis. In this study, deductivism was also necessary to help reach a larger audience, formulate hypothesis, and test pre-existing variable about online repurchase intentions.

Deductivism is concerned with testing existing theories whilst inductive is focused on developing fresh theory from the data (Singh and Baipai, 2008). More so, deductive approach places more emphasis on causality whilst inductive dwells more on unveiling new phenomenon (Pandey, 2019). Inductive is mostly associated with qualitative research whilst deductive is employed in quantitative research (Ditlmann and Kopf-Beck, 2019). The deductive approach answers mostly how and why questions and deduces theories via experiments after establishing hypotheses.

The current thesis is testing hypothesis whether from the empirical literature or from new data collection. In this sense, a deductive approach was part of the approaches adopted (Blumberg et al., 2008; Lin *et al.*, 2010). The deductive approach permits researchers to achieve confirmations on hypothesis tested which also helps understand empirical research (Walter and Ophir, 2019). The inductive approach was also adopted as evidenced by the need to obtain

deeper insights for some research questions (George, 2019). In this process, qualitative data sets were utilised.

Scholars suggest that the inductive approach follows a linear process and assumes that the researcher’s view is subject to change due to latest findings (Bell and Bryman, 2011). Nonetheless, the deductive approach is perceived as effective tool for exploring which theory to presume and definitive reasoning (Valentine, 2009). Drawing from the above, the current study uses both the deductive and inductive approach. In this sense, it adopts the abductive approach (Giuliani, Frambach, Driessen, and Martimianakis, 2020; Coreynen, Vanderstraeten, van Witteloostuijn, Cannaerts, Loots, and Slabbinck, 2020), for reasons outlined in this reason.

Table 3. 1: Alignment of research questions

Research Question	Research Approach	Type of Data
What are the gaps in knowledge within the literature surrounding customer repurchase intention?	Inductive	Qualitative
What are the determinants of customer, repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context?	Inductive and Deductive	Qualitative and Quantitative
What is the role of social media on customer repurchase intention?	Inductive and Deductive	Qualitative and Quantitative
How does the knowledge of customer repurchase intention enhance company sales?	Deductive	Quantitative
How can managers develop more effective marketing strategies within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention?	Inductive and Deductive	Qualitative and Quantitative

3.4 Research design

The literature suggests that the research design is the overall strategy used to integrate the different components of the study (Creswell and Poth, 2016). This helps the study to be coherent and logical, thereby, ensuring that the research problem is addressed effectively (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018). Others suggest that the research design is the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data (Booth, Colomb, and Williams, 2018).

The research design does not imply any research methods for data collection because data collection for any design could be collected using any method (Flick, 2018). This is informed by the research questions. Scholars often equate the research design with quantitative and qualitative research methods (Nardi, 2018). In this sense, researchers often make a choice between quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods research designs (Khoo-Lattimore, Mura, and Yung, 2019). This is dependent on the nature of data to be collected to answer the research questions.

In mixed methods, both qualitative and quantitative techniques are used in a single project (Timans, Wouters, and Heilbron, 2019). The literature points out that there is a variety of mixed methods, including concurrent, sequential, and embedded (Johnson and Walsh, 2019). The concurrent mixed methods involve using qualitative and quantitative approaches in parallel. This is often done in a single phase of data collection and analysis. On the other hand, there is the sequential mixed methods (Johnson, Grove, and Clarke, 2019). This involves more than one stage of data collection and analysis (McChesney and Aldridge, 2019). For instance, a study can collect qualitative data sets, analyse them, and then use insights from this stage to inform the quantitative part of the study.

3.4.1 Research design and Justification

The author opted for the mixed methods research design because it offered a practical and logical option that goes beyond paradigm conflicts (Baran, 2020). In this way, both qualitative and quantitative data was used to help make the analysis more complete. Some of the research questions needed quantitative data sets, whilst others needed qualitative data sets. This helped to achieved complementarity. The data collection and analysis were done sequentially, meaning that there were more than one phase of data collection and analysis, as presented in chapter 4. The approach taken was appropriate for the problem and challenges presented.

Altogether, these form what is known as research design, that is, framing the parameters of what is already known, while recognising scholars' philosophical assumptions about what is real and their outlook towards the research problem in question. However, to understand under what paradigm this research will operate it is crucial to delve deeper into the ontological, epistemological, and methodological assumptions which will keep the research in check and guide pre actions of the study.

Firstly, ontology is an idea that stemmed from philosophy which is popularly defined as a theory which describes the construction of the world. According to Gruber (1993), an ontology is the explicit specification of conceptualization (Qiaoli Zhu *et al.*, 2010). Ontology is relatively useful in terms of helping extract information from both humans and computers as needed (Myrgiotti *et al.*, 2009). Moreso, Creswell (2017) suggests that ontology are assumptions which do exist and are often reality.

Epistemology on the other hand, is the connection between the researcher, the reality, and the existent assumption (Healy and Perry, 2000). Epistemology is the scientific knowledge that the researcher absorbs in the study of or research into a field. Lastly, methodology focuses on the

systematic method of gathering and examining data derived from an analysis (Kameda, 2005; Baran, 2020). This process is what this entire chapter dwells on as it is the most suitable to collate and examine enough data for such a research study. According to Teddlie and Tashakkori, (2009), a research methodology is a widespread approach to specifying how research questions ought to be asked and resolved. This includes general preferences for research designs, universal considerations, population sampling logic, collection of data and analytical strategies, procedures for making inferences and the criteria for evaluating and improving quality of empirical research.

Research methodology is a systematic way of solving research issues (Thornhill, Saunders, and Lewis, 2015). It is also a science of researching how a study or research is done scientifically (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Accordingly, the researcher has several a research problem to solve. Considering this, a methodological approach is required to gather evidence that answers the research questions (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2011; Johnson, Grove, and Clarke, 2019). Scholars suggest that the researcher not only needs to be aware of research techniques, methods of gathering data, methods of analysing data, but must fully grasp the idea behind research methodology to understand what type of research designs are needed for the study (Amaratunga et al., 2002).

Ascertaining the research methodology early is beneficial to setting the right research ideas in place. Solving the research problem which is determining what factors instigate customers to purchase items within the online environment requires a well thought out methodology which is what this chapter addresses (Creswell, 2002; Booth, Colomb, and Williams, 2018). Research methodology is largely a clear logic behind the choice of methods used in the context of this research. It helps to justify the use of other techniques over others, to achieve the objectives of the research (Yang et al., 2004; Johnson, Grove, and Clarke, 2019).

Previous studies suggest that in the social sciences, researchers must ascertain the research design beforehand (Bell and Bryman, 2011). In fact, the research design used in every research is key to understanding the key aspects to data collection and obtain results that are authentic and valid (Hair et al., 2011; Baran, 2020). This design is not just a work plan, but it is a practical process which helps to answer the research questions. In this sense, the research design helps to ensure that evidence is obtained in the most unambiguous way possible.

In other words, this means that to retrieve the right evidence a suitable type of plan needs to be made to meet this requirement. To accurately test a theory or analyse primary or secondary

data, a clear plot on how to do this must be stated. A research design focuses on dealing with a logical problem, as well as the associated logistical issues (Yin, 1989; Booth, Colomb, and Williams, 2018). Research design is different from research methods. In fact, methods focus on the means in which data can be obtained from people or circumstances. More so, research design is centred on the question of “what evidence do I need to gather more than the question of what methods do I need to gather them”.

This study ensures that the appropriate research design is employed to successfully answer the research questions. The research method is centred on the mode of collecting data. It is regarded as the logical structure of inquiry through which the research questions in this study will be executed (Fue et al., 2009; Booth, Colomb, and Williams, 2018). Bell and Bryman (2011), argues that the selected research design is made of up a framework of fundamental guidelines and principles which are important to the requirements of the researcher and the research question.

According to Grafton et al., (2011) there are several types and subtypes of research designs and they include longitudinal design, cross-sectional design, experimental, semi experimental, correlational which consists of case-control study and observational study. There are also reviews which includes literature review and systematic review. There are also descriptive designs which includes naturalistic, case study, observation, and survey design. Highlighting the types of research design is vital but selecting the most suitable one is crucial for a research study. Accordingly, making this decision is informed by the nature of the research objectives and/ or research questions.

3.4.2. Case study

According to Mooi and Sarstedt (2011), a case study is an in-depth study of a specific research which is void of comprehensive comparative inquiry or statistical surveys. To make research easy the case study design is used to narrow down a broad field of research (Roth, 2019). This design can be used to test specific theories especially when there is a lack of information in the area. Descriptive design aids in terms of offering answers pertaining to the who, what, where and how questions associated with a certain research problem.

A case study is predominantly used to gather information regarding the present status of the phenomena or to describe what is in existence where variables are concerned (Field, 2015). This type of research design can produce reasonable data through observational methods which

sometimes cannot be replicated. For this study, the case study does not suffice as an appropriate research design.

3.4.3 Experimental design

Experimental design on the other hand, is a process that helps the researcher attempt to predict possible occurrences in the research (Field, 2015; Beach, 2020). This design is often used where there is time priority in a relationship that is casual and it supports the ability to manipulate, randomise and control. This may produce results that are not reflective and generalisable to the reality. Although it provides one of the highest levels of single study evidence, it is still not valid for this research (Singh and Bajpai, 2008; Roth, 2019).

3.4.4 Longitudinal design

Longitudinal research allows for the same sample to be examined over a long period of time (Amaratunga et al., 2002). This makes it possible to have repeated observations. Recurring interviews can be conducted, enabling researchers to observe changes over time. Consequently, the longitudinal type of research design helps facilitate a prolonged analysis of a specific phenomenon. This creates room for the prediction of future results based on long tested research (Amaratunga et al., 2002; Singer, 2019).

3.4.5 Cross-sectional design

The cross-sectional research design possesses distinct features that can be broken down into three areas. These include a great deal of reliance on existing variances rather than changing the progressing intervention. Secondly, time dimensions are inexistent. Finally, the population sampling groups are chosen on the grounds of present differences and not random allocation (Hong and Thong, 2013).

Considering all the research designs, their advantages and disadvantages, a cross-sectional design was adopted for this research. This is because a cross-sectional study design employs an observatory study that examines data gathered from a population or a subset at a specific point in time (Cameron and Price, 2009; Sundaresh, Yi, Roy, Riley, Wildeman, and Wang, 2020). Cross-sectional research design will enable this study to obtain a visible snapshot of the outcome and variables associated with online customer repurchase intentions. The study has a specific time limit that is consistent with a doctoral study, that is, data collection and analysis were completed in under 2 years.

This selected research design helped focus on drawing and studying inferences from empirical differences between phenomena, subjects, and people. This study is concerned with finding

connections between variables in a specified time. Data was retrieved from internet shoppers, and online retailers. A cross-sectional design was useful because it focuses on identifying groups based on differences existing in the samples instead of randomly seeking them. This research design is not bound to a geographical sample, it can be executed anywhere as it is not an observational study. However, semi-structured interviews were drawn from ten internet users in Nigeria.

Lin (2008) suggests that the results could be argued as being time bound and static. This gives no sign of a thoroughly observed sequence of events, historical or unfixed contexts. In this sense, outcomes cannot be used to effect relationships or cause changes as the results have not been tested over time. More so, this thesis obtained insights from 100 respondents. As such, the method helped estimate the prevalence of the factors influencing customer repurchase intentions. Insights from the qualitative data sets helped to deepen understanding. However, Hess (2008) argues that cross-sectional research design can prove difficult in terms of finding similar people required, phenomenon and subject within a specific time.

Regardless, this thesis ensured ample time was given to reach out to the sample of interest. Similarly, the relevant subject matter as guided by the research questions was covered. Further, the analysis was conducted within the timeframe of a doctoral study, and results have the potential for replicability. Given that the researcher used personal savings to finance the research, the study kept the costs to the minimal, and used data collection methods that would help to reduce costs. It is for this reason that the survey was conducted using google forms, face to face and telephonic interviews.

Therefore, the cross-sectional study design was appropriate because it was deemed to be less costly. In contrast (Culnan, 2000) states that in most cases where cross sectional research design methods are utilised there is no follow up with regards findings. Despite all this, the cross-sectional research design is appropriate for this study as it involves the use of different groups of individuals who have different characteristics.

3.5 Research Strategy and Justification

The importance of having a structured plan on how to solve the research question and collect the right data is a vital part of any research. Accordingly, research strategy is the general plan or map for a research problem consisting of structures, objectives which are the desired outcomes and outline of devices needed to carry out the strategy (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2011;

Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Similarly, the research strategy belongs in the broader development plan of a research approach. Having clear research objectives is key for any research and to achieve the objectives a clear strategy is crucial to realising that. More so, the research objectives determine the strategy required. Research methods on the other hand is concerned with the nature of the research problem in general (Nambisa, 2002; Bryman, 2017). Bearing in mind the objectives of this research, having a detailed plan as to how best these can be attained and making the choice between qualitative research strategy, quantitative research strategy or both is vital.

3.5.1 Qualitative research strategy

Qualitative method of research fascinates the thorough investigation of specific issues and allows proper comprehensive understanding of research to be achieved. Through structured and unstructured interviews and observations, qualitative method of research aid in retrieving and assessing perceptions and values of respondents (Bell and Bryman, 2011; Bryman, 2017). This is particularly useful to this research as some of the sub-questions aim to establish a deep understanding of customer repurchase intentions within the online environment. It is the inner beliefs and values of individuals that help to answer some of the research questions, and as such, warrants a qualitative approach.

Qualitative research, however, essentially is of diagnostic exploratory nature. This makes it challenging to implement in the development of conceptualisations in ever changing subjects like consumer behaviour (De Ruyter and Scholl, 1998; Bryman, 2017). However, it provides the possibilities to reveal newer understandings about online customer repurchase intentions that are contextually nested. It must be noted that qualitative research does not promise direct answers or straightforward mode of tackling research problems and objectives. It also does not offer a set of rules that must be followed (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Denscombe, 2014).

In fact, qualitative research is a strategy rather than a certain set of techniques and its validity and appropriateness can be derived from the social phenomenon being studied. In consumer behaviour, the interpretations of participants are important as these may be informative of different experiences and social contexts (Hogg and Maclaran, 2008). Nevertheless, qualitative research helps to generate new theories and evaluate what existing and new perceptions participants hold in respect to this evolving phenomenon. In understanding the way people think about purchasing or purchasing things online, qualitative research can help with regards

examining, interpreting, understanding such reality as social constructs through diverse perspectives and meanings people attach to them (Greenhalgh, 2001; Bryman, 2017).

This study considers qualitative research strategy as it centres on gaining understanding of the opinions, views and experiences of individuals linked to their personal practice with regard repurchasing items online. Establishing a deep understanding of the factors influencing consumers to engage in online repurchases is vital information within the context of the growth of online retailing. Within qualitative research, there are several methods of data collection methods, as outlined by Chitakunye (2012), and Denscombe (2014). This requires utilisation of skills like effective communication, note taking and planning to obtain useful data for the purpose of the research at hand. The qualitative strategy is consistent with interpretive methods and helps to establish a deep understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. Considering the need to answer the research questions comprehensively, the qualitative strategy was adopted.

3.5.2 Quantitative research strategy

Quantitative research on the other hand, recognises proportional scopes of perspectives and opinions via structured data gathering techniques thereby producing aggregated statistical information on several attributes (Singh and Baipai, 2008). Quantitative research is aligned to the deductive approach. Here, it is used to test theoretical understandings, and variables that have been identified in the literature. In fact, quantitative research is mostly associated with the positivist approach of research. This is based of science which holds that knowledge that is objective can only be retrieved from user's observation, practice, or experience (Robson, 2002). Quantitative research is characterised by assumptions that the behaviour of humans can be explained in what may be called social facts which can be examined by the methodologies that use the deductive rationale of natural or social sciences.

This strategy is of great advantage to this study as it aids the development of hypotheses and theories that are testable and generalisable (Amaratunga et al., 2002; Bloomfield and Fisher, 2019). The quantitative strategy is a form of empiricism as it not only tests existing data but introduces new ones and verifies them. Quantitative research helps investigate distinguishing characters, empirical boundaries and tend to evaluate the 'how much' or 'how can' or 'how often' questions (Cao et al., 2005). This research strategy is valid when it comes to studying relationships between behavioural components like online consumer behavior, as is in this study. More so, it is tied to explaining an epistemological methodology for understanding the

truth and value of propositions and permits flexibility in the way data is handled. With this, it is possible to compare variables, and aggregate using statistical approaches (Amaratunga et al., 2002).

More so, data for specific variables can be quantified at a specific time with the use of quantitative method as required for this study. Hence, this thesis also required the use of quantitative methods to help evaluate key insights with regards to concepts and variable where customer repurchase intentions and sales performance are concerned (Denzin and Lincoln, 2003; Hair Jr, Page, and Brunsveld, 2019).

3.6 Types of data

Accordingly, this research was executed using a combination of primary and secondary data to obtain well rounded information on perspectives.

3.6.1 Primary data

To collect data several effective data collection strategies are carried out. Primary data is the type collected for the specific research study at hand. This one is used to solve and answer the research problems with the most suitable procedures. Primary data when sourced adds new data into the existing well of social knowledge (Cachai and Millaward, 2011). Primary data is different from secondary data which is data created by other researchers for the reuse of the general community of researchers. It is collected for specific purposes and involves the use of several research methods like surveys with questions set to find answers to a certain issue or phenomenon.

The primary data collection yields recent data and tend to be proprietary and may take longer time to collect and are usually more costly to implement. The specificity of primary data is an added advantage (Cachia and Millward, 2011; Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Moreover, primary data can be executed by will or when required at any time or any place without competition (Denscombe, 2014).

The current study used primary data sets as already outlined. The intention was to obtain recent perceptions and views on why consumers repurchase items online despite the many challenges. These primary data sets also helped to establish a deep understanding of factors that influence consumer repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context. Scholars suggest that primary data is ideal for obtaining data surrounding consumer behaviour related phenomenon as the participants are involved in the processing and sharing of opinions, thoughts, views, and

perceptions (Cachia and Millward, 2011). This yields up to date results that can help to answer the research questions (Cachia and Millward, 2011).

The study used interviews and a survey, as primary data sets. This was necessary to obtain insights to answer the research questions. Moreover, using different methods helped to capitalise on the benefits of triangulation (Denscombe, 2014). The primary data sets were collected sequentially, with one data set being analysed first before moving to the next. This helped to deepen understanding on online repurchase intentions, and to ensure that all important areas of the research topic were covered.

3.6.2 Secondary data

Secondary data is that data already collected by researchers for a different or similar research problem to that of the current research (Cachia and Millward, 2011). It is data that is being reused to conduct new research. Internal secondary data is one previously collected and available upon request, such as sales data of a company used to investigate products (Yang et al., 2003). External secondary data, on the other hand, is that which companies or individuals have, but at times offered at a cost. The collection of secondary data is easier to obtain as it is present in books, journals, databases, and existing surveys.

The secondary data tends to have greater sample sizes which means more views and perceptions of participants are obtained and is often generalisable. It is cheaper and easier to access and, in many cases, has more authority as it is peer reviewed or examined by several authorities. Secondary data often provides arguments that are more accurate. However, some secondary data may be outdated and not entirely fit for to resolve the current research question at hand. More so, data may not always be available, and there may be errors due to inaccurate analysis, wrong demography, or poorly created questions in surveys (Denscombe, 2014).

Additionally, secondary data tends to contain information that is factual. Sometimes, secondary data may not be reported in the appropriate form that is required by some studies or reports. Lastly, the sources of secondary data are official databases or archives which could be online or offline (Hess, 2008). This study used secondary data. Here, academic journal articles were reviewed, as illustrated in chapter 2. Further, consumer behaviour reports and market reports on online shopping and markets were also reviewed to obtain relevant statistical information about online repurchase intentions, as illustrated in chapters 1, 2, 4, and 6. This was necessary to make the current study more relevant and comprehensively answer the research questions.

3.7 Data collection methods

Understanding the type of research methods that suit any study is vital to getting the right data which may solve the research questions of any study. Research methods are a broad range of methods or techniques in social sciences or psychology. These methods differ depending on the sources of data, the sampling techniques used, and the means used in data collection (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Choosing the right research methods can help attain better results thereby yielding data that is more appropriate and accurate for the study. The decision of the type of methods to use depends on the time allocated for the research, the resources, the people available to involve in such research and the cost involved. The approach to understanding what methods to use depends also on validity and reliability issues to be achieved, as well as analytical processes (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018).

The methods of gathering data whether primary data or secondary data depends on the research questions asked and how much the researcher wants or intends to get from the research. Using various research methods especially during a specific research can ensure better reliability of such research and help prove the hypotheses created or create new theories (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2011). The researcher can obtain varied data both from methods like interviews and questionnaires. Following from this understanding, the study employed the mixed methods approach, as explained in the next section.

3.7.1 Mixed methods

In examining social sciences many researchers have employed mixed methods to help achieve varied results (Gummerson, 2000; Denscombe, 2014). According to Grafton et al. (2011) mixed methods can be categorised into two main methods which are qualitative and quantitative methods of research. These methods, however, enable researchers to analyse a wide range of methodological data which can help build valid hypothesis. Mixed methods enable easy access to a combination of perception and approaches. The current study used mixed methods because these were best suited to answer the research questions.

However, before arriving at the decision to use mixed methods or not it is paramount to check if the research needs such approach. The complexity of today's research issues which are numerous calls for answers beyond the easy numbers of quantitative knowledge or the generous words of qualitative reasoning which comes by simply interviewing people and or handing them questionnaires (Langford et al., 2002; Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018). The combined use of qualitative and quantitative data sets in gaining increasing prominence in consumer

research and marketing. As such, the adoption of mixed methods for the current study is also consistent with other social research studies (Denscombe, 2014). More importantly, mixed methods helped to gain from the benefits of triangulation, and comprehensively answer the research questions. Both strategies are key to achieving good results whose validity can be better trusted when presented.

Scholars suggest that combining qualitative and quantitative data sets enhances the believability of the results (Denscombe, 2014). This means that it is safer to combine both forms of data collection to satisfy the increased call to provide sophisticated evidence for every research being executed. For example, when multiple sources of data are utilised it can provide clearer understanding of the thoughts of a great number of people around the world (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018). More so, the use of mixed methods can give room for comparison of recent and existing understandings. It was also for this reason that the mixed methods approach was adopted.

3.7.2 Interviews

In gathering appropriate data to fulfil some of the research objectives for this study, interviews were used. Scholars suggest that interviews are qualitative in nature and can be used alongside other research techniques within a research project (Brewerton and Millward, 2001). There are various forms of interviews and they consist of structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews. Any of these forms of interview can be used depending on the questions or problems being researched and the analytical strategy being used. Structured interviews are carried out with predetermined set of questions which usually include several prescribed answers which the interviewee must select from.

Cachia and Millward (2011), suggest that this form of interview format is set up such that the interviews are like self-administered questionnaires. The interviewer is close by and ready to answer any queries or questions that arise. This helps to ensure that data collected can be quantified and compared between participants. This form of interview has an advantage for this thesis in that several online entrepreneurs in Delta state Nigeria were interviewed to gather data on what they think makes people come back online to purchase their goods and services. This method is suitable for deductive approach to research because the areas of exploration are not restricted to the subjects which are included in the interview schedule.

Unstructured interviews on the other hand, sees the evolving of questions as the interview process unfolds. However, this paper neither uses solely structured or unstructured interview

but semi-structured which is distinguished by components of structured and unstructured interviews alike. Culnan, (2000) suggests that semi-structured interviews are where set questions in sequence have been used to guide the interview process but includes the process of adding questions to facilitate deeper exploration of the problems or topic brought by the researcher. Because of this flexibility, the semi-structured interviews were used, and these were aided by an interview guide.

This process took the form of a conversation that was managed with vital questions asked and key notes taken down to aid easy analysis of data retrieved. The sample size for this were four (4) entrepreneurs. These were interviewed both face to face and telephonically to help reduce the research costs, reach respondents timeously and conveniently. However, because of the principal of voluntary participation, of the participants approached, only the four agreed to take part in the study also individuals in this region are not always willing to divulge information about their companies. Moreover, because the qualitative part focused on establishing the depth of understanding, a small sample was thus necessary (Chitakunye, 2012). The participants that provided insights within this data set were from Delta state, Nigeria. These were conveniently selected, and their businesses had established online shopping platforms. These respondents were drawn from different industries, gender, age, and were either owners or managers of the respective enterprises. Hence, these were deemed to have enough knowledge about online shopping activity in Nigeria. Insights from this data source were analysed before moving to the next data source.

3.7.3 Questionnaire survey method

The research utilised the questionnaire method as it was found to be associated with the deductive approach, and the quantitative strategy. Questionnaires allowed this study to cover a wide number of participants with minimum expense in terms of effort and money (Guba and Lincoln, 1995; Hair Jr, Page, and Brunsveld, 2019). The participants had to be resident in Nigeria. The researcher was in London, United Kingdom. As such, google forms were used to help administer the questionnaire for efficiency purposes. Further, the questionnaire was used to help obtain data that would answer some of the research questions.

Contrary, Mooi and Sarstedt (2011) suggests that questionnaires have the tendency to be misinterpreted and this occur in terms of misinterpretation of questions asked. There are also arguments pertaining to the reliability of questionnaires. Nonetheless, the respondents for this study were asked willingly to participant thereby making them provide information voluntarily.

The questions were designed to obtain nominal and ordinal data. Here, the research constructs, as identified in the literature (see chapter 2), were measured using the Likert scale.

3.7.4 Secondary data set used

The research made use of available statistical indicators to help answer some of the research questions. These were obtained from different authentic and trusted sources such as the government statistical office, the World Bank, United Nations (UN), Nigeria Country Commercial Guide (NCCG), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNTAD), United Nations Economic Commissions for Africa (UNECA) and other trusted institutions. The data set used is as illustrated in figure 3.2.

Table 3. 2: secondary data

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Year	Social N users (Worldwide) - Billions	GDP/Capita (USD)	GDP (BILLION USD)	Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)	Population (Million)	Total labour force (Millions)	Sales Revenue for Jumia (Million USD)	Internet subscribers (Millions)
2018	2.65	2396.3	397.8	29.2	195.88	60.72	130.6	94.8
2017	2.48	2412.4	375.7	27.68	190.87	59.04	94	93.2
2016	2.28	2456.3	404.6	25.67	185.96	57.39	93.6	91.88
2015	2.14	2563.1	494.6	24.5	181.14	55.81	34	97.03
2014	1.91	2563.9	568.5	21	176.4	54.25	28	76.32
2013	1.59	2476.9	515	19.1	171.77	52.81	0	64.23
2012	1.4	2385	459.4	16.1	167.23	51.4	0	32.94
2011	1.22	2350.3	410.3	13.8	162.81	50.05	0	27.6
2010	0.97	2292.4	363.4	11.5	158.5	48.76	0	23
2009	0.91	2180	291.9	9.3	154.32	47.46	0	18.6

Table 3. 2.1: Outcome of hypothesis testing

Null Hypothesis	N	P-value (sig.)	Correlation co-efficient	Direction of Association/ relationship	Strength of Association/ relationship	Decision
H5a: There is no correlation between the number of internet users in Nigeria and the population.	10	.000	.995	Positive	Strong	Reject
H5a: There is no correlation between the number of internet users in Nigeria and the total labour force.	10	.000	.993	Positive	Strong	Reject
H5a: There is no correlation between the number of internet users in Nigeria and the number of internet subscribers	10	.000	.960	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the number of internet users in Nigeria	10	.000	.996	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the population of Nigeria.	10	.000	.996	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the total labour force of Nigeria.	10	.000	.995	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the number of internet subscribers in Nigeria.	10	.000	.960	Positive	Strong	Reject
H3: There is no correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the GDP of Nigeria.	10	.001	.879	Positive	Strong	Reject

H3: There is no correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the number of internet users in Nigeria.	10	.039	.658	Positive	Moderate	Reject
H5a: There is no correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the number of internet subscribers in Nigeria.	10	.013	.745	Positive	Moderate	Reject

However, financial records for a company like Jumia, a major retailer in Nigeria could only be obtained for the period 2014 until 2018. The other records could not be in the public domain. Whilst all other indicators will be compared over a 10-year period, sales revenues for Jumia will only be considered for a 5-year period.

3.8 Sampling Design and Methods

Previous studies suggest that sampling is a key step in the process of research as it constitutes the represented subset or sample to gather the necessary information from (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). There are probability and non-probability sampling techniques. With probability techniques, every element of the population has a known chance of being selected. On the other hand, with non-probability sampling, the probability of selecting very specific elements to include in a study is unknown. In fact, scholars suggest that the sampling phase of any research process is one of the most vital aspects as it aids in validation of results (Hair, 2011). Moreover, the sample must represent the population to be relied on.

This research used mixed methods which include both quantitative and qualitative. With regards the qualitative research, the sampling technique adopted is the non-probability sampling techniques also considered as the purposive sample method; Further, non-probability sampling was preferred because it allows the researcher to make subjective judgement pertaining to research interest. Due to the objectives that required answers set by the researcher, the purposive sample method was used.

This technique will give the researcher leverage to pick only a few online entrepreneurs and managers of Nigerian firms that meet the criteria as not all the online companies can be included in this research.

For the quantitative research on the other hand, stratified random technique and convenience techniques which are part of the probability sampling methods were utilised. This is because of the need to reach out to those respondents that were knowledgeable about online shopping in Delta state, Nigeria. This was also necessary to uphold the principles of voluntary

participation in a study. This is justified as the people selected will already be active online shoppers.

More so, it is reportedly less expensive, and less complex than non- probability technique as it is more specific and restricted to a particular population. This method is expected to decrease the chance of systematic mistakes or sample bias. Given the limited financial resources for the data collection, and the limited time for a doctoral study, insights had to be obtained from those participants who were willing to provide their responses within a set time limit.

The in-depth interviews are targeted at online entrepreneurs and managers while the questionnaires are aimed at consumers who shop online and actively participate in an online internet shopping forum. The intention was to reach out to those respondents that were knowledgeable about online shopping in Nigeria, and that were willing to voluntarily participate in the study.

Participants- to answer the research question, this research gathered primary data. The participants were adults. Some of them will be online entrepreneurs and managers of several businesses of interest. More so, participants were persons who belonged to an active online forum of choice, focused on internet shopping in Nigeria.

Table 3. 3: Sample size

Participant Description	Target respondents	Quantity
Data Source	Online entrepreneurs/ managers	4 respondents
Semi-structured interviews	Online shoppers	100 respondents
Survey	Various indicators	10 years
Secondary data		

Target population- The target population in this paper included online entrepreneurs, managers, and online shoppers in mostly retail in Delta state, Nigeria. There are 6 online stores in the Delta state. The degree of operations in the businesses was considered to ascertain the formula used to include them in the target population. More so, an active group of 140 users in an online forum focused on internet shopping in Delta state made up the target population too.

Response Rate- The total number of 180 questionnaires were sent out to potential respondents and a record of 100 questionnaires were returned filled out by the members of this online shopping forum selected by the researcher. This revealed a total success rate of response of 85% out of 118 survey questionnaires expected to be completed. A response rate above 50%

is sufficient for a research and anything figures beyond that is good and appropriate for publishing.

Sampling Frame- The chosen companies used were sourced on the Nigerian Country Commercial Guide (NCCG). The website revealed several online companies in Nigeria. The online entrepreneurs, managers, and internet shoppers (Found on a Facebook Online forum focused on internet shoppers in Nigeria specifically in Delta state) constitute the sampling frame.

3.8.1 Sample size

Creswell (2003), states that the population size used during management research must be enough to validate the data collected. The sample size for the study is as discussed below. The research sample size was 6 companies, 140 participants from an online forum. To measure the adequate sample size, the use of survey monkey was done. The analysis revealed a total of 140 participants that were contacted for this study.

Stage 1- Quantitative data was collected through survey. For this research the direct source of data was through the participants. 180 were sent out to the respondents with a success return rate ranging from 100- 118 responses. Approximately each respondent filled the questionnaire within 15 to 30 minutes. Interview sessions were carried out involving online entrepreneurs and managers within those 6 companies but anything response around 5-4 companies was fine. The interviews lasted between 40-60 minutes each to retrieve vital data needed for the research. To support the primary data, secondary data of revealing 10-year period of online shopping in Nigeria and correlations between other constructs was collected and utilised.

Stage 2- The survey done retrieved quantitative data from members of the online forum based on internet shopping in Delta state Nigeria. The reason for this was that the information required to gain insights and answer the research question may not be readily available via a random sample but can be easily provided by respondents. The respondents had to have vital information due to their experiences with online shopping in Nigeria. The semi-structured interviews were targeted at online entrepreneurs and managers of online companies to gain relevant data from them. At least two online entrepreneurs and two managers were targeted. More so, these discussions were recorded and transcribed later for the purpose of this research. The secondary data was analysed and correlated to test hypotheses.

Pilot testing- This was used to examine the reliability of the research instruments used. Sample questionnaires were initially sent out to 12 members of the group to gain more understanding. More so, these 12 participants were not included in the main study as they could already have a bias because of their previous information of the questionnaire's contents.

An interview on skype was held to do a pre-test of the interview tool which was planned for the current study. This method was employed because of its usefulness and convenience. This pilot test aided the researcher in discovering potential questions that can be misconstrued or may be ambiguous for the interviewees to grasp clearly.

Sample Size Determinants utilising Statistical methods- Stratified random sampling was implemented to ascertain the sample size. A scientific parameter to determine the needed sample criteria and create sample size decision was applied. The level of confidence considered was 95% and the level of precision and sampling error was considered at $\pm 5\%$. This helped to obtain a true population value as the standard deviations are within two. Examining a population of 140 members within the online internet shopping forum, the scientific guideline employed suggests a sample size of ≥ 103 respondents at $\pm 5\%$ level of precision. The formula used to measure the sample is;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

As illustrated here, N signifies the population, e portrays the level of population and the sample size is indicated n.

The survey monkey website was used to calculate the sample size required. To unveil the sample size a screenshot has been highlighted below.

The screenshot shows the SurveyMonkey sample size calculator interface. At the top, there are two buttons: "Pro sign up" (yellow) and "Sign up free" (green). Below these, there is introductory text: "How many people do you need to take your survey? Even if you're a statistician, determining survey sample size can be tough." and "Want to know how to calculate it? Our sample size calculator makes it easy. Here's everything you need to know about getting the right number of responses for your survey." The main section is titled "Calculate your sample size" and contains three input fields: "Population size" with the value 140, "Confidence level (%)" with a dropdown menu set to 95, and "Margin of error (%)" with the value 5. Below these fields, the calculated "Sample size" is displayed in large green text as 103.

Although 103 respondents were required, only 100 returned usable questionnaires. Moreover, following the principles of voluntary participation to this research study, the researcher obtained only 100 responses. However, the survey instrument was sent to all members of the study population. It would have been good if all had returned their questionnaires, as this would have helped to reduce the sampling error (Babbie, 2020). The number of participants to the survey was limited by the sampling frame used. This is what was available, and usable. In this sense, it can be said that responses from the survey element of the study were obtained from 71.4% of the study population.

3.9 Data Analysis plan

Qualitative data was analysed using content and thematic analysis. Using NVivo, the researcher generated word clouds to aid the content analysis, as is consistent with previous studies (Sotiriadou, Brouwers, and Le, 2014). Emerging themes were then explored using thematic analysis. This helped to understand the context in which the words were used. Qualitative data was analysed in an iterative manner following the principles outlined by Spiggle (1994). The quantitative data was analysed using descriptive, associative, and predictive analytical techniques. This was made possible by using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS). The data collected will be used to understand the extent to which the factors of

customer repurchase intentions influence consumers to buy goods and how it impacts sales of companies.

3.10 Access and ethical considerations

Research ethical issues are considered an imperative concern for research all around the world including management research (Denzin and Lincoln, 2003; Hair Jr, Page, and Brunsveld, 2019). According to Saunders (2007), research ethics are moral responsibilities connected with the process of research. Moreover, issues such as integrity and values are considered by both participants and firms because of the presence of ethics (Weeks et al., 2004; Silverman, 2020). Adhering to ethical principles is vital for every research as it can prevent any unwanted transgressions of ethical considerations in research. The research ensured that fundamental ethical principles were followed throughout the process of this study.

For this study, ethical clearance was provided in writing by the university's ethical committee. Further, a participant information sheet was prepared to provide enough information to respondents before they engaged in the research. Consent was obtained in writing. Thus, informed consent was obtained. Pseudonyms are used in the reporting of the results to help ensure confidentiality and privacy of the respondents. Data was also anonymised to protect the identity of individuals and organisations. The study was conducted in accordance with the university's ethical guidelines.

Data for this study was collected voluntarily from the consumers and online entrepreneurs. Additionally, during the investigation process, careful planning and continuous vigilance were kept maintaining ethical standards and ensure ethical measures like the ones stated above. With the ethical standards in mind, the safeguarding of participants' rights at every given time was achieved by means of obtaining informed consent.

Furthermore, data was concealed to protect privacy, give any possible clue of identity, keep demographic details, maintain confidentiality and anonymity by coding them. Blumberg, et. al (2008) argues that to maintain and keep research ethics, any arising ethical issues should be dealt with as soon as possible by adhering to the following guidelines which include, securing informed consent, debriefing respondents, and explaining participants' rights to privacy.

More so, for every survey questionnaire that was shared out, fundamental research standards were maintained. For example, at the top of the survey questionnaires the participants were informed about the purpose of the research. Participants were also made aware that their

involvement would be treated with extreme privacy and confidentiality. The researcher's contact details were also provided with the intention of helping to address queries that might arise.

Moreover, prior the research, letters and emails were sent out to online entrepreneurs seeking their consent to be involved in this research. The interviews, participants were informed of the fundamental ethical justifications. Thus, to the endorsement of a clearly ethically-sound study, outlining the reliability and validity of this research is vital to ensuring its true value to the body of customer repurchase intentions literature (Cameron and Price, 2009; Allan and Skinner, 2020).

3.11 Reliability and validity of study

Researchers suggest that the reliability and the validity of any research are crucial aspects that need to be observed (Saunders et al., 2007; Bell and Bryman, 2011; Silverman, 2020) because they help to build trust in the outputs of the research. According to Bell and Bryan (2011), reliability is connected to the question of whether the results of a research are repeatable, and this is important for future studies and replicability of the study. Validity of a study on the other hand, is postulated to be the degree to which a construct weighs what it is ought to weigh (Hair et al., 2011), and this helps with the accuracy of the results. To defend the quality of data collected and ensure the chosen the instrument weighs what is stated to be measured is the reason why the researcher is testing the current research validity.

In this paper, to ascertain the validity of the research instrument, the Content Validity method was used. This method was selected as it is relevant to the objectives of this research. More so, to assess the secondary data validity, the Criterion- related method of validity was implemented by the researcher.

Therefore, it is crucial to establish the reliability and validity of any study because they both influence the process of data analysis and validation (Weeks et al, 2004; Creswell, 2003; Yin, 2003).

Cronbach's Alpha has been adopted to measure the reliability of this research. Accordingly, the study proposes a higher degree of Cronbach's coefficient alpha shows a more advanced reliability of measurement scale. To measure the internal consistencies of the given population sample, the Cronbach coefficient is utilised.

Table 3. 4: Reliability of the research constructs

Research Construct	Reliability Statistics		
	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
Influence of social media	.651	.647	4
Perceived value	.545	.549	2
Privacy and trust	.631	.632	5
Brand reputation	.525	.537	3
System availability and functionality	.607	.608	3
Most influential factors for online repurchases	.835	.818	8
Other influential factors for online repurchases	.830	.825	6

As a result, this study is deemed valid and reliable as the collection of data was achieved through the utilisation mixed research methods with the intention of gaining from the benefits of triangulation (Nguyen and Leblanc, 2011). More so, the validity and reliability of this study is important and is achieved through mixed methods. Further, both secondary and primary data have been used. Further, triangulation of sources utilised, and information gathered, are assessed through multiple variables, sample size and data analysis tools (Collins and Hussy, 2011). Additionally, validity and reliability levels can be increased and achieved through comparisons, clear objectives, and adequate measurements (Silverman, 2020). For the quantitative data sets, reliability tests were conducted for the different research constructs, as illustrated in chapter 4. A summary of the reliability testing is as illustrated in table 3.3. Overall, the results reveal that the constructs were measured using a reliable scale. This will be illustrated in further details in the next chapter.

3.12 Methodological limitations

It is important to acknowledge some methodological limitations, as below:

1. The research of this paper was in the United Kingdom and the study was centred on Nigeria. However, the researcher used online mediums like phone calls and video interviews.
2. Retrieving past data was a challenge for the researcher as the nature of how data is kept or stored in the country the research was conducted is still lagging. A lot of extensive research had to be carried out
3. Training was required for the researcher in areas of interview conducting, questionnaire management and gather/analysing of secondary data sets using statistical tools like

SPSS and NVivo to accurately interpret data gathered. However, financial resources limited the depth of training. Regardless, the researcher acquired enough skills to interpret both qualitative and quantitative data sets using the relevant software.

4. Primary data collection was conducted within the online environment and was understood within the context of limitations associated with online surveys.
5. There were constraints of resources because the project was self-funded, and researcher had to draw from personal savings. Data collection was within the limits of the available financial resources.

Other limitations are discussed in chapter 6.

3.13 Summary of the chapter

This chapter discussed the methodological issues and made justifications on why particular courses of action were undertaken. This chapter explained the research philosophy, the research approach and strategy that was adopted. It also discussed and justified the methods that were employed to help execute the research appropriately. The research population, sampling, and data analysis plans were also discussed. Ethical issues were explained in detail, and the researcher outlined how ethical principles were observed. Issues surrounding reliability, validity, and representativeness of the sample were also discussed. The approach taken was appropriate for the problem and challenges presented.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The means of analysing data will be based on research methods uses to gather data. It is fundamental to examine data to ensure the validity of the research when it pertains to a research question. This stage is a vital as it analyses raw data thereby creating new theories or adding to or confirming existing ones (Hair, et al., 2015). Firstly, the secondary data set is analysed, and reported. This is followed by the primary data. There were two sets of primary data, quantitative, and qualitative. The quantitative results and presented, followed by the qualitative results. This is consistent with sequential analysis as outlined in chapter 3. The data from interviews were transcribed and analysed making it verifiable with the opinions and perceptions of respondents carefully inputted.

4.2 Secondary data analysis

This section presents the results of secondary data. It starts by conducting correlational analysis, and then engaging with linear regression analysis.

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to determine if there was a relationship between the number of internet users and the sales revenue of Jumia, one of the leading online retailers in Nigeria. The results are as illustrated in table 4.1.

Table 4. 1: Internet users vs sales revenue

		Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)	Sales Revenue for Jumia (Million USD)
Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)	Pearson Correlation	1	.910*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.032
	N	5	5
Sales Revenue for Jumia (Million USD)	Pearson Correlation	.910*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032	
	N	5	5

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result was significant at the 0.05 level, as illustrated by a p-value of 0.032 and a correlation co-efficient of .910. This is interpreted as a positive and strong correlation. That means as the number of internet users increases, the sales volumes of Jumia also increases. Another correlation was conducted to determine the relationship between all the other secondary data sets, and the results obtained are as illustrated in table 4.2.

Table 4. 2: Internet and economic indicators

		Correlations						
		GDP/Capita (USD)	GDP (BILLION USD)	Social N users (Worldwide) - Billions	Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)	Population (Million)	Total labour force (Millions)	Internet subscribers (Millions)
GDP/Capita (USD)	Pearson Correlation	1	.879**	.621	.658*	.593	.578	.745*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.055	.039	.071	.080	.013
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
GDP (BILLION USD)	Pearson Correlation	.879**	1	.260	.301	.239	.221	.385
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.468	.398	.506	.540	.272
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Social N users (Worldwide) - Billions	Pearson Correlation	.621	.260	1	.996**	.996**	.995**	.960**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.055	.468		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)	Pearson Correlation	.658*	.301	.996**	1	.995**	.993**	.967**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	.398	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Population (Million)	Pearson Correlation	.593	.239	.996**	.995**	1	1.000**	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.071	.506	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Total labour force (Millions)	Pearson Correlation	.578	.221	.995**	.993**	1.000**	1	.938**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.080	.540	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Internet subscribers (Millions)	Pearson Correlation	.745*	.385	.960**	.967**	.942**	.938**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013	.272	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results suggest that as the number of internet users in Nigeria increase, there is also a corresponding increase in the total labour force, and internet subscribers. Similarly, as the number of social network users worldwide increases, there is a corresponding increase in the number of internet users in Nigeria, total labour force in Nigeria, and internet subscribers. Further, as Nigeria’s GDP per capita increases, there is a corresponding increase in the GDP, the number of internet users, and the number of internet subscribers. This provides an opportunity to online businesses, and thus reinforces earlier results of a positive correlation between the number of internet users and the sales revenues of Jumia, one of the leading online

retailers in Nigeria. This is also interpreted as an opportunity for businesses to encourage online purchases.

Table 4. 3: Outcome of hypothesis testing

Null Hypothesis	N	P-value (sig.)	Correlation co-efficient	Direction of Association/ relationship	Strength of Association/ relationship	Decision
H5a: There is no correlation between the number of internet users in Nigeria and the population.	10	.000	.995	Positive	Strong	Reject
H5a: There is no correlation between the number of internet users in Nigeria and the total labour force.	10	.000	.993	Positive	Strong	Reject
H5a: There is no correlation between the number of internet users in Nigeria and the number of internet subscribers	10	.000	.960	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the number of internet users in Nigeria	10	.000	.996	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the population of Nigeria.	10	.000	.996	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the total labour force of Nigeria.	10	.000	.995	Positive	Strong	Reject
There is no correlation between the number of social network users worldwide and the number of internet subscribers in Nigeria.	10	.000	.960	Positive	Strong	Reject
H3: There is no correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the GDP of Nigeria.	10	.001	.879	Positive	Strong	Reject
H3: There is no correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the number of internet users in Nigeria.	10	.039	.658	Positive	Moderate	Reject
H5a: There is no correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the number of internet subscribers in Nigeria.	10	.013	.745	Positive	Moderate	Reject

4.2.2 Linear Regression

Linear regression analysis was conducted to determine whether knowing the number of internet users, and internet subscribers could help to predict the GDP of Nigeria. This follows from earlier results that indicated a positive and strong correlation between internet users and the sales revenue of Jumia, one of the largest online retailers in Nigeria. This understanding helps to enrich our understanding of consumer online repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context.

4.7.2.1 GDP and Internet users in Nigeria

Table 4.4 illustrates the mean and standard deviations of Nigeria's GDP and the number of internet users over a period of 10 years, that is, from the year 2009 to the year 2018. The results also indicate that the two variables (GDP and the number of internet users) are not correlated. However, earlier results indicated a moderate correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the number of internet users in Nigeria.

Table 4. 4: GDP and internet users in Nigeria

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
GDP (BILLION USD)	428.1200000	81.60553903	10
Internet Users (Nigeria-Millions)	19.78500000	6.974230742	10

Correlations

		GDP (BILLION USD)	Internet Users (Nigeria-Millions)
Pearson Correlation	GDP (BILLION USD)	1.000	.301
	Internet Users (Nigeria-Millions)	.301	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	GDP (BILLION USD)	.	.199
	Internet Users (Nigeria-Millions)	.199	.
N	GDP (BILLION USD)	10	10
	Internet Users (Nigeria-Millions)	10	10

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Internet Users (Nigeria-Millions) ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 4. 5: Regression model - GDP and internet users in Nigeria

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.301 ^a	.091	-.023	82.537182515672680

a. Predictors: (Constant), Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)

b. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

The model summary, as illustrated in table 4.6 indicates that R is .301. The r square, that is, the co-efficient of determination is .091. It shows how much variance in our outcome variable (GDP) is explained by our predictor variable (total number of internet users in Nigeria). That means 9.1% of all the variance in GDP can be predicted by the total number of internet users in Nigeria.

Table 4. 6: GDP and internet users

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5436.084	1	5436.084	.798	.398 ^b
	Residual	54499.092	8	6812.386		
	Total	59935.176	9			

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	358.399	82.298		4.355	.002	168.621	548.178
	Internet Users (Nigeria- Millions)	3.524	3.945	.301	.893	.398	-5.573	12.621

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	391.1717529	461.2976685	428.1200000	24.57660138	10
Residual	-99.2717438	136.0984497	.0000000000	77.81680194	10
Std. Predicted Value	-1.503	1.350	.000	1.000	10
Std. Residual	-1.203	1.649	.000	.943	10

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

Table 4.6 is used to test whether our model is better than just using the mean to predict an outcome. A p value of .398 is not statistically significant and indicates that the regression model generated is a poor predictor of GDP. Though the number of internet users contribute to GDP outcomes, there are other stronger predictors variables for GDP. Regardless, the number of internet users is an indicator of growing revenues in internet shopping, as illustrated by earlier correlation results.

The coefficients help formulate the linear regression line. When using the formula method, and the numbers above can be plugged into the formula to help make accurate predictions. That means, the formula can be used to predict GDP (outcome) variable when the knowledge of the number of internet users (predictor variable) is retrieved. The B value as indicated by the constant is our intercept. This indicates the point where the number of internet user's indicator is zero. The unstandardized item under internet users is the weight of the regression line. The associated t-test results reveal whether the predictor is statistically significant or not. The p values indicate mixed results. Though the result is not statistically significant, the number of internet users contribute to the GDP.

Figure 4. 1: GDP and number of internet users

Figure 4.1 indicates that the residual seems to be normally distributed around the mean. This is a good sign because it is consistent with the assumptions of the linear regression.

Figure 4. 2: Normal P-P Plot

Figure 4.2 indicates that there are fairly a few distributed scores as indicated by the regression standardised predicted value and the regression standardised residual. The fair distribution of scores is around the mean, and thus, it can be said that the assumptions for regression have been met. Overall, though the number of internet users can help to predict GDP, there are other predictors that can yield better results. Other indicators must be used to help build a good model.

4.7.2.2 GDP and internet subscribers

Table 4.7 illustrates the mean and standard deviations of Nigeria's GDP and the number of internet subscribers over a period of 10 years, that is, from the year 2009 to the year 2018. The results also indicate that the two variables (GDP and the number of internet subscribers) are not correlated. However, earlier results indicated a moderate correlation between Nigeria's GDP/capita and the number of internet subscribers in Nigeria.

Table 4. 7: GDP and internet subscribers

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
GDP (BILLION USD)	428.1200000	81.60553903	10
Internet subscribers (Millions)	61.96000000	33.01787092	10

Correlations

		GDP (BILLION USD)	Internet subscribers (Millions)
Pearson Correlation	GDP (BILLION USD)	1.000	.385
	Internet subscribers (Millions)	.385	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	GDP (BILLION USD)	.	.136
	Internet subscribers (Millions)	.136	.
N	GDP (BILLION USD)	10	10
	Internet subscribers (Millions)	10	10

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Internet subscribers (Millions) ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 4. 8: Regression model - GDP and internet subscribers

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.385 ^a	.148	.042	79.878070067672670

a. Predictors: (Constant), Internet subscribers (Millions)

b. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

The model summary, as illustrated in table 4.58, indicates that R is .385. The r square, that is, the co-efficient of determination is .0148. It tells how much variance in our outcome variable (GDP) is explained by our predictor variable (total number of internet subscribers in Nigeria). That means 14.8 % of all the variance in GDP can be predicted by the total number of internet subscribers in Nigeria.

Table 4. 9: GDP and Internet subscribers

ANOVA ^a								
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression	8891.127	1	8891.127	1.393	.272 ^b		
	Residual	51044.049	8	6380.506				
	Total	59935.176	9					

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)
b. Predictors: (Constant), Internet subscribers (Millions)

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	369.138	55.987		6.593	.000	240.031	498.245
	Internet subscribers (Millions)	.952	.806	.385	1.180	.272	-.908	2.812

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	386.8440247	461.5044250	428.1200000	31.43092493	10
Residual	-94.9440231	126.7101898	.0000000000	75.30976668	10
Std. Predicted Value	-1.313	1.062	.000	1.000	10
Std. Residual	-1.189	1.586	.000	.943	10

a. Dependent Variable: GDP (BILLION USD)

Table 4.9 is used to test whether our model is better than just using the mean to predict an outcome. A p value of .278 is not statistically significant and indicates that the regression model generated is a poor predictor of GDP. Though the number of internet subscribers contribute to GDP outcomes, there are other stronger predictors variables for GDP. Regardless, the number of internet subscribers is an indicator of growing revenues in internet shopping.

The coefficients help to formulate the linear regression line. When using the formula method, and the numbers above can be plugged into the formula to help us make accurate predictions. That means, the formula can be used to predict GDP (outcome) variable when the knowledge

of the number of internet subscribers (predictor variable) is derived. The B value as indicated by the constant is our intercept. This indicates the point where the number of internet subscriber's indicator is zero. The unstandardized item under internet users is the weight of the regression line. The associated t-test results tell whether the predictor is statistically significant or not. The p values indicate mixed results.

Figure 4. 3: GDP and internet subscribers

Figure 4.3 indicates that the residual seems to be normally distributed around the mean. This is a good sign because it is consistent with the assumptions of the linear regression.

Figure 4. 4 indicates that there are fairly a few distributed scores as indicated by the regression standardised predicted value and the regression standardised residual. The fair distribution of scores is around the mean, and thus, it can be said that the assumptions for regression have been met. Overall, though the number of internet subscribers can help to predict GDP, there are other predictors that can yield better results. Other indicators must be used to help build a good model.

Figure 4. 4: Normal P-P Plot

4.3 Survey Results: Reliability Analysis

The literature suggests that a higher level of Cronbach’s coefficient alpha indicates a higher reliability of the measurement scale. From the results provided in table 4.10, the Cronbach’s Alpha value for each research construct ranges from 0.525 to 0.835 validity as indicated. Furthermore, the item total values ranged from 0.537 to 0.825.

Table 4. 10: Reliability statistics

Research Construct	Reliability Statistics		
	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
Influence of social media	.651	.647	4
Perceived value	.545	.549	2
Privacy and trust	.631	.632	5
Brand reputation	.525	.537	3
System availability and functionality	.607	.608	3
Most influential factors for online repurchases	.835	.818	8
Other influential factors for online repurchases	.830	.825	6

Considering the outcome from the results provided in table 1.10, the Cronbach’s Alpha value for each of the research constructs ranges from 0.525 to 0.830 as indicated. Furthermore, the item total values ranged from 0.537 to 0.825. This is consistent with Dunn, Seaker and Waller

(1994), Chinomona (2011), who suggest that the cut-off point should be at least 0.5. The results obtained for each of the constructs are discussed here in turn.

4.3.1 Research Construct 1: Influence of Social Media

Table 4.11 below presents the unadjusted reliability statistics for research construct (Influence of Social Media).

Table 4. 11: Reliability for social media construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.651	.647	4

For the four items in the influence of social media construct, the Cronbach's Alpha result was 0.651, and the associated standardised value of .647. This was above the cut-off point of 0.5, the item total statistics suggest that if one of the items is deleted, then the reliability will be reduced. As such, no items were deleted from this construct.

Table 4. 12: Item total statistics for social media construct

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online	4.1000	.91563	100
Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product	4.0500	.85723	100
Fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms	3.8400	1.10755	100
Social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting	3.7800	.98041	100

The mean scores are within the range of a five-point Likert scale, and the standard deviations range from .85 to 1.1.

Table 4. 13: Inter-item correlation matrix for social media construct

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix				
	Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online	Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product	Fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms	Social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting
Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online	1.000	.302	.325	.362
Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product	.302	1.000	.168	.181
Fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms	.325	.168	1.000	.544
Social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting	.362	.181	.544	1.000

The inter-item correlation matrix has positive scores, indicating that the items within this construct were all measuring the same think. This result suggests that a higher Cronbach alpha coefficient is likely.

Table 4. 14: Total item statistics for social media construct

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online	11.6700	4.728	.448	.207	.573
Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product	11.7200	5.517	.273	.099	.677
Fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms	11.9300	3.965	.490	.316	.541
Social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting	11.9900	4.252	.528	.336	.512

If the item “Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product”, is deleted, the Cronbach alpha coefficient will increase to 0.677. However, this is not much difference with the Cronbach alpha coefficient of .651 obtained for all the items. For this reason, all the items were retained.

Table 4. 15: Scale statistics for social media construct

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
15.7700	7.351	2.71120	4

The mean, variance, and standard deviations obtained for the 4 constructs is illustrated by table 4.15.

4.3.2 Research construct 2: Perceived Value

Table 1.3 below presents the reliability statistics for research construct (Perceived Value).

Table 4. 16: Reliability statistics for perceived value construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.545	.549	2

For the two items in the perceived value construct, the Cronbach's Alpha result was 0.545, and the associated standardised value of 0.549. This is above the cut-off point of 0.5 and thus makes this measure reliable. The associated inter-item correlation matrix and item total statistics are also illustrated by table 4.17.

Table 4. 17: Item total statistics for perceived value construct

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on	4.3000	.67420	100
When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more	4.1000	.59459	100

The mean and standard deviations of the 2 items are as illustrated by table 4.17. The mean is within the range of the five-point Likert scale used to measure this construct.

Table 4. 18: Inter-Item correlation matrix for perceived value construct

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix		
	When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on	When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more
When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on	1.000	.378
When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more	.378	1.000

The inter-item correlation matrix is positive, and this suggests that the 2 items were measuring the same construct.

Table 4. 19: Item total statistics for perceived value construct

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on	4.1000	.354	.378	.143	.
When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more	4.3000	.455	.378	.143	.

No items were deleted as this result provided the optimal outcome, as illustrated by table 4.19.

Table 4. 20: Scale statistics for perceived value construct

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
8.4000	1.111	1.05409	2

The mean, variance, and standard deviation of the 2 items used to measure this construct are as illustrated by table 4.11.

4.3.3 Research construct 3: Privacy and Trust

For the five items in the privacy and trust construct, the Cronbach's Alpha result was .631, and the associated standardised value of .632. Though this was above the cut-off point of 0.5, and thus makes this measure reliable and usable.

Table 4. 21: Reliability statistics for privacy and trust construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.631	.632	5

The associated inter-item correlation matrix and item total statistics are also illustrated by table 4.22.

Table 4. 22: Item total statistics for privacy and trust construct

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses	3.0800	1.26874	100
I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details	3.5100	1.18488	100
Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour	4.0400	.72363	100
I would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a 'Pay on delivery basis'	4.1100	.77714	100
I have bought items from online vendors even when I did not trust them	3.3700	1.40457	100

The mean score of the items range from 3.08 to 4.11. This is within the limits of the 5-point Likert scale used to measure this construct. The associated standard deviations range from 0.72 to 1.40.

Table 4. 23: Inter-item correlation matrix for privacy and trust construct

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix					
	I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses	I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details	Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour	I would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a 'Pay on delivery basis'	I have bought items from online vendors even when I did not trust them
I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses	1.000	.631	.107	.104	.306

I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details	.631	1.000	.141	.213	.146
Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour	.107	.141	1.000	.208	.363
I would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a 'Pay on delivery basis'	.104	.213	.208	1.000	.342
I have bought items from online vendors even when I did not trust them	.306	.146	.363	.342	1.000

The inter-item correlation matrix is positive, and this suggests that the 5 items were measuring the same construct. However, there are some low correlation coefficients such as .104, .107 and so forth. These have the impact of reducing the Cronbach alpha coefficient.

Table 4. 24: Item total statistics for privacy and trust construct

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cranach's Alpha if Item Deleted
I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses	15.0300	7.343	.493	.459	.515
I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details	14.6000	7.919	.453	.437	.540
Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour	14.0700	10.409	.302	.150	.617
I would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a 'Pay on delivery basis'	14.0000	10.162	.318	.165	.610
I have bought items from online vendors even when I did not trust them	14.7400	7.305	.403	.286	.578

The item total statistics suggests that is item “Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour”

is deleted, the Cronbach alpha coefficient for this construct will decrease to 0.617. Therefore, all the five items were included.

The mean, variance, and standard deviations obtained for the scale are as illustrated in table 4.25.

Table 4. 25: Scale statistics for privacy and trust construct

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
18.1100	12.341	3.51302	5

4.3.4 Research construct 4: Brand reputation

For the three items in the brand reputation construct, the Cronbach’s Alpha result was .525, and the associated standardised value of .537. Though this is above the cut-off point of 0.5 which indicates a high level of internal consistency for our scale. The associated inter-item correlation matrix and item total statistics are also illustrated below.

Table 4. 26: Reliability statistics for brand reputation construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.525	.537	3

Table 4. 27: Item total statistics for brand reputation

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space	4.0100	.74529	100
I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors	4.2000	.65134	100
I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy	4.3700	.54411	100

The item statistics reveal that the mean score ranges from 4.01 to 4.37. This is within the range of the five-point Likert scale used to measure this construct.

Table 4. 28: Inter-Item correlation matrix for Brand reputation

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix			
	I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space	I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors	I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy
I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space	1.000	.266	.240
I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors	.266	1.000	.331
I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy	.240	.331	1.000

The inter-item correlation matrix is positive, and this suggests that the 3 items were measuring the same construct.

Table 4. 29: Item total statistics for brand reputation construct

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space	8.5700	.955	.311	.097	.491
I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors	8.3800	1.046	.370	.146	.372
I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy	8.2100	1.238	.354	.134	.418

The item total statistics shows the Cronbach alpha coefficient if any of the items is deleted. Thus, all deletions will fall below .525, and as such, all items for this construct were retained.

Table 4. 30: Scale statistics for brand reputation construct

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
12.5800	1.963	1.40115	3

The mean, variance, and standard deviations obtained for the scale are as illustrated in table 4.30.

4.3.5 Research construct 5: System availability and functionality

For the three items in the system availability and functionality construct, the Cronbach's Alpha result was .607, and the associated standardised value of .608. This is above the cut-off point of 0.5, thus makes this measure reliable and usable.

Table 4. 31: Reliability statistics for system availability and functionality construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.607	.608	3

The associated inter-item correlation matrix and item total statistics are also illustrated below

Table 4. 32: Item total statistics for system availability and functionality construct

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website	4.2800	.65258	100
I am more likely to repurchase goods from websites that offer very good delivery	4.5000	.61134	100
I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries	4.2900	.60794	100

The item statistics reveal that the mean score ranges from 4.28 to 4.29. This is within the range of the five-point Likert scale used to measure this construct.

Table 4. 33: Inter-item correlation matrix for system availability and functionality construct

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix			
	I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website	I am more likely to repurchase goods from websites that offer very good delivery	I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries

I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website	1.000	.380	.277
I am more likely to repurchase goods from websites that offer very good delivery	.380	1.000	.367
I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries	.277	.367	1.000

All variables in the inter-item correlation matrix is positive, and this suggests that the 3 items were measuring the same construct.

Table 4. 34: Item total statistics for system availability and functionality construct

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website	8.7900	1.016	.397	.166	.537
I am more likely to repurchase goods from websites that offer very good delivery	8.5700	1.015	.467	.218	.433
I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries	8.7800	1.103	.386	.157	.550

The item total statistics shows the Cronbach alpha coefficient if item “I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries” is deleted will be 0.550. This, and other possible deletions will fall below 0.607, and as such, all items for this construct were retained.

Table 4. 35: Scale statistics for system availability and functionality construct

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
13.0700	1.965	1.40169	3

The mean, variance, and standard deviations obtained for the scale are as illustrated in table 4.35.

4.3.6 Research Construct 6: Most influential factors for online repurchases

For the eight items in the most influential factors for online repurchases construct, the Cronbach's Alpha result was .835, and the associated standardised value of 0.818. Though this is above the cut-off point of 0.5, the item total statistics suggest that if two items are deleted, then the reliability will be much improved.

Table 4. 36: Reliability statistics for most influential factors for online repurchases construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.835	.818	8

The item statistics reveal that the mean score ranges from 5.7 to 7.01. This is within the range of the eight-point scale used to measure this construct.

Table 4. 37: Item statistics for most influential factors for online repurchases construct

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Trust	7.0100	1.18488	100
Ease of use	6.8400	1.52898	100
Fulfilment derived from using website	6.0000	2.16958	100
Enjoyment derived from using website	5.7800	2.18618	100
Perceived value	6.8200	1.38812	100
Brand reputation	6.8800	1.10353	100
Online platform functionality	6.5400	1.72574	100
Privacy	6.8100	1.75634	100

Table 4. 38: Item total statistics for most influential factors for online repurchases construct

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted

Trust	45.6700	70.365	.578	.514	.818
Ease of use	45.8400	66.095	.596	.432	.812
Fulfilment derived from using website	46.6800	53.371	.794	.767	.779
Enjoyment derived from using website	46.9000	55.343	.711	.700	.794
Perceived value	45.8600	77.394	.161	.167	.858
Brand reputation	45.8000	79.273	.140	.106	.854
Online platform functionality	46.1400	59.879	.764	.707	.788
Privacy	45.8700	60.215	.732	.713	.792

The item total statistics shows the Cronbach alpha coefficients remain high if any of the items are deleted. As such, all the eight items were retained.

Table 4. 39: Scale statistics for most influential factors for online repurchases construct

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
52.6800	83.250	9.12415	8

The mean, variance, and standard deviations obtained for the scale are as illustrated in table 4.39.

4.3.7 Research Construct 7: Other influential factors for online repurchases

For the six items in the other influential factors for online repurchases construct, the Cronbach's Alpha result was .830, and the associated standardised value of .825. Though this is above the cut-off point of 0.5, the item total statistics suggest that if two items are deleted, then the reliability will be much improved.

Table 4. 40: Reliability statistics for other influential factors for online repurchases construct

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.830	.825	6

The associated inter-item correlation matrix and item total statistics are also illustrated in table 4.41.

Table 4. 41: Item statistics for other influential factors for online repurchases construct

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Product characteristics	5.2200	.89420	100
Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	5.4700	.78438	100
Brand reputation and status	4.9500	1.00880	100
Ease of use of website, delivery and returns	4.8600	1.37819	100
Pricing strategy	4.9100	1.08334	100
Available support, contact and responsiveness	4.9000	1.69670	100

The item statistics reveal that the mean score ranges from 4.86 to 5.47. This is within the range of the six-point scale used to measure this construct.

Table 4. 42: Inter-item correlation matrix for other influential factors for online repurchases construct

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix						
	Product characteristics	Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	Brand reputation and status	Ease of use of website, delivery and returns	Pricing strategy	Available support, contact and responsiveness
Product characteristics	1.000	.413	.371	.247	.333	.188
Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	.413	1.000	.260	.304	.276	.203
Brand reputation and status	.371	.260	1.000	.562	.532	.534
Ease of use of website, delivery and returns	.247	.304	.562	1.000	.729	.879
Pricing strategy	.333	.276	.532	.729	1.000	.775
Available support, contact and responsiveness	.188	.203	.534	.879	.775	1.000

All the correlation coefficients in the inter-item correlation matrix are positive, and this suggests that the six items were measuring the same construct.

Table 4. 43: Item total statistics for other influential factors for online repurchases

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Product characteristics	25.0900	23.355	.355	.280	.844
Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	24.8400	23.954	.346	.231	.845
Brand reputation and status	25.3600	20.576	.615	.391	.802
Ease of use of website, delivery and returns	25.4500	16.210	.822	.799	.750
Pricing strategy	25.4000	18.747	.779	.648	.769
Available support, contact and responsiveness	25.4100	14.446	.768	.823	.774

Table 4. 44: Scale statistics for other influential factors for online repurchases

Scale Statistics			
Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
30.3100	27.226	5.21787	6

The mean, variance, and standard deviations obtained for the scale are as illustrated in table 4.44.

4.4 Descriptive Analysis

This section focuses on descriptive analysis.

4.4.1 Demographics

The demographics of the respondents are presented here in turn.

4.4.1.1 Age of respondents

It was found that 46% of total respondents were (26-35) years old, 32% were (18-25) years old, 19% were (36 -50) years old and 3% were 51 years old and above. Data collected in this category had no missing values.

Figure 4. 5: Age of respondents

4.4.1.2 Ownership of a Smartphone

It was found that 78% of the respondents own a smartphone whilst 22% do not.

Figure 4. 6: Ownership of smartphone

Table 4. 45: Ownership of a smartphone

Do you own a smartphone?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	78	78.0	78.0	78.0
	No	22	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Data collected in this category had no missing values, as illustrated by table 4.45.

4.4.1.3 Time spent online

The pie chart below illustrates the percentage of the respondents on how much time they spend online daily. It was found that 40% spent 3-5 hours, 31% spent 1-2 hours, 28% spent 6 hours and above whilst only a percent (1%) spent less than an hour online. Data collected in this category had no missing values.

Figure 4. 7: Time spent online

4.4.1.4 Frequency of online shopping

Respondents were asked to indicate their frequency of shopping online. It was found that 43% of the respondents shop once a month, 16% once a week, 5% once per day, and 36% of the respondents indicated that they shop online multiple times a day. Data collected in this category had no missing values.

Figure 4. 8: Online shopping frequency

4.4.1.5 Frequency of buying through social media

Figure 4.9 present individual responses to how often do they buy products and services advertised through social media and mobile apps. It was revealed that 70% of respondents do occasionally, 17% do very often and 13% do not buy products and services advertised through social media and mobile apps. Data collected in this category had no missing values.

Figure 4. 9: Buying frequency

4.4.2 Influence of social media

This section assesses the perceptions on the influence of social media on customer repurchases.

4.4.2.1 Social media platforms and customer repurchases

Figure 4.10 presents responses to how repurchase of goods and services online is being influenced by social media platforms. It was revealed that 2% of respondents strongly disagreed, 47% agreed, 10% neither agree nor disagree, 5% disagree and 36% strongly agree that social platforms and tools influence consumer repurchases on the online platforms.

Figure 4. 10: Social media repurchases

Data collected in this category had no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.2.2 Review of products

Figure 4.11 below reveals that 32% of respondents strongly agreed, 47% agreed, 16% neither agree nor disagree, 4% disagree and 1% strongly disagree that rating and review of products purchased influence consumer repurchases.

Figure 4. 11: Rating and review of products

Data collected in this category had no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.2.3 Poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms

Figure 4.12 present individual responses to how fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media. It was revealed that 31% of respondents strongly agreed, 39% agreed, 19% neither agree nor disagree, 5% disagree and 6% strongly disagree.

Figure 4. 12: Fulfilled customers and poor reviews

Data collected in this category had no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.2.4 Social media platforms, transparency, and trust

The bar graph (see figure 4.13) reveal that 25% of respondents strongly agreed ,40% agreed, 25% neither agree nor disagree, 8% disagree and 2% strongly disagree that social media platform promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting.

Figure 4. 13: Social media and transparency

Data collected in this category had no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.3 Perceived Value

This section assesses the perceptions of perceived value on customer repurchase intentions.

4.4.3.1 Consumer's expectations and satisfaction

The bar graph (see figure 4.14) present individual responses to how repurchase can be counted on, when an actual product or service meets a consumer expectation and satisfaction is met. It was revealed that 41% of respondents strongly agreed, 49% agreed, 9% neither agree nor disagree and 1% disagree.

Figure 4. 14: Meeting customer expectations

4.4.3.2 Repurchase of same brand

The bar graph (see figure 4.15) reveal that 22% of respondents strongly disagreed, 26% disagreed, 10% neither agree nor disagree, 23% agree and 19% strongly agree that consumers are likely to repurchase with the same brand when purchased goods and services do not meet perceived expectations.

Figure 4. 15: Perceived expectations

Table 4. 46: Repurchasing the same brand

When purchased goods and services do not meet perceived expectations, consumers are likely to repurchase with the same brand

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	22	22.0	22.0	22.0
	Disagree	26	26.0	26.0	48.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	10	10.0	10.0	58.0
	Agree	23	23.0	23.0	81.0
	Strongly agree	19	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

There were no missing values, as illustrated by the table above. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.3.3 Shopping on a website

Figure 4.16, and table 4.47 present consumer’s responses to how they return in Nigeria to purchase more when they feel fulfilled shopping on a website. After analysis it was revealed that 23% of respondents strongly agreed, 64% agreed and 13% neither agree nor disagree.

Figure 4. 16: Online shopping in Nigeria

Table 4. 47: Fulfilment and return to purchase

When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neither Disagree nor agree	13	13.0	13.0	13.0
	Agree	64	64.0	64.0	77.0
	Strongly agree	23	23.0	23.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

There were no missing values, as illustrated by the table above. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.4. Privacy and Trust

This section assesses perceptions of privacy and trust on customer repurchase intentions.

4.4.4.1 Trusting Nigerian online businesses

Figure 4.17 present individual responses if it's easy trusting Nigerian online business. It was revealed that 12% of respondents strongly agreed, 34% agreed, 18% neither agree nor disagree, 22% disagree and 14% strongly disagree to find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses.

Figure 4. 17: Online business and trust

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.4.2 Privacy

Bar graph (see figure 4.18) present individual responses if they will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keep client's personal details. After analysis it shows that 21% of respondents strongly agreed, 36% agreed, 25% neither agree nor disagree, 9% disagree and 9% strongly disagree.

Figure 4. 18: Keeping customer personal details and repurchases

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.4.3 Feedback

Figure 4.19 present consumers responses if survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers to consumer behaviour. 25% of respondents strongly agreed, 57% agreed, 15% neither agree nor disagree and 3% disagreed.

Figure 4. 19: Requesting feedback

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.4.4 Online repurchases

Figure 4.20 revealed that almost 32% of total respondents strongly agreed, 51% agreed, 13% was uncertain that they would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a Pay on Delivery basis and 4% disagree.

Figure 4. 20: Pay on delivery

There were no missing values, as illustrated by the table above. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.4.5 Online vendors and trust

About (21%) strongly agree, (42%) agree, (8) % neither agree nor disagree and (11) %, (18) % disagree and strongly disagree respectively that they have bought items online vendors even when they did not trust them as illustrated by figure 4.21.

Figure 4. 21: Online purchases and trust

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.5 Brand Reputation

This section assesses perceptions of brand reputation on customer repurchase intentions.

4.4.5.1 Repurchasing brands with good reputation

Figure 4.22 present individual responses if they encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space. It was revealed that 25% of respondents strongly agreed, 54% agreed, 18% neither agree nor disagree and 3% of the respondents disagree.

Figure 4. 22: Brands with good reputation

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.5.2 Brands that deliver quality service

In terms of repurchases from brands that deliver quality service, 32% strongly agree, 57% agree, 10% neither agree nor disagree and 1% disagree. These were the responses obtained when respondents were presented with the evaluative statement, and the results are as illustrated by figure 4.23.

Figure 4. 23: Repurchasing quality brands

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.5.3 Trusted brands and online purchases

In terms of buying from trusted brands, 38% of respondents strongly agreed, 54% agreed, 4% neither agree nor disagree, 3% disagreed and 1% strongly disagree. This is how they responded when presented with the evaluative statement as illustrated by figure 4.24.

Figure 4. 24: Trusted brands

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.5.4. Brands with returns policy

Table and bar graph below present consumers responses to the evaluative statement stating that “I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy”. It was found that 40% of respondents strongly agreed, 57% agreed and 3% neither agree nor disagreed.

Figure 4. 25: Returns policy

There were no missing values. Therefore, this data is usable for further analysis.

4.4.6. System availability and functionality

This section assesses perceptions of system availability and functionality on customer repurchase intentions.

4.4.6.1 *Quality of goods and a better website*

Respondents were asked whether they would repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website. It was found that 38% of the respondents strongly agree, 53% agreed, 8% neither agreed nor disagreed and 1% disagreed. This is illustrated by figure 4.26.

Figure 4. 26: *Quality of goods and quality of the website*

4.4.6.2 *Websites that offer very good delivery*

Respondents were also asked if they were more likely to repurchase goods from websites that offer very good delivery. It was found that 55% strongly agreed, (41%) agreed, 3% neither agreed nor disagreed and 1% disagreed, as illustrated by figure 4.27.

Figure 4. 27: *Websites that offer good delivery*

4.4.6.3 Vendors who respond promptly to online queries

Respondents were also asked whether they would repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries. It was found that 36% strongly agreed, 58% agreed, 5% neither agreed nor disagreed and 1 % disagreed.

Figure 4. 28: Response to online queries

4.4.6.4 Vendors that provides quality online shopping experience

Respondents were also asked whether they would repurchase from an online vendor that provides quality shopping experience despite poor quality goods. It was found that 18% strongly agreed, 23% agreed, 7% neither agreed nor disagreed, 22 % disagreed, and 30% strongly disagreed, as illustrated by figure 4.29.

Figure 4. 29: Shopping experience

4.4.6.5 Aftersales and online repurchases

Respondents were also asked whether they were keen on receiving aftersales follow up as it will make me repurchase items online. It was found that 22% strongly agreed, 42% agreed,

33% neither agreed nor disagreed and 1 % disagreed, and 2% strongly disagreed. This is illustrated by figure 4.30.

Figure 4. 30: Aftersales

4.4.7 Completing a survey after online shopping

Respondents were asked about their attitudes towards completing a quick customer survey. It was revealed that 45% of respondents immediately take part in survey, 39% postpone survey for a later date, 14% are uninterested in completing the survey and 2% suggest other things.

Figure 4. 31: Quick customer survey

4.4.8 Most influential factors for online repurchases

This section presents respondents perceptions on the most influential factors for online repurchases.

4.4.8.1 Trust

Respondents were asked whether trust was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 97% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (40%), very influential (37%), somehow influential (14%), and influential (6%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.32.

Figure 4. 32: Trust

4.4.8.2 Ease of use

Respondents were asked whether the website’s ease of use was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 93% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (43%), very influential (30%), somehow influential (12%), and influential (8%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.33.

Figure 4. 33: Ease of use

4.4.8.3 Fulfilment derived from using website

Respondents were asked whether fulfilment derived from using the website was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 79 % were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (27%), very influential (33%), somehow influential (11%), and influential (8%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.34.

Figure 4. 34: Fulfilment derived from using website

4.4.8.4 *Enjoyment derived from using website*

Respondents were asked whether the enjoyment derived from using the website was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 78% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (19%), very influential (33%), somehow influential (18%), and influential (8%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.35.

Figure 4. 35: Enjoyment derived from using website

4.4.8.5 *Perceived value*

Respondents were asked whether the perceived value was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 94% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (36%), very influential (34%), somehow influential (20%), and influential (4%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.36.

Figure 4. 36: Perceived value

4.4.8.6 Brand reputation

Respondents were asked whether brand reputation was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 97% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (25%), very influential (54%), somehow influential (12%), and influential (6%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.37.

Figure 4. 37: Brand reputation

4.4.8.7 Online platform functionality

Respondents were asked whether the online platform functionality was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 86% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (34%), very influential (34%), somehow influential (13%), and influential (5%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.38.

Figure 4. 38: Online platform functionality

4.4.8.8 Privacy

Respondents were asked whether privacy was an influential factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 86% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely influential (53%), very influential (20%), somehow influential (9%), and influential (4%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.39.

Figure 4. 39: Privacy

4.4.9. Other influential factors for online repurchases

This section assesses perceptions of other factors that influence online repurchases.

4.4.9.1 Product characteristics

Respondents were asked whether product characteristics are an applicable factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 98% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely applicable (40%), very applicable (49%), applicable (8%), and moderately applicable (1%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.40.

Figure 4. 40: Product characteristics

4.4.9.2 Satisfaction and previous shopping experience

Respondents were asked whether customer satisfaction and previous shopping experience are an applicable factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 99% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely applicable (58%), very applicable (35%), applicable (5%), and moderately applicable (1%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.41.

Figure 4. 41: Previous shopping experience

4.4.9.3 Brand reputation and status

Respondents were asked whether brand reputation and status were an applicable factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 97% were positive, with responses ranging from

extremely applicable (32%), very applicable (42%), applicable (19%), and moderately applicable (4%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.42.

Figure 4. 42: Brand reputation and status

4.4.9.4 Ease of use of website, delivery and returns

Respondents were asked whether ease of use of website, delivery and returns were an applicable factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 86% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely applicable (41%), very applicable (35%), applicable (8%), and moderately applicable (2%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.43.

Figure 4. 43: Ease of use, delivery and returns

4.4.9.5 Pricing strategy

Respondents were asked whether pricing strategy is an applicable factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 98% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely applicable (33%), very applicable (42%), applicable (11%), and moderately applicable (12%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.44.

Figure 4. 44: Pricing strategy

4.4.9.6 Available support, contact and responsiveness

Respondents were asked whether Available support, contact and responsiveness are an applicable factor for online repurchase. It was revealed that 86% were positive, with responses ranging from extremely applicable (53%), very applicable (27%), applicable (5%), and moderately applicable (1%). This is as illustrated by figure 4.45.

Figure 4. 45: Available support, contact and responsiveness

4.5 Correlation Analysis

Correlations estimate the strength of the linear relationship between two (and only two) variables. Correlation coefficients range from -1.0 (a perfect negative correlation) to positive 1.0 (a perfect positive correlation). The closer correlation coefficients get to -1.0 or 1.0, the

stronger the correlation. The closer a correlation coefficient gets to zero, the weaker the correlation is between the two variables.

Table 4. 48: Interpretation guide for correlation co-efficient

Coefficient Range	Strength of Association
+/- .81 to +/- .100	Strong
+/- .61 to +/- .80	Moderate
+/- .41 to +/- .60	Weak
+/- .21 to +/- .40	Very weak
+/- .00 to +/- .20	None

4.5.1 Influence of social media

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between influence of social media, and other variables (perceived value, privacy and trust, and brand reputation). It was hypothesised that:

Null hypothesis: There is no relationship between influence of social media, and other variables (perceived value, privacy and trust, and brand reputation).

Alternative hypothesis: There is a relationship between influence of social media, and other variables (perceived value, privacy and trust, and brand reputation).

From the table below correlation coefficient for perceived value versus influence of social media is 0.541**. This is significant at the at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. Though there is a positive association, this is weak. With a p value of .000, the null hypothesis is rejected. It was also found that the influence of social media is positively correlated with privacy and trust. This is illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.509**. This is significant at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. Once again, the strength of the association is weak. Given a p value of 0.00, the null hypothesis is rejected. It was also found that there is a weak positive association between influence of media and brand reputation. This is illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.452**, and is significant at the 0.01 level, 2-tailed. The results also reveal a very weak correlation between influence of social media and system availability, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.370**, at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. With a p value of .000, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Further results reveal a non-existent relationship between influence of social media and factors for online repurchases. With a p value of .866, the null hypothesis is accepted. Finally, results also reveal a negative very weak correlation between influence of social media and other factors

for online repurchases, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of -0.220^{**} , 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.028, the null hypothesis is rejected.

4.5.2 Perceived value

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between perceived value, and other variables (privacy and trust, brand reputation, system functionality, and other factors for online repurchases). It was hypothesised that:

Null hypothesis: There is no relationship between perceived value, and other variables (privacy and trust, brand reputation, system functionality, and factors for online repurchases).

Alternative hypothesis: There is a relationship between influence of social media, and other variables (privacy and trust, brand reputation, system functionality, and factors for online repurchases).

The perceived value is weakly positively correlated with privacy and trust. This is illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.228^{**} , 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.022, the null hypothesis is rejected. It was also found that there is a very weak correlation between perceived value and brand reputation, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.269^{**} , at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.007, the null hypothesis is rejected. The results also reveal that there is a very weak positive correlation between perceived value and system availability, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.372^{**} , at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.000, the null hypothesis is rejected. Further results also reveal that there is a negative and very weak relationship between perceived value and other factors for online repurchases as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of -0.211^{*} , 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.028, the null hypothesis is rejected.

4.5.3 Privacy and Trust

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between privacy and trust, and other variables (brand reputation, system functionality, and factors for online repurchases). It was hypothesised that:

Null hypothesis: There is no relationship between privacy and trust, and other variables (brand reputation, system functionality, and factors for online repurchases).

Alternative hypothesis: There is a relationship between privacy and trust, and other variables (brand reputation, system functionality, and factors for online repurchases).

The results reveal a very weak but positive correlation between privacy and trust, and brand reputation, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.283**, at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.004, the null hypothesis was rejected. Further, it was found that there is a very weak positive correlation between privacy and trust, and factors for online repurchases, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.317**, at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. With a p value of 0.001, the null hypothesis was rejected. On the contrary, the relation between privacy and trust, and system availability, as well as other factors for online repurchases was found not to be significant.

4.5.4 Brand reputation

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between brand reputation, and other variables (system functionality, and factors for online repurchases). It was hypothesised that:

Null hypothesis: There is no relationship between brand reputation, and other variables (system functionality, and factors for online repurchases).

Alternative hypothesis: There is a relationship between brand reputation, and other variables (system functionality, and factors for online repurchases).

It was found that brand reputation is positively correlated with system availability and functionality, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.458**, at the .01 level, 2 tailed. However, the correlation is weak. With a p value of .000, the null hypothesis is rejected. There was evidence of a negative correlation between brand reputation and factors for online repurchases, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of -0.123. However, this result was not significant. Similarly, there was some evidence of a negative association between brand reputation and other factors for online repurchases, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of -0.136. Once again, this result was not significant.

Figure 4. 46: Correlation analysis

			Correlations						
			Influence of Social Media	Perceived Value	Privacy and Trust	Brand Reputation	System Availability and Functionality	Factors for Online Repurchases	Other Factors for Online Repurchases
Spearman's rho	Influence of Social Media	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.541**	.509**	.452**	.370**	.017	-.220*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.866	.028
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Perceived Value	Correlation Coefficient	.541**	1.000	.228*	.269**	.372**	-.041	-.211*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.022	.007	.000	.689	.035
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Privacy and Trust	Correlation Coefficient	.509**	.228*	1.000	.283**	.064	.317**	.074
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.022	.	.004	.525	.001	.461
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Brand Reputation	Correlation Coefficient	.452**	.269**	.283**	1.000	.458**	-.123	-.136
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.007	.004	.	.000	.223	.177
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	System Availability and Functionality	Correlation Coefficient	.370**	.372**	.064	.458**	1.000	-.111	-.164
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.525	.000	.	.273	.102
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Factors for Online Repurchases	Correlation Coefficient	.017	-.041	.317**	-.123	-.111	1.000	.573**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.866	.689	.001	.223	.273	.	.000
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Other Factors for Online Repurchases	Correlation Coefficient	-.220*	-.211*	.074	-.136	-.164	.573**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	.035	.461	.177	.102	.000	.
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

4.6 Regression Analysis

The survey instrument was designed to collect nominal and ordinal data. Following from this, ordinal regression analysis selected for the primary data sets. Linear regression is conducted for the secondary data sets.

4.6.1 Performance, perceived value, and trust

The researcher used ordinal regression model to determine the relationship between performances and perceived, trust. Under ordinal regression, the researcher dealt with Model Fitting Information, Goodness-of-Fit, Pseudo R-Square, Parameter Estimates and Test of Parallel Lines.

Table 4. 49: Performance, perceived value, and trust- Ordinal Regression

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on	Disagree	1	1.0%
	Neither Disagree nor agree	9	9.0%
	Agree	49	49.0%
	Strongly agree	41	41.0%
I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses	Strongly disagree	14	14.0%
	Disagree	22	22.0%
	Neither Disagree nor agree	18	18.0%
	Agree	34	34.0%
	Strongly agree	12	12.0%
I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space	Disagree	3	3.0%
	Neither Disagree nor agree	18	18.0%
	Agree	54	54.0%
	Strongly agree	25	25.0%
I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website	Disagree	1	1.0%
	Neither Disagree nor agree	8	8.0%
	Agree	53	53.0%
	Strongly agree	38	38.0%
Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online	Strongly disagree	2	2.0%
	Disagree	5	5.0%
	Neither Disagree nor agree	10	10.0%
	Agree	47	47.0%
	Strongly agree	36	36.0%
Valid		100	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		100	

Table 4.49 illustrates the proportion of cases in each category. It indicates there is no missing values and all 100 scores are valid. Forthwith, the researcher investigated whether the model gives adequate predictions. Therefore, the researcher examined the model fitting information

Model Fitting Information was tested to determine whether the model improve our ability to predict the outcome. The chi-square statistic ($p < 0.05$) indicates that the model gives a significant improvement over the baseline intercept only model. This fundamentally tells us

that the model gives better predictions than if it was guessed based on the marginal probabilities for the outcome categories.

Table 4. 50: Model fitting information

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	157.508			
Final	118.375	39.133	14	.000

Table 4. 51: Goodness of fit

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	151.870	148	.397
Deviance	93.614	148	1.000

As reflected in the table 4.50, Goodness-of-Fit contains Pearson's chi-square statistic for the model and another chi-square statistic based on the deviance. These statistics are intended to test whether the observed data are inconsistent with the fitted model. Table 4.51 demonstrates that based on Pearson's Chi-square statistic and Chi-square statistic based on the deviance, the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis as $p > 0.05$ suggesting the model does fit very well.

Table 4. 52: R-Square

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.574
Nagelkerke	.637
McFadden	.520

For the ordinal regression models, it not possible to compute the same R^2 statistic as in linear regression so three approximations are computed instead that are Cox and Snell, Nagelkerke and McFadden. As reflected in table 4, Nagelkerke is .637, suggesting the model explain 63.7% of the variance in the dependent variables. Therefore, 63.7% of the variance in the outcome is explained by explanatory variables which indicates the fitting model is good.

Table 4. 53: Test of parallel lines

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	118.375			
General	83.783 ^b	34.592 ^c	28	.182

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

- a. Link function: Logit.
- b. The log-likelihood value cannot be further increased after maximum number of step-halving.
- c. The Chi-Square statistic is computed based on the log-likelihood value of the last iteration of the general model. Validity of the test is uncertain.

The test of parallel lines can help you assess whether the assumption that the parameters are the same for all categories is reasonable. The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories. As reflected in table 5, the significance of our Chi-Square statistic is $.182 > .05$ that determines null hypothesis is rejected. Consequently, for the model, the proportional odds assumption appears to have held because the significance of Chi-Square statistic is $.182 > .05$. Hence, ordered logit coefficients are equal across the levels of the outcome and the effect of explanatory variables are consistent (proportional) across the different thresholds

As reflected in the table 4.54, Parameter Estimates table contains the coefficients, their standard errors, the Wald test, and associated p-values (Sig.), the 95% confidence interval of the coefficients and odds ratios. Parameter Estimates suggests if p- values less than alpha level they are statistically significant otherwise not. The findings indicate that there is significant association between performance and trust as $p < 0.05$ for all elements of strategic technology alliance in the Location estimates.

For variables PVA=1; PVA= 2, PVA=3, PTA=1, PTA=2, PT=3 and PTA=4, a default reference point was set at location PTA=5. In other words, PTA=5 is the reference point. PTA=3 is -2.95, which is less than our reference point. This indicates that lower cumulative scores are more likely for this variable. Similarly, PTA=2 estimate value of -4.52 is less than

the reference variable and indicates that lower cumulative scores than the reference variable are more likely. Further, the estimate for PVA=2 is -7.274, and this is lower than the reference variable. Again, this suggests that lower cumulative scores are more likely. PVA=3 has an estimate value of -4.290 and is lower than the reference variable. Hence, lower cumulative scores are more likely. However, for all the variables PVA=1; PVA= 2, PVA=3 PTA=3 and PTA=4, there is a statistically significant result as represented by p values of .000, .000, .001, .008 and 0.009 respectively.

Table 4. 54: Parameter estimates

		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[PVa = 2]	-7.274	1.432	25.795	1	.000	-10.081	-4.467
	[PVa = 3]	-4.290	.954	20.205	1	.000	-6.160	-2.419
	[PVa = 4]	-.634	.777	.666	1	.001	-2.157	.889
Location	[PTa=1]	.830	.915	.824	1	.364	-.963	2.623
	[PTa=2]	-.452	.791	.327	1	.008	-2.002	1.098
	[PTa=3]	-.295	.852	.120	1	.009	-1.965	1.374
	[PTa=4]	.281	.727	.149	1	.700	-1.145	1.706
	[PTa=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[BRa=2]	1.955	1.842	1.126	1	.289	-1.656	5.565
	[BRa=3]	-.875	.722	1.469	1	.226	-2.289	.540
	[BRa=4]	-.430	.560	.590	1	.442	-1.528	.667
	[BRa=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[SAFa=2]	-.912	2.631	.120	1	.729	-6.069	4.244
	[SAFa=3]	.420	.866	.235	1	.628	-1.277	2.116
	[SAFa=4]	-.619	.476	1.689	1	.194	-1.552	.314
	[SAFa=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[ISMa=1]	-6.465	1.942	11.077	1	.001	-10.271	-2.658
	[ISMa=2]	-1.550	1.199	1.670	1	.196	-3.900	.800
	[ISMa=3]	-3.395	.897	14.328	1	.000	-5.153	-1.637
	[ISMa=4]	-.246	.491	.251	1	.616	-1.208	.716
[ISMa=5]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.	

Link function: Logit.

a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

For variables BRA=2, BRA=3, BRA=4, the reference point is set at variable BRA=5, which is a zero. Considering this, BRA=2 has an estimate value of 1.955. This is higher than the reference variable, and thus lower cumulative scores are unlikely. Similarly, BRA=3 has an estimate value of -0.875 which is lower than zero. Once again, lower cumulative scores are likely. Additionally, BRA=4 has an estimate value of -.430. This is less than zero, and hence, a lower cumulative score is likely. For all the variables BRA=2, BRA=3, BRA=4, there are statistically insignificant results as illustrated by p values of .289, .226 and .442 respectively.

For variables SAFA=2, SAFA=3, and SAFA=4, the reference point is set at SAFA=5. This has an estimate value of zero. Considering this SAFA=2 has an estimate value of -.912. This indicates that a lower cumulative score than the reference point is more likely. SAFA=3 has an estimate value of .420, and this indicates that a lower cumulative score than the reference point is more unlikely. SAFA=4 has an estimate value of -.619, which is less than the reference variable. This suggests that lower cumulative scores are more likely. For all the variables SAFA=2, SAFA=3 and SAFA=4, there are statistically insignificant results as illustrated by p values of .729, .628 and .194 respectively.

For variables ISMA=1, ISMA=2, and ISMA=3 and ISMA=4, the reference point is set at ISMA=5. This has an estimate value of zero. Considering this ISMA=1 has an estimate value of -6.465. This indicates that a lower cumulative score than the reference point is more likely. SAFA=3 has an estimate value of -1.550, and this indicates that a lower cumulative score than the reference point is more unlikely. SAFA=4 has an estimate value of -3.395, which is less than the reference variable. This suggests that lower cumulative scores are more likely. SLA=4 has an estimate value of -.246 which is lower than the reference point. This suggests that a lower cumulative score is more likely. For all the variables ISMA=1 and ISMA=3 I there are statistically insignificant results as illustrated by p values of .001 and .000 respectively. For SMA=2, and ISMA=4, there are statistically insignificant results as illustrated by p values of .196 and .616 respectively.

The researcher then converted the estimates into odds ratio by finding their exponents. In other words, it is important to take the exponents of the estimate values to get the odds. In fact, the odds ratio is a relative measure of effect, which allows the comparison of the intervention group of a study relative to the reference variable. In other words, the odds ratio represents the

constant effect of a predictor variable, on the likelihood that one outcome will occur. This is illustrated in table 4.55.

Table 4. 55: Odds ratio

<i>Location</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Odds ratio</i>	<i>Chance</i>
[PTA=1]	.830	0.436041193	43.60%
[PTA1=2]	-.452	0.636305153	63.63%
[PTA1=3]	-.295	0.744531271	74.45%
[PTA1=4]	-.281	0.755024003	75.50%
[BRA=2]	1.955	0.044600955	4.46%
[BRA=3]	-.875	0.416863203	41.68%
[BRA=4]	-.430	0.650523230	65.05%
[SAFA=2]	-.912	0.401781065	40.17%
[SAFA=3]	.420	0.724137903	72.41%
[SAFA=4]	-.6190	0.538481292	53.84%
[ISMA=1]	-6.465	0.001556324	0.15%
[ISMA=2]	-1.550	0.212247540	21.22%
[ISMA=3]	-3.395	0.033541023	3.35%
[ISMA=4]	-.2460	0.781925130	78.19%

The assumption of proportional odds is that the odds are meant to be the same no matter which levels of ordinal outcomes. Yet, the results reveal a chance of 63.63%, 74.45% and 75.45% for outcomes PTA1=2, PTA1=3 and PTA1=4 variables respectively. Similarly, results reveal a chance of 41.68%, 65.05%, for BRA1=2, BRA1=3, BRA1=4, outcomes respectively. Similarly, results reveal a chance of 40.17%, 72.41% and 53.85% for SAFA=2, SAFA=3 and SAFA=4 outcomes respectively. In a similar vein, results reveal a chance of 0.15%, 21.22%, 3.35% and 78.19% for outcomes ISMA=1, ISMA=2, ISMA=3, and ISMA= 4 variables respectively.

4.7 Qualitative results

This section discusses the qualitative findings of the study. Firstly, content analysis is used to explore the patterns emerging from the data. Here, results are presented using a word cloud. This is followed by thematic analysis to help contextualise the patterns emerging from the content analysis. The emergent themes are discussed in more detail and illustrated using extracts from the respondents.

4.7.1 Background

A word cloud was generated to see the patterns in the data collected. The most prominent and meaningful words included “customers”, “attires”, “online”, “fashion”, “managers”, and so forth. This pattern is illustrated by figure 4.47.

Figure 4. 47: Word cloud on background theme

The emergent meanings of these words included background of the respondent, personalisation, product quality, role in the company, type of business, and years of experience. These are illustrated by the coding query, as presented in figure 4.48.

Figure 4. 48: Sub-themes on background

	A : Interview subject G	B : Interview subject L	C : Interview subject M	D : Interview subject O
1 : Background of respondent	1	0	0	0
2 : Personalisation	0	0	2	0
3 : Product quality	0	0	1	0
4 : Role in company	2	0	1	1
5 : Type of business	2	0	1	1
6 : Years of experience	1	1	1	1

It was found that respondents talked about their role in their respective companies, type of business they are in, and years of experience in the business. This background information was vital to establish an understanding of the type of respondents, their knowledge and depth of their businesses, as illustrated by figure 4.49.

Figure 4. 49: Matrix coding query on background

Whilst the study is taking an interpretive approach, the NVivo software provides an opportunity to quantify the word frequency, and this helps to visualise the emergent themes in relation to the text coded. This is important to show progression from content analysis to thematic analysis. It also helps to enhance the iterative process of thematic analysis. Similar graphics were used to analyse and visualise all the other themes.

4.7.1.1 Years of experience

When asked about their experience in their business or industry, the respondents had this to say:

Table 4. 56: Years of experience

Respondent	Years of experience
G	2 years
L	For about four years now
M	Errrrm, we have been in business for about 12 years now but our online presence I would say has been (quick pause) around 5 years.
O	Well we are nearing our 4th year. We should be 4 years old in September.

The fact that the respondents’ business continues to operate for at least 2 years, or more is interpreted as an indication of business sustainability. Whatever they are doing, they are making their business to continue operating whilst others are closing. This suggests that the respondents are knowledgeable about their businesses and appear to be making the right decisions.

4.7.1.2 Type of business

Respondents G has business within the educational sector, as illustrated by the extract below:

...when certain exams are close, it is the reason to market to such individuals taking those exams...getting a tutor is not cheap....

This suggests that the business is educational because of the use of the term “exams”, “tutor”, and so forth, that are often associated with teaching and learning. On the other hand, respondent M is in fashion, as illustrated by the extract below:

we design, make and sell bespoke fashion outfits from suits to traditional attires and selected casual trends for both male and female customers. We also make attires for kids. Because you know the fashion industry is a very diverse and wide one, we have different departments that take care of selected areas of fashion.

For respondent O, their business is in different product categories, as illustrated by the extract below:

We sell basically everything from daily consumer goods to specialised items like phones and gadgets and we are now branching into selling travel tours and deals. We do a lot of sales mostly, we sell shoes, clothing, products generally.

Thus, the respondents share insights from different industries and backgrounds. In this sense, understandings derived help to obtain a perspective from different areas of business and industries.

4.7.1.3 Role in company

Respondent G reported that he was the founder of the company, and employs other managers as illustrated by the extract below:

We have the product lead, product manager. He joined us in august, but before then it was me. So, the pictures, the copies the terms they design I worked on it but now he does all (Interview subject G).

Not only is respondent G a founder but has managerial responsibilities. Similarly, respondent M had this to say:

I am responsible for marketing and business development here in Delta state. So, my department retrieves information from customers, we build up the company's marketing plans for increased sales.... (Interview subject M)

As for respondent M, his role also involves business development, as well as developing marketing plans. He runs a department, and thus has managerial responsibilities. In a similar vein, respondent O had this to say:

I am a business development manager here. I have a software and computer sciences background and I am actively involved with the online purchasing and

customers who come to us online, what they do and buy. I am also involved with things associated with website contents; you know ads. That's why I decided to take the time out for this interview when you mentioned it was about online customer repurchase intentions (Interview subject O).

Respondent O reveals that sort of training that some of these managers have. They are experts in their fields with different training levels. As for respondent O, he is a manager with “software and computer sciences background”. This is interpreted to mean that he has expertise in his line of business, as illustrated by the extract above.

4.7.2 Company Website

A word cloud was generated to see the patterns in the data collected about the company website. The most prominent and meaningful words included “customers”, “know”, “trust”, “website”, “social”, “media”, “visitors”, “online”, and so forth. This pattern is illustrated by figure 4.50.

Figure 4. 50: Word cloud on company website

The emergent meanings of these words included continuous improvement, ease of use, simplicity, online sales, web traffic, social media, trust, honesty, transparency, and so forth, as illustrated by the coding query, and presented in figure 4.51.

Figure 4. 51: Emergent themes on company website

	A : Interview subject G	B : Interview subject L	C : Interview subject M	D : Interview subject O
1 : Continuous improvement	1	0	0	1
2 : Decision making	0	3	0	0
3 : Ease of use	3	1	2	1
4 : Honesty	1	0	0	0
5 : Online sales	0	0	1	4
6 : Relevance	0	1	0	0
7 : Simplicity	0	0	1	1
8 : Social media	2	2	3	1
9 : Tracking system	0	0	1	1
10 : Transparency	1	0	0	0
11 : Trust	3	0	1	2
12 : Web traffic	0	0	1	1

It was found that a higher concentration of the discussion was around the website’s ease of use, social media, online sales, and trust, as illustrated by figure 4.52.

Figure 4. 52: Matrix coding query on company website

4.7.2.1 Ease of use and simplicity

Respondents revealed that customers prefer a website that is easy to use, and simple. This is illustrated by the extract below:

no hanky panky so that they can understand what they are going into. Some people would say ah I have already filled the form and you’re showing me one big amount and they run away. They also look at ease of use and that’s because on this side of the world most people are, I don’t know if its internet lazy, but they don’t want to do it themselves, they want to, they want it to be easy. If it involves so much about they have to think, or its complex, they are not interested (Interview subject G).

The” hanky panky” are interpreted as complexities. So, there must be no “hanky panky”. This means that there must be simplicity. If the online platform lacks clarity and simplicity, customers “runaway”. Therefore, “ease of use” is required. Customers want the website “to be easy”. In fact, customers “are not interested” in anything that is “complex”. This was also reinforced by interview subject L when he had this to say:

I mean, generally I think people want to see very fast what they came there to see. So this could be funny – so if I found your sites looking for how can I buy water but if I am seeing how to make meat-pie, or how to make, I will just leave...So it’s really just how to quickly get to the point for what they are there for and basically you have a very short window maybe 15 seconds or even less. Customers decide to leave if they don’t see what they are looking for. So, I would say that.

So, when customers visit a website, they expect to find what they are looking for and not to be tangled in the complexity of multiple click buttons. In fact, “people want to see very fast what they came there to see”. Here, speed of access is of essence. Customers want to “quickly get to the point for what they are there for” within a very short space of time.

4.7.2.2 Social media

Another theme that emerges in connection with the website is social media. This is illustrated

by the extract below:

Errrm, yes word of mouth is about 30% of our customers the others are via marketing efforts we make on social media primarily Facebook (Interview subject G).

It was found that both traditional medias, including “word of mouth” and social media, are avenues that are used by the respondents’ organisations for marketing purposes. This is reinforced by interview subject L, and interview subject M, as illustrated by the extracts below:

Partly, I don’t know if I can say a lot but obviously people do come from social media to purchase items... Facebook LinkedIn Instagram Twitter (Interview subject L).

At the moment most of these online visitors come from certain social media platforms, some of them just click on and off, others view a selection of attires but don’t check out completely either due to measurement issues or we suspect the prices being out of their range (Interview subject M).

However, some customers are moved by what they see on social media whilst some are not moved at all, as illustrated by the extract below:

As a customer, when I see ads on social media outlets, I am hardly moved to be honest, I am more of a need/necessity guy. I buy what I want/need when necessary and from where I can rely on satisfying me. But on the other hand, we are able to tell where visitors on our sites have come from, either they came as a result of an ad prompt or if they entered the website URL directly on their desktop or mobile browser. That’s how we know what platforms to invest more and what times our ads are more seen and more efficient. So, I would say yes, at least 40 – 50% of our first-time visitors come through social media platforms (Interview subject M).

It is suggested that managers must use both online and offline platforms to ensure that they reach their customers more effectively. Whilst there is an increasing trend towards the use of online shopping and social media to engage with customers, managers must also continue to use traditional avenues because some customers do not easily adapt to innovations.

4.7.2.3 Online sales, traffic

Another theme that emerged is that of online sales and web traffic. This is illustrated by interview subject M when he had this to say:

We hardly record any online purchases daily. What we do have are completed reservations with deposits and with this we have around 30 – 45 daily. When this is done, appointment is made for the customer. We have a reservation software for this. Client is notified of the next available dates and they can confirm which one

suits them. But with our casuals, we have around 16 – 30 orders daily but like I said our fabrics are pricy, so we don't expect huge figures (Interview subject M).

Others “hardly record any online purchases daily”. However, they have “completed reservations with deposits”. This illustrates online engagement by the consumers. An online booking system is used, and this requires specific resources, such as “a reservation software”. Engagement with the online platform is also reinforced by interview subject O, when he had this to say:

And I mean active visitors not erm you know some people just stumble on our page from ads, they click on us one time and they go. I mean people who peruse the website, they go around because they want to shop and those who do shop with us eventually... Well in the last nine to 12 months, on these 250 to 350 visitors, we do get around 70 purchases per day and during the weekends we have a lot more around 120 to 150 purchases... Bear in mind we have a few stores in Delta state but we have close to 49% of our sales coming through online platforms (Interview subject O).

This illustrates the growing trend of online sales. However, it is not everyone who visits the website that buys. Others “stumble” and “go”. Therefore, managers must ensure that no one “stumbles” by making the online purchasing process simple.

4.7.2.4 Trust, honesty, transparency

It also emerged that purchases on the online platform require trust, honesty and transparency. This is illustrated by the extracts below:

Trust is major, it's the challenge the first time they come... But we do pay upfront so there is that need for trust. I have not received any classes and you're telling me to pay (short laugh) ... So, once we cross that hurdle and they see that our tutors deliver, they have more trust and also we found that people who are referred by friends naturally have high trust so they don't even ask questions, they just pay because most likely their friends has told them (Interview subject G).

Trust is a major challenge. For this reason, customers are sceptical about making payment upfront. In fact, trust must be earned, and thereafter customers can make referrals. These referrals are often made by highly trusted people such as friends. Interview subject M explains that issues of fraud and “fake merchandising” affect both customers and vendors.

The online shopping scene has experienced issues with fraud and fake merchandising and trust me both customers and vendors face these problems. So, I would say for first time visitors using online platforms, they are hardly trusting but might be willing to take the risks but in repurchase then the trust factor is now replaced with how they perceive the particular company or product you know what I mean? (Interview subject M).

Because of fraud, first time users are always sceptical of online shopping. However, once trusted relations have been established, online purchases occur.

Hmm, well in Nigeria the stance on trust for our customers, let me say for the first-time customers, usually around negative tending to indifferent. They are more likely to distrust going online to buy something than trust it.... But with the second time purchase, what or how we've done or how they find our services and products beats the trust. They now have trust somehow so when they come back, trust doesn't really play a role anymore at that time. But I would say that the Nigerian customers who patronise us for the first time they either don't trust much or they don't care about trust. Their decision doesn't rest on trust. They take the risk when they want to buy what they need from you (Interview subject O).

Thus, customers always perceive the risks of doing online purchases. For this reason, traditional sales avenues must always be kept open.

4.7.2.5 Continuous improvement, tracking

Also emerging from the data is the idea of continuously improving the company website and engaging with tracking systems. This is illustrated by the extract below:

So, I mean right now we are redesigning our entire website cos we've not done any redesign since we launched it initially 2 years ago so now, we are doing it. At this point we are not solely looking at where they are having challenges, cos the whole design is changing we are looking at what we want them to know when they land on the website (Interview subject G).

Continuous improvement also means “redesigning” the “entire website”. Managers identify areas of the website posing some challenges, and then make improvements as appropriate. This is reinforced by the extract below:

When we notice customers, who have had issues repeatedly, we reach out to them directly to find out if their system is compatible enough for the version of the software we are using or what not. Some people need further help and we are willing to offer it, so this is what makes us stand out to our customers – that direct means. That's what I think the Nigerian customers who patronise us want, that direct link for communication (Interview subject O).

Here, there is a continuous review of the system that is informed by customer feedback. This direct interaction with customers also helps to meet the needs of customers more effectively. Further, the notion of continuous improvement is enhanced by tracking systems as illustrated by interview subject M when he says:

we have a tool that sort of tells us how our customers use our website, where they spend more time, what they seem to like and dislike. It just helps us in generating

electronic information or should I say data. You know like analysable data so to speak. So, we cannot really see much and most of this monitoring should I say cookies, the customer has to agree to us using this the moment they load our website and because no sensitive information is collected, there is definitely no breach in privacy. Some of our customers save their details on our sites and have no fear because they know we respect their privacy which is very important to them because they pay lots of money to us and it is the least we can do you know (Interview subject M)

These tracking tools help to monitor customer behaviour, and managers note what the customers “*seem to like and dislike*”. This information is used to improve the service provision. However, in doing so, managers respect the privacy and confidentiality of their customers.

4.7.3 Customer repurchases

A word cloud was generated to see the patterns in the data collected about customer repurchases. The most prominent and meaningful words included “customers”, “know”, “trust”, “brand”, “website”, “time”, “experience”, “service”, “online”, and so forth. This pattern is illustrated by figure 4.53.

Figure 4. 53: Word cloud on company repurchases theme

The emergent meanings of these words included brand reputation, customer satisfaction, personalisation, service quality, trust, and so forth, as illustrated by the coding query, and presented in figure 4.54.

Figure 4. 54: Emergent themes on company repurchases

	A : Interview subject G	B : Interview subject L	C : Interview subject M	D : Interview subject O
1 : Brand reputation	1	1	1	1
2 : Communication	2	0	0	0
3 : Customer satisfaction	0	0	0	1
4 : Empathy	0	1	0	0
5 : Engagement	2	1	1	0
6 : Idleness	1	0	0	0
7 : Other offers	1	0	0	0
8 : Personalisation	0	2	2	1
9 : Pricing	1	0	0	0
10 : Process	0	0	2	0
11 : Review	1	0	0	0
12 : Seasonality	2	0	0	0
13 : Service quality	1	1	1	1
14 : Social media	0	0	0	1
15 : Testimonials	1	0	0	0
16 : Time period	1	0	0	0
17 : Trust	4	1	2	3

It was found that a higher concentration of the discussion was around brand reputation, engagement, personalisation, service quality and trust, as illustrated by figure 4.55.

Figure 4. 55: Matrix coding query on company repurchases

4.7.3.1 Brand reputation

An emergent theme that encourages customer repurchase is that of brand reputation, as illustrated by the extract below:

we still need to do more about the brand reputation and awareness. I think so far; we try to listen to what our customers say when they speak to us. That gives us an idea of what brand we represent to them. They see us as a place to find good teachers. That's the word they use, I want someone that is very good. And they also, in a way they see us as expensive (Interview subject G).

Here, the focus is on building brand reputation as a route through which customer repurchases may occur. Within this, the managers listen to “what the customers say when they speak”. This is interpreted as paying attention to the needs of the customers. In this way, a positive brand reputation is built. Similarly, interview subject M had this to say:

We might be a smaller corporation, or should I say business when compared to other fashion delivery outlets here in Nigeria, but our customers know what we can deliver, and that reputation influences them repurchasing with us. Our reputation might not be the biggest push on new customers but it is definitely very influential when it comes to our existing customers and them coming back to shop with us. In my opinion I believe that first time shoppers who patronize us do this mostly through referrals and how niche the content or messages on our ads can be. You know the saying in Nigeria – ‘who know go know’ you know we sort of are like that, customers who know our quality know us and that keeps them coming back so we endeavour to retain that reputation cos it is not easy to please a majority of Nigerian customers (laughs) they are quite dynamic and what you think might apply more often than not doesn’t work.

It was found that reputation influences customer repurchases. A positive reputation leads to other referrals. Here, their reputation is built around the quality of service that they provide. In this sense, brand reputation is a strategic resource for customer repurchases. This is also reinforced by interview subject O when he states that:

Honestly, I would say not really but I do understand that our brand’s reputation over time makes customers more likely to repurchase, but it is not a big influencer. It is one of the influencers like you would say, I am using your word now influencer. But what I understand from brand reputation is the fact that our customers come online, and we can deliver what they want over time, the fact that they can now rely on us. In that regard, it influences them specifically because we are a small brand we are not as big as the (brief pause) permit me to mention the name because they are not my brand but because we are not as big as the kongas, the jumias they are the big ones, they have the huge brand reputations. It is out there you know publicly but we are smaller, our consumer base is smaller, so the brand reputation only affects that small part of the market that are already part of our consumer base if you understand me (Interview subject O).

4.7.3.2 Customer engagement

It also emerged that the company’s techniques to engage with customers are of importance.

This is illustrated by Interview subject G had this to say:

So, the quality of the service, the tutor themselves. We’ve found that if a client is not excited about a tutor, the propensity to come the next month is reduced but if they are super excited, what we found they come and then they get other services because now they know I got a maths tutor from you, I can also get guitar, piano tutor. They sort of outsource their learning to us once the first tutor really impressed them. That’s like a major reason why they come back (Interview subject G).

Here, the tutors engage with the learners in an active manner, and this has the effect of enhancing “*the quality of service*”. That excitement created between a learner and the tutor is the pull factor required to actively engage the learner. Once the learner is “super excited” with the service offered, then there is a higher propensity that they will seek for other related services provided within the educational establishment such as “*guitar, piano*”, and other related

services.

Further, clients engage with the company website. They also get engaged when problems that arise are resolved timeously, as illustrated by interview subject L in the extract below:

So, a lot has to do with experience on the website, how quick you are to resolve problems they have, resolve issues and how effective the product itself would be that's also a factor that affects them (Interview subject L).

Interview subject M reveals that “customers want responsiveness”. This reinforces the speed of service and the direct contact established with the customers. By saying “our customers need to know there is someone they can speak with directly”, interview subject M is drawing our attention to the importance of establishing personal contact with clients in the fashion business. This helps to create rapport, and make the customers feel wanted and cared for, as illustrated by the extract below:

Also, our customers want responsiveness, for some reasons, they might experience issues, how fast can you resolve these issues? And how much contact do you have? Our customers need to know there is someone they can speak with directly about issues like measurements and sizes, website navigation, or maybe they just want to feel very certain so they don't make mistakes (Interview subject M).

Further to that, it was found that customers engage with the web content, as illustrated by interview subject O:

So, it is a big boost for us. So when they use the website, if it is easy to use, they get like they are fulfilled, they buy what they want to buy, they get a lot of options, and then they feel like you relate to their needs particularly (Interview subject O).

By stating that customers “feel like you relate to their needs”, interview subject O is drawing our attention to understanding the needs of customers. Once these needs are fulfilled, repurchases are likely to occur.

4.7.3.3 Personalisation

Another emergent theme is that of personalisation of the service. This helps to encourage customer repurchases as illustrated by interview subject L:

I think it's how personalized their experience is on your website...So in my opinion when people think or feel like just an extra person using your website, they probably wouldn't use it but when there is a personalised feel. Say where possible you apply a personalised feel like 'hi John', or 'welcome back john' or 'hi john the last time you were here was last week Tuesday and you did this', you know those kinds of things, it feels very personal errrm so for instance when someone is having a crisis of some sort, the needed focus should be how to help them out of it as humanly as

possible not necessarily being defensive about the product saying 'oh it would work ooo'... This is really what I think makes customers come back to use our products cos they feel like you understand their own pin points (Interview subject L).

Thus, there is a need to personalise customer experience on the website. The customers must feel valued and wanted. There must be a “*personalised feel*”. For instance, the customers can be even greeted by their names when they visit the website like “*hi John*”, “*welcome back John*”. This suggests that the customer is already known and appreciated. It also gives the customers a sense of belonging, and thus mostly likely to result in customer repurchases.

Customers want responsiveness and a personalised service, as illustrated by interview subject M in the extract below:

Let me point this out, we have a system where on a client's first visit, their sizes and dimensions and I mean detailed because we do measure every part of a client's physical body. Now these dimensions are given to the client and with their permission stored on the portal so if they need to repurchase say when they are overseas and I tell you this happens all the time, they can place orders but only when they know that they haven't considerably changed since the time when measurement was taken. So eerrm yea... Also, our customers want responsiveness, for some reasons, they might experience issues, how fast can you resolve these issues? And how much contact do you have? Our customers need to know there is someone they can speak with directly about issues like measurements and sizes, website navigation, or maybe they just want to feel very certain so they don't make mistakes (Interview subject M).

At times, customer details are stored on a system to ensure that their needs are met timeously. However, these details are stored with the permission of the customer. This helps when the customer needs to make a repurchase because the required information will be retrieved at the click of a button. This on its own is indication that the customer is known and valued. It gives them a sense of belonging. However, any changes that might have occurred since the previous purchase are noted and incorporated into the repurchase plan. The availability of this personal information helps to resolve issues that arise quickly and timeously. This is also reinforced by interview subject O as he states:

The first time they come, if they made notes of any problems they faced, and next time they come online you have resolved those issues, or you've applied those suggestions, they feel like they have had a personalised experience, customers well I am speaking for our customers here, so once you do this, and give them this kind of personalised experience, make them know we value their patronage, they always come back. Their repurchase intention as you put it is sure, they come back surely (Interview subject O).

Here, we learn that customer feedback is important. The customer voices that come through this feedback must be listened to and actioned. By stating that “*if they made notes of any*

problems they faced, and next time they come online you have resolved those issues, or you've applied those suggestions, they feel like they have had a personalised experience", is interpreted as drawing insights from customer feedback and making improvements to the service. Therefore, it is imperative that user generated content on the online platform must be harvested and used effectively.

4.7.3.4 Service quality

It also emerged that service quality influences customer repurchase decisions as illustrated by interview subject G:

So, the quality of the service, the tutor themselves. We've found that if a client is not excited about a tutor, the propensity to come the next month is reduced but if they are super excited, what we found they come and then they get other services because now they know I got a maths tutor from you, I can also get guitar, piano tutor. They sort of outsource their learning to us once the first tutor really impressed them. That's like a major reason why they come back (Interview subject G).

The “*quality of the service*” offered by the “*tutor themselves*” influences customer repurchases. The aim must be to make the customer “*super excited*”, meaning that the tutor must be knowledgeable about the subject and deliver the learning materials in such a way that connects and remains memorable to the learner. In fact, the tutors must be passionate and enthusiastic about their subjects, and at the same time, create rapport with the learners using techniques that engage the learners in the learning process.

Further, an ability to resolve customer problems timeously is important, as illustrated by Interview subject L:

So, a lot has to do with experience on the website, how quick you are to resolve problems they have, resolve issues and how effective the product itself would be that's also a factor that affects them (Interview subject L).

Here, the product must deliver what is promised. When customers have issues or problems, they must be resolved quickly with the intention of keeping the customer satisfied. Similarly, “*customers want responsiveness*”, as illustrated by interview subject M:

Also, our customers want responsiveness, for some reasons, they might experience issues, how fast can you resolve these issues? And how much contact do you have? Our customers need to know there is someone they can speak with directly about issues like measurements and sizes, website navigation, or maybe they just want to feel very certain so they don't make mistakes (Interview subject M).

It also emerged that the contact with the customers is very important. In fact, “customers need

to know there is someone they can speak with directly”. This helps to reassure customers and build a trusting relationship that will eventually result in repurchases.

4.7.3.5 Trust and transparency

Trust and transparency also emerge as major factors that influence customer repurchases, as illustrated by interview subject G:

So that transparency helps them trust the system, it also helps them plan. We have clients call us and say so I am busy and I don't know when the month is ending or beginning but your platform helps me keep in touch of my schedule so I get notifications of how many lessons I have and now I can pay upfront before my lessons run out. But if you didn't tell me, I simply won't know and just go about my life not knowing so that helps them come back...Errm I would say trust but let me think about it. Looking at mentally now the people who give us the most money, the people who have used us for a long period and most of them built a relationship over time so I think its trust (Interview subject G).

In fact, “transparency helps” customers to “trust the system”. Thus, customers end up using the company website to plan. They can plan on the platform because it is trusted. Notifications to customers are also sent to remind them of upcoming activities or events. In this way, the burden of scheduling daily activities is minimised. This helps to build a lasting relationship and encourages customer repurchases.

On the contrary, Interview subject L points out that it is empathy rather than trust that makes customers repurchase, as illustrated by the extract below:

It's not really trust, trust is not part of it, it's more empathy is the biggest thing cos erm I think everybody wants to be understood so if you make customers feel like you understand them and understand what they need per time then they know that they connect with you, and they would come back whatever you're selling (Interview subject L).

Here, the important thing is to understand the customers and their needs. In fact, “if you make customers feel like you understand them and understand what they need”, then there is a likelihood of establishing a bond and lasting relationship. In that way, customers will “come back whatever you're selling”. This reinforces the notion of trust and transparency as illustrated by the customer experience.

4.7.4 Customer feedback

A word cloud was generated to see the patterns in the data collected about customer feedback. The most prominent and meaningful words included “customers”,

It was found that a higher concentration of the discussion was around phone calls, emails, and feedback, as illustrated by figure 4.58.

4.7.4.1 Phone calls

It was found that customer feedback is often provided via phone calls, with the intention of getting immediate feedback. This is illustrated by the extracts below:

In addition to that, we literally just call them, we call every client at least 2 at least 3 times in the course of the lesson. One at the start, one at the middle and one at the end of the lesson.... So, every month we call them three times because sometimes they may not type out what really they want to see but when we speak to them we get their real concerns and experience. What they are really concerned about o that way we are always in touch with our clients (Interview subject G).

It emerged that phone calls are an important communication channel used. This helps to make the clients feel valued and remembered. Their feedback on the service is obtained this way, and any corrective action is taken timeously. The intention is to obtain the real concerns and experiences of the respondents. This feedback is important to help improve the service provision.

The findings reveal that phone calls are a preferred channel of communication to obtain feedback because of the immediate response that is obtained, unlike other channels as surveys. This is illustrated by the extract below:

Most times we notice some begin the survey but do not complete while others choose to complete at a later date but never return. Because of this we use these phones calls and moments of contact with customers to retrieve as much useful information as we can about their preferences and how best to improve our services to them. They are usually happy to give out as much information in person or over the phone because I think it makes them feel like they are being understood directly and by someone representing our company. Whereas online, it probably feels like another survey where their opinion would only make up a statistic rather than count. We pay attention to these things over time and continue to improve (Interview subject M).

Telephonic interactions help managers to obtain as much information as possible from the clients. This helps in establishing a direct link between the company and its customers.

4.7.4.2 Emails

Emails are also used to provide customer feedback. This is illustrated by the extract below:

Actually, we use email campaigns, I don't know if you know intercom. We use intercom for either of those things, so we use it to reach out to customers after they

sign on or to follow up with them afterwards. We also have an upon feedback channel where people reach out to us. Personally, though every now and then I also email customers asking them for feedback on what they do, or how they are finding the website or the product itself. I have calls with customers on those issues (Interview subject L).

Email campaigns are used “to reach out to customers”. This is part of the customer “feedback channel”. These emails establish a direct link and targeted communication to known customers. Feedback obtained can be about their experience with the products or their experience on the company website. These emails establish a direct link, as illustrated by the extract below:

When we notice customers who have had issues repeatedly, we reach out to them directly to find out if their system is compatible enough for the version of the software we are using or what not. Some people need further help and we are willing to offer it so this is what makes us stand out to our customers – that direct means. That’s what I think the Nigerian customers who patronise us want, that direct link for communication (Interview subject O).

The idea of reaching out directly to customers is important. It is through direct contact that feedback is obtained. It is “that direct link” that helps management to review their systems and make improvements where necessary.

4.7.4.3 Reviews

Feedback is also obtained through review systems that have been set by the respective companies, as illustrated by the extracts below:

So we have an in-house review system where after each session, the client receives a notification to give feedback based on how the classes have been so there they meet the tutors and they also give us information on what was right, what could be improved on (Interview subject G).

For interview subject G and others like them, there is “an in-house review system” where “the client receives notification to give feedback”. They give “information on what was right, what could be improved on”. Thus, the feedback is designed to help the company improve on its weaknesses. It also helps the company to know what they are doing well on. Further, reviews are also on the online platform, as illustrated by the extract below:

Its difficult cos I have seen many companies, I went through the reviews on Google, the person that gave the review is the owner of the company [BOTH LAUGH] because I know him and I know he is the owner of the company but other people would not know but he has to put that there to encourage people to use. To at least give it a try. So, I think errr what else would they want to see, eerrnnnn, of course the goods themselves, the product. (Interview subject G)

Figure 4. 60: Emergent themes on aftersales

	A : Interview subject G	B : Interview subject L	C : Interview subject M	D : Interview subject O
1 : Calls	1	0	1	1
2 : Contact	1	0	1	0
3 : Dedicated service	1	1	1	2
4 : Digital devices	1	0	1	0
5 : Discounts	1	0	0	0
6 : Feedback	1	0	1	0
7 : Gifts	1	0	0	0
8 : Honesty	0	1	0	0
9 : Incentives	1	0	0	0
10 : Personalisation	0	0	1	0
11 : Post-purchase plans	0	1	0	0
12 : Refund	2	1	1	0
13 : repurchase	1	0	0	0
14 : Transparency	1	1	0	0

Figure 4. 61: Matrix coding query on aftersales

It was found that a higher concentration of the discussion was around phone calls, dedicated service, refund policy, feedback, and transparency, as illustrated by figure 4.61.

4.7.5.1 Contact

Contact with customers is often made through phone calls and emails. This is illustrated by the extracts in table 4.57.

Table 4. 57: Contact

Respondent	
Interview subject M	Over time, we have noticed that they prefer to be contacted through more direct mediums like phone calls. In the case of emails, they disregard any emails that appear generic therefore email has to be personal and meant specifically for them.
Interview subject G	So, once they book, the sales team hands over to the customer success and the first thing they do is to call the customer and try to understand the person’s needs on a deeper level which they find the customers really like.
Interview subject O	Because of this and because of how simply they want to be reached, we used phone calls, emails and texts.

It emerged that customers “prefer to be contacted through more direct mediums like phone calls”. It was also found that customers do not pay much attention to emails “that appear

generic”. Therefore, the emails have “*to be personal and meant specifically*” for the targeted client.

4.7.5.2 Dedicated service

Respondents share the view that a dedicated and personalised service is an essential part of the aftersales experience. It was also found that companies have established a dedicate team for aftersales service. The personal contact is important because the customers “want that human interface”. Others establish channels that are “dedicated to support” and have a “24 hours” service to “respond to customers and other issues they may have”. This is interpreted as a caring way of looking after the customers. This is illustrated in table 4.58.

Table 4. 58: Dedicated service

Respondent	
Interview subject G	we have a team dedicated to customer success; they are a segment of customer experience. They are, what their job in short is to make customers happy, that’s their mandate.
Interview subject M	we have delegated phone numbers and departments dedicated to resolving customer issues and follow up to make sure such issues do not occur again in the future.
Interview subject O	though the internet is meant to reduce manpower and human interface, in Nigeria customers still want that human interface, it is very relevant to them, so we have guys dedicated to taking or making calls regarding conflict resolution.
Interview subject L	Also, we have a channel dedicated to support and a person dedicated to support so this person is there 24 hours in a day to actually respond to customers and other issues they may have.

4.7.5.3 Refund policy

It was found that the respondents’ respective companies have a refund policy in place to help enhance the customer after sales experience.

Table 4. 59: Refund policy

Respondent	
Interview subject G	For those that are not happy we refund the money that they paid, less any lessons that have been taught depending on the reasons why they are not happy, if it’s claimed the tutors’ fault, they can be refunded the whole money.
Interview subject L	So, we have a refund, we do refund, so for customers who request a refund, we do refund them, we have a 100% refunds policy.
Interview subject M	I forgot to add that we do have customers who after paying deposits and confirming reservations might change their minds, we give them 50% refund on their deposits but if they come back, they need to pay a fresh deposit even if it’s for the same fabric or attire or what have you.

It was found that the companies have refund policies in place. So, those “customers who

request a refund”, they get refunded. However, this depends on the type of service a refund is requested for. In some cases, a customer may request a refund for a service already received. If it is the customers’ fault, then no refund is given. If it’s the company’s fault, then the client will “*be refunded the whole money*”. This helps customers to keep trusting the companies.

4.7.5.4 Feedback

It was found that customer feedback, whether positive or negative, is an essential component of the after sales experience.

The aftersales team also carry out surveys and market research hand in hand with my department and we use this information to prepare for issues our customers might have so we anticipate it and make sure they don’t face such problems (Interview subject M).

It was found that managers are proactive because they “use this information to prepare for issues” that might be raised by customers. In this sense, they “anticipate” problems and act proactively. Further, incentive schemes are used to entice repurchases as illustrated by the extract below:

If they, once you use us the first time you qualify for an incentive for the next two months. That helps them book more and if you refer a friend, you get additional discount that helps them (Interview subject G).

Because of other free offers made after the actual purchase, customers end up repurchasing and referring others. However, other respondents are of the view that aftersales must be distinguished from “*upselling*”, as illustrated by the extract below:

I mean aftersales should be aftersales, but people take it to mean marketing – like upselling... But not really upselling, upselling can be annoying so aftersales should be (long pause) aftersales specifically should be solely about what they bought and stuff like that (Interview subject L).

4.7.6 Plans

A word cloud was generated was generated to see the patterns in the data collected about respondents’ plans. The most prominent and meaningful words included “customers”, “goal”, “online”, “time”, “delivery”, “payment”, “platform”, “information”, and so forth. This pattern is illustrated by figure 4.62

Figure 4. 62: Word cloud on plans theme

The emergent meanings of these words included feedback system, payment system, tracking system, cost reduction, website, and so forth, as illustrated by the coding query, and presented in figure 4.63.

Figure 4. 63: Emergent themes on planning

	A : Interview subject G	B : Interview subject L	C : Interview subject M	D : Interview subject O
1 : Automation	1	0	0	0
2 : Cost reduction	0	0	1	0
3 : Customer repurchase	0	1	0	0
4 : Feedback system	2	0	0	0
5 : Payment system	0	0	0	1
6 : Privacy	0	0	0	1
7 : Reaching out	1	0	0	0
8 : Simplicity	0	1	0	0
9 : Tracking system	1	0	0	1
10 : Transparency system	1	0	0	0
11 : Website	0	1	0	0

It was found that a higher concentration of the discussion was around feedback system and tracking system, as illustrated by figure 4.64.

Figure 4. 64: Matrix coding query on planning

It also emerged that some of the respondents have plans to “*automate the marketing process*”, with the intention of competing more effectively, as illustrated by the extract below:

Secondly is to tighten up the marketing, automate the marketing process and that’s across board ... (Interview subject G).

This illustrates that managers understand the importance of technological innovations in business, and how these can be used to enhance marketing practices. Respondents also indicated that they plan to install a tracking system on their websites, as illustrated by the extract below:

...we use home story. It just tells us how long they stay on our site, where they click when on our sites, but you see the moment they go on another tab we are unable to see what they do (Interview subject O).

It was found that tracking systems can help to gather basic information such as the time spent by the customers on the website, the tabs that they visit. This information is vital for decision making. Similarly, interview subject L had this to say:

In terms of obviously the website, making people want to come back for online repurchase I mean this is always the goal right, even now. Even going a few years is too far, more like today cos we are actually trying to do that already. That’s what keeps the business going right...Errm and I would say is helping the customer just achieve more by doing less... And that’s the goal we are trying to meet so what can we do to make the customers get where they are trying to get without actually doing more basically and making that as useful as possible for them, that’s like the main thing we have in mind for them.

Enhancement of the website was of priority. The intention is to make “*people want to come back for online repurchases*”. Continuous improvement is the website is “*what keeps the business going*”. This illustrates the penetration of online shopping in Nigerian society, and

what companies are doing to attract more online traffic. Others plan to find ways of saving costs, as illustrated by the extract below:

In the near future we are interested in finding ways to save on delivery costs – maybe see how clients can come to collect or outsource our delivery but before such a decision is made, we need to know that we are not drifting away from our organisational image and culture (Interview subject M).

To conclude this section, the qualitative findings reveal how managers are engaging the technological innovations in their businesses. From giving customers feedback, managing aftersales activities, and engaging customers through the online platforms. Also, quantitative study, Reliability tests were conducted, and then followed by descriptive analysis. There were no missing values, thereby making the data usable. This was followed by correlational analysis, and finally regression analysis.

Given the rise in online sales across the globe, and the fall of the traditional high street businesses, it is important that managers in Nigeria must seriously think about using technological innovations more effectively to attract and retain consumers in Delta state and other parts of Nigeria too. This helps them to be more cost effective, reach a wider market and compete effectively. However, there is still a need to build trust with customers to ensure that they increase their use of online purchases. The next chapter discusses the findings in relation to the literature.

4.8 Summary of the chapter

This chapter has presented the results from secondary data, and then followed by primary data sets. Data analysis was done sequentially, with the secondary data being analysed first. This was followed by an analysis of the survey data, and finally the qualitative data. The secondary data set revealed a positive and strong correlation between internet users and the sales revenue of Jumia, one of the largest online retailers in Nigeria. The results suggest that as the number of internet users in Nigeria increase, there is also a corresponding increase in the total labour force, and internet subscribers. This suggests that economic factors have an impact on online repurchase intentions. Similarly, as the number of social network users worldwide increases, there is a corresponding increase in in the number of internet users in Nigeria, total labour force in Nigeria, and internet subscribers. As such, social networks, and social media contribute to online repurchase intentions. Further, as Nigeria's GDP per capita increases, there is a corresponding increase in the GDP, the number of internet users, and the number of internet

subscribers. This understanding helps to enrich our understanding of consumer online repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context.

The survey results revealed that within the Nigerian context, the key determinants that influence customer repurchase intentions, within the online environment, include satisfaction from previous experiences, available support, privacy concerns, levels of trust and perceived reliability. These results were reinforced by insights from the qualitative study. It was found that both traditional medias, including “word of mouth” and social media, are avenues that are used by the respondents’ organisations for marketing purposes. However, some customers are moved by what they see on social media whilst some are not moved at all. Whilst there is an increasing trend towards the use of online shopping and social media to engage with customers, managers must also continue to use traditional avenues because some customers do not easily adapt to innovations. Other respondents suggested that repurchases can be improved by personalisation of the customer experience within the online platforms. In this way, customers feel valued and wanted, and establish a sense of a “*personalised feel*”. It also gives the customers a sense of belonging, and thus mostly likely to result in customer repurchases and increased sales. Contextually based factors such as culture, cybersecurity concerns, demographics, and geographical location also emerged as important factors that influence online customer repurchase intentions. The next chapter discusses the results within the context of the literature.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the results of the study. Firstly, it analyses the demographics of the Nigerian consumer by drawing insights from both the primary data and the secondary data sets. The impact of different factors on purchase intentions are then discussed. Thereafter, a contextually based model is developed that can assist online vendors in Nigeria in developing strategies that can increase their customers' intentions to repurchase.

5.2 Demographics of the Nigerian consumer

Primary data for this study comprised of a sample of 100 respondents who were invited to take part in the survey. The findings reveal that 47% of respondents were between 26 and 35 years of age, 30% between 18 and 25 years, 19% between 35 and 50 years as well as a final 4% of respondents over 50 years of age. Secondary data sets reveal that Nigeria is the most populated country in Africa and 7th in the world with 196 million people (Gerland, Raftery, Ševčíková, Li, Gu, Spoorenberg, Alkema, Fosdick, Chunn, Lalic, and Bay, 2014). Over half of this population (51%) are children, teenagers, and young adults between the ages of 0 and 19 years of age. Further, 25% of the population is comprised of people between the ages of 20 and 35 years. This is followed by 17.6% aged between 35 – 60 years and the rest are made of senior citizens over 60 years.

The age distribution above not only reveals that 43% of the population of Nigeria are within the working age, it is also clear that most of the nation's population are children and young adults (Agwu and Carter, 2014). This information is important in understanding the standard of livelihood, purchasing power and the effect of influencers on customer repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context. These demographics presents an opportunity for the penetration of smartphone usage, internet, and technological devices. Of interest to this study is that the results revealed an association between demographic variables and online repurchase intentions. In a similar vein, economic factors influenced online repurchase intentions within the Delta state. Apart from Adeleke (2020), most of the literature is silent about the influence of demographic factors on online repurchase intentions (Abrar, Zaman, and Satti, 2017; Wijaya and Farida, 2018). These findings are interesting and helps us to reconceptualise the TAM model, and account for demographic variables

Further secondary data sets revealed that Nigeria has a very high dependency ratio (Udo, 2011). This provides an opportunity for online vendors to reach to young people. However, the young people are not their primary customers. In fact, young people in Nigeria rely on their parents, guardians, or members to make purchases and repurchases on their behalf. This is usually at the discretion of the sponsor and is sometimes affected by their social and economic as well as emotional reasons. Therefore, there is a need for online vendors to refocus their marketing strategies, and ensure they also adopt methods that appeal to the older citizens since they provide the funds for the purchases. Hence, steps must be taken to incorporate traditional selling methods alongside the technologically induced models (Urvashi *et al.*, 2017). Here, it is worth noting that economic and cultural factors are at play. The high dependency ration indicates that the young people have limited purchasing power because they depend on their parents financially, and a welfare system as that in western society is not available in the Delta state. Though the young people may use a lot of social media, they use it for social interactions because they do not have the capacity to transact independently. This is unlike young people in countries like the UK who have support systems such as unemployment benefits (Crisp and Powell, 2017; Gregg, 2015). Whilst the literature focuses on constructs outlined in the traditional TAM model (Baby and Kannammal, 2020; Bae and Han, 2020), the reality in the Delta state brings something that departs from what has always been reported in the literature about online repurchase intentions. Rather, the reality in the Delta state awakes us to the role played by parents in the repurchase intentions of young people. In other words, the young people will need parental approval for their transactions. Yet, the literature has always assumed that the young people make their independent online shopping decisions (Eriksson, Rosenbröijer, and Fagerstrøm, 2017; Lupton, 2020).

It was found that 78% of respondents own and use a smartphone daily while 22% do not own smartphone or similar devices. Another interesting finding was that 41% of the respondents spend approximately between 3 and 5 hours daily online. Further, 29% of the respondents spend between 1 and 2 hours using the online platform. Another 29% spend over 5 hours, and only 1% spend less than an hour using the online platform daily. This is an indication of time spent on mobile devices, smartphones, tablets, mobile applications, messaging, shopping, and other online interactional activity. The frequency of online purchases was reported as 4% of

once a day, 36% shop weekly, 16% purchase items multiple times every week and 44% once monthly.

Though respondents spend a lot of time online, there is a considerably low shopping frequency. The increase in online activity can be explained by increased internet penetration (Udo, 2011). However, there is a need to convert online activity into purchases. It was also found that 41% of respondents who spend between 3 and 5 hours online daily and the 29% who spend over 5 hours are in the 18 – 25 age range, and the 26 – 35 age range, respectively. This is important to know for market targeting purposes, as well as encouraging customer repurchases.

The secondary data reveal that there are 23.3 million smartphone users in Nigeria, and yet, the population is 198 million people. It was also found that 51% of the population live in urban areas. It was also observed that some rural communities do not have access to electricity nor the internet. Regardless, the literature suggests that by the year 2015, there will be a total of 143 million smartphone users in Nigeria (Statista, 2016). This presents an opportunity for increased online business activity.

The literature assumes that the more time spent online, the higher the likelihood of online shopping activity (Beckers, Cárdenas, and Verhetsel, 2018; Haque and Mazumder, 2020; Barska and Wojciechowska-Solis, 2020). However, the Nigerian context is different. Though participants from the Delta state spend a lot of time online, the shopping frequency is very low. This suggests that they are for the most part involved in social interactions rather than shopping.

5.3 Factors affecting customer repurchase intentions

This section discusses results of the factors affecting customer repurchase intention as depicted in the literature. These include social media, perceived value, brand reputation, returns policy, trust, pay on delivery practice, privacy, systems availability, and functionality, and finally, fulfilment, ease of use and enjoyment.

5.3.1 Impact of Social media on repurchase intentions

Previous studies suggest that social media has an impact on customer repurchase intention (Pauwels and Neslin, 2015; Mergel, 2013). The literature also suggests that social media creates a universal platform for the analysis, comparison, evaluation, and rating of customer experiences (Aden et al., 2006; Huang and Benyoucef, 2013). Other scholars suggest that using the social media platforms, customers can serve as unpaid marketers for brands that provide satisfaction and at the same time as critics of brands that fail to provide satisfaction (Meyer, 2017). More importantly, social media platforms and the internet provide multiple choices for

customers generating a sense of empowerment, building trust, brand reputation and repurchase intentions (Smith, 2016; Meyer, 2017).

It was found that 72% (occasionally) and 18% (very often) react towards adverts on social media applications. It also emerged that from this group, some end up making a purchase. Only 10% of respondents reported to “*never*” buy goods and services because of online prompts. Further, 36% agreed, and 47% strongly agreed with the statement that “*social media platforms and tools influence how respondents repurchase goods and services online*”. However, 10% neither disagree nor agree, whilst only 5% disagree. Only 2% strongly disagreed. It was found that those who were indifferent were guided by product specifications and previous experience because they knew exactly what they wanted. However, bad experiences resulted in consumer distrust. As such, some consumers gained assurances from known and reputable brands. There are also those respondents who indicated that they would never purchase items through social media ads. Therefore, there is a need to build trust and encourage these customers to engage with technological innovations in the business environment. Consistent with this, the results from qualitative data sets revealed that there is an increasing number of

It was also found that those who occasionally or very often buy goods through social media ads do so because of necessity. This is because they found the item to be essential, advert well timed, product at the right perceived price, and there being limited options. This is interpreted to mean that such consumers are ‘last minute’ buyers. It can be said that customer repurchase intention can be properly understood when businesses recognise the essential behaviour of Nigerian consumers. Given that consumers react positively to online adverts, an opportunity arises for vendors to use the online platforms, encourage customer repurchases, and gain consumer loyalty.

The literature suggests that consumers fail to purchase goods and services on online platforms because of distrust, bias, and subjective views on social media (Jiang and Wang, 2006; Shashank and Devaraj, 2018). Consistent with the literature, it was found that Nigerian online shoppers distrust some online adverts. Because of this, customers fail to buy or engage in any repurchases. Some interpret pop up adverts as an invasion of privacy. In fact, the literature suggests that some consumers prefer repurchasing from a source because of their reliability, set routines, satisfaction, and ease in continuity (Hess, 2008).

When presented with an evaluative statement stating that *‘ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product’*, only 1% of respondents strongly disagreed, and 3% disagreed. Further, 16% of the respondents were indifferent, whilst 48% agreed and 32% strongly agreed. It emerged that those indifferent relied on their previous experiences. In this sense, repurchase is guaranteed if product specifications match customer expectations, and achieved good satisfaction levels. The effect of other influencers in this case are negligible depending on the entire purchase process. For example, some indicated that they would repurchase an essential item, one which they use daily. This was contrary to the negative reviews and ratings. It emerged that most of the Nigerian customers ignore ratings and reviews and rely on their individual experiences for any repurchases.

Previous studies suggest that customer repurchase intention directly affects sales (Lee et al., 2009). Others suggest that there is a direct link between customer repurchase intention and competitiveness of the business environment (Kim et al, 2012). However, given the competitiveness of the Nigerian business environment, it is important for online vendors to understand the Nigerian consumers. This will enable them to understand the dynamics of gaining consumer trust, loyalty, and gain market share.

When presented with an evaluative statement stating that *“fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms”*, 70% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed, 19% were indifferent, and only 11% disagreed and strongly disagreed. Whilst ratings and reviews on social media platforms are very important, some Nigerian consumers pay less attention to them. Yet, negative reviews can also be detrimental to a business.

Therefore, there is a need for a coordinated approach focused on exceeding customer expectations, delivering utmost satisfaction whilst simultaneously keeping tabs on customer reviews, ratings, and customer feedback. In this context, Nigerian businesses must adopt an organizational culture that pays attention to retrieving customer feedback and reviews. This enables both online and traditional businesses to be more informed about their customers, and thus develop strategies to meet customer needs more efficiently and effectively.

Scholars suggest that the use of social media and the internet helps to promote transparency (Bertot, Jaeger, and Grimes, 2010; Gunawong, 2015). Contrary to the literature, when presented with the statement that *“social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting”*, 10% of respondents disagreed. It

was found that these respondents believe information on social media is either subjective, manipulated for personal interest and at best biased. As a result of some unethical business practices in Nigeria, this category of respondents suspected that online vendors manipulate customer reviews and ratings.

On the other hand, 61% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed, while 26% were indifferent. The results reveal that availability of information and transparency provides information to consumers, highlights the importance of customer feedback, and more importantly, empowers customers. This helps to reduce customer distrust and encourage repurchase intention.

Whilst social media has a positive impact on online repurchase intentions, as reported in the literature (Bigne, Andreu, Hernandez, and Ruiz, 2018; Isah and Ogundele, 2020), the situation in the Delta state is different. There is a distrust on online transactions because of cyber security concerns. Whilst the respondents agreed that the ratings and reviews of social media were important, even with positive ratings reviews and ratings, there is a hesitancy to undertake transactions on the online environment. This is unlike in countries like the UK and USA where online transactions have become an inseparable part of daily life (Appel, Grewal, Hadi, and Stephen, 2020). These are interesting findings because contrary to the view that social media has an impact on customer repurchase intention (Carlson, Rahman, Taylor, and Voola, 2019), in the Delta state, the main focus is on social interactions rather than online transactions.

5.3.2 Perceived value

Previous studies suggest that perceived value is an influencer (Moliner *et al.*, 2007). According to Davis (1989), perceived value is measurable when purchase is complete and encountered. This means that the customer only has an idea of this value when they have the final product or service. In fact, perceived value is measured across customer's expectations (Hume, 2008). However, expectations are built around a customer's depth of knowledge on product specifications or service as well as their perception on characteristics of the offering (prices and deals). The results reveal that consumers also measure perceived value across the buying process. When presented with an evaluative statement stating that, "*when an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectation and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on*", 90% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed, only 1% disagreed, and 9% were indifferent. This suggests that perceived value is an influential factor on CRI. Results also reveal that perceived value is high when expectation matches actual product, ease of use of

service, free and easy delivery. The efficiency in the delivery of each of these services during the purchase process can either increase or decrease the level of perceived value a consumer receives from making a purchase. This has a very direct effect on customer repurchase intentions. These findings are consistent with the literature.

Participants reported that they become unhappy when they must pay additional costs for delivery. However, it was also found that most consumers willingly pay additional charges for deliveries. This reduces the extent of perceived value derived. Hitherto, the few respondents who disagree or remain neutral do so for several reasons. Firstly, their repurchase intention changes due to the need to explore other options. This also changes the moment a competitor brand offers free delivery or other value-added services. Consequently, unavailable stock or system failures can account for changes in customer repurchase intention despite meeting perceived value in previous transactions. For instance, a returning customer would reach out to competitor brands if they cannot find what they planned to repurchase. And if such a brand can meet their needs, repurchase is now based on satisfaction and perceived value derived from the brand (Rousseau et al., 1998; Chan, To, and Chu, 2015). For instance, online retailers in Nigeria constantly pay attention to inventory management and logistics to ensure that they are well positioned to service their customers.

On the contrary, 43% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that '*when purchased goods and services do not meet perceived expectations, consumers are likely to repurchase with the same brand*'. Similarly, 48% disagreed and strongly disagreed, while only 9% were indifferent. The category of respondents who disagreed represent customers and consumers who operate simply on shifting patronage when expectations are not met. The absence of perceived value signifies no repurchase unless measures and steps are taken to identify and remedy aspects of the transaction that they are not happy with. Online vendors with good after sales follow up can identify areas within that needs improvement and how to meet expectations of unsatisfied customers.

However, it was important to find out why some customers may agree with the evaluative statement already outlined. It was important to understand why they repurchase despite poor experiences and unmatched expectations. Most recurring reasons were product unavailability or limited options, available options seemingly untrustworthy, geographical location and proximity. For instance, several interview subjects complained about services they receive from internet providers but have remained with such providers regardless. This is because this

may be the only option in the geographic area for the provision of the respective product or service. Thus, a lack of competition in the area is of concern, and consumers have no other choice. Contrary to the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), where there is no choice, consumer repurchases occur even if the service or product is of poor quality.

At this point it is evident that customer repurchase intentions is influenced by the perceived value a customer derives from purchasing a product or service. This confirms the applicability of hypothesis H1. However, findings suggest that in the absence of perceived value, customer repurchase can still recur depending on social, economic, and personal circumstances discussed above.

A lack of competition in some areas such as manufacturing creates an environment where repurchase intentions occurs despite low levels of perceived value. The literature suggests that consumers serve as self-educators developing sound knowledge of the product they want and are willing to pay additional costs or expend additional efforts before receiving the products (Katole, 2011). Therefore, there is a need to encourage competition and widen consumer choices.

Results also revealed a relationship between the perceived value a customer feels from purchasing a product and fulfilment derived from making use of a vendor's online platform or means of service delivery. Fulfilment derived from using a service delivery channel adds to the overall perceived value (Riska *et al.*, 2016). However, perceived value levels can be remedied without fulfilment from making use of an online service delivery channel. It was found that 86% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that, '*when I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more*'. Only 14% of the respondents were indifferent.

Results also revealed that 14% of the customer base remain sceptical even after feeling fulfilled after making use of a service. The final appearance and value perceived after receipt of a product or service determines repurchase intention ultimately. Hitherto, businesses and online vendors whilst paying attention on innovativeness of service delivery mediums should endeavour to match expectations of customers. They must desist from over selling products and making unrealistic claims and promises.

Furthermore, it is important for online vendors to incorporate and diligently enforce warranty and insurance policies. Results reveal this to be an integral aspect. It was found that most consumers must be made to feel safe and achieve more perceived value. In other words,

consumers would feel a higher degree of perceived value knowing the product is insured, trusted warranty exists, and returns policy are upheld by vendors. Having extra packages like this not only insulate brands from issues that inhibit customer repurchase intentions, but also makes consumers confident and relaxed when purchasing goods and services either online, or over the counter (Saunders and Thornhill, 2003).

5.3.3 Brand reputation

Consistent with the literature surrounding the influence of brand reputation on repurchase intentions of online shoppers (Yannopoulou, Koronis and Elliott, 2011), it was found businesses with good corporate reputation create competitive advantage because they are able to influence consumer behaviours and attitude (Murray, 1991). Results reveal that Nigerian customers rely on brand reputation over lower costs and promotional offers. Because of a lack of trust, there is reliance on brand image and reputation. It was found that product characteristics, product performance, pricing range, value and lifespan of product are also important factors. Because of differences in purchasing power and standards of living, the purchase of a product despite a customer's perception of the brand is dependent on socio-economic conditions of the buyer at the given time. Though the customers may rely on brand reputation, there is limited activity in terms of online repurchase intentions. Rather, repurchases take place in the offline environment rather than online. This is because of cyber security concerns within the Nigerian online shopping environment (Bello and Griffiths, 2021).

Presented with the statement that, "*I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputations despite apparent trust issues in the Nigerian online shopping space*", 79% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed. Only 3% of respondents disagreed, whilst 18% were indifferent. During interviews, participants were asked to make selections between a set of popular brands under different classes of products and services. In the first exercise, their standards of living and total expenditure revenues were not considered. Findings from this first exercise reveal a tendency towards brands with good corporate reputation, image, and presence. These were mainly big corporations and businesses with the best quality in products and services, with a nationwide distribution network. These had higher costs and prices than smaller brands.

In the second exercise, participants were asked to consider their current lifestyle and socio-economic situation in providing their answers. Findings from second exercise show that Nigerian consumers are more likely to purchase and repurchase with big and reputable brands

rather than newer and smaller firms, but, this does not apply. Customers must rely on brands that offer lower costs when making recurring expenditure. However, it was found that Nigerian consumers are willing to go beyond their means and purchase from brands with higher reputation when purchasing highly sensitive products.

The effect of price range and pricing strategy of Nigerian businesses is lower than that of brand reputation on customer repurchase intentions. Lower costs and promotional activities are effective only due to lower purchasing power of many Nigerian consumers. On the contrary, with a growing purchasing power and increasing standards of living, customers have revealed their readiness to shift patronage and purchase from more reputable brands. Findings reveal that some Nigerian consumers perceive lower costs and promotions to mean lower quality in products and services. For instance, 55% of the respondents strongly agreed and 38% agreed that *“when spending huge amounts online, I purchase from trusted brands rather than cheaper options or discounted vendors”*. Participants suggest that consumers are more willing to stick to brands they know. They are reluctant to take risks and try new brands despite lower prices or promotional deals (Rousseau *et al.*, 1998; Matzler, Grabner-Kräuter and Bidmon, 2008).

This is supported by 56% and 33% of respondents who strongly agreed and agreed respectively, with the statement that, *“I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors”*. This suggests that brand reputation has a higher influence on customer repurchase intention than pricing and promotional activities. Therefore, there is a need to develop business models that increase customer patronage. In Nigeria, a company’s brand reputation is developed through several factors which include product characteristics, service quality, equity and value, system availability and functionality, presence, and available support. These factors collectively build up the value perceptions of the customers. Brand reputation which is developed over time is directly linked to trust because customers’ perception of a brand is what determines the extents of vulnerability, that consumers are willing to accept based on the positive expectations they have from purchasing a product or service (Matzler, Grabner-Kräuter and Bidmon, 2008).

5.3.4 Returns policy

The internet and technological advancements have helped to improve shopping experiences (Katole, 2011). It was found that 59% of respondents agreed and 38% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement that, *“I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy”*. The remaining 3% were indifferent. Results revealed that

those indifferent represent consumers who hardly return items and only purchase when extremely sure. They tend to inspect, evaluate, and compare products before purchase. Customers also accept that when products are purchased online mistakes and errors occur. Further, the literature suggests that information from vendors can be misinterpreted and sometimes wrong items are selected, and products returned (Yiu *et al.*, 2007).

Within the Nigerian online shopping environment, these errors are mostly attributed to quality of websites and service delivery mediums, ease of use and navigation, unclear description of products and services by online vendors. For example, a customer searching for a landline stumbles upon a communications provider and on the website, photos underlying the product description show a physical landline telephone. The customer makes payment and anticipates the delivery of the product. On delivery, the customer finds out he/she needs to buy a landline telephone and that the vendor's ultimate offering is the connectivity. Information provided is inaccurate.

Firstly, due to misleading descriptions and presentation of service offering or misinterpretation of information, expectations can never be met, and thereby, the customer gains no perceived value. Hence, the growth of certain classes of online businesses in Nigeria depend on changes in perceptions as consumers avoid online purchases. However, consumers confirm that when shopping online with companies whose brands they perceive to be stronger and more reputable, issues described earlier rarely occur. Therefore, online repurchase is largely influenced by a firm's reputation (Hess, 2008; Lee et al, 2011). On the contrary, it was found online repurchases are influenced by cyber security issues, rather than just a firm's reputation. This is an interesting finding because it amplifies the importance of internet security issues within the Nigerian online shopping environment. The personal encounters with cyber security issues discourage consumers to transact online, but just to view the product or service, and then go to transact in the offline environment. This goes back to the issue of trust.

5.3.5 Trust

Trust is not only an influencer of customer repurchase intention but a catalyst that controls levels of customer repurchase intentions (Hong and Cho, 2011). The literature suggests that trust is perceived as a category of certain beliefs pertaining mainly to the competence and integrity of another party (Suh and Han, 2003). In this case, competence is measured by performance, quality of service delivery and all other factors that make up a firm's brand and reputation. Integrity entails the extent to which vendors meet expectations, match description

and offers with actual products and services. Therefore, when competence and integrity are accounted for, trust is built and nurtured over time (Xu *et al.*, 2011).

It was found that 47% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed with the statement that, “*I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses*”, while 36% disagreed and strongly disagreed, and 17% were indifferent. Most respondents find it hard trusting Nigerian online businesses. These rely on previous experience, perceived value, and brand reputation to influence their purchase and ultimately repurchase of a product or service. Though it is easy to trust the Nigerian online businesses, transacting online is still difficult. This may mean that Nigerian customers prefer to transact offline rather than online. This may also be a cultural issue because of the need for the physical presence of both buyer and seller to transact.

Findings revealed that factors include but are not limited to previous bad experience, unmatched expectation and dissatisfaction, unfulfilled warranty and after sales policies as well as poor performance of product or poor-quality service. A peculiar scenario is one where consumers purchase products at exorbitant prices only to find the same product being offered by another vendor at a very low price. The customer feels completely robbed and vulnerable leading to distrust. In the offline environment, there are opportunities to physically see the product and negotiate (Yusuf and Madichie, 2012; Thiel, 2019). Embedded within the Nigerian culture is negotiation of prices, and this cannot be done through online shopping.

These findings are consistent with the view that trust is directly related to perceptions on brand reputation and therefore has a major influence on customer repurchase intention (McKnight and Choudhury, 2002). However, trust becomes irrelevant when it comes to necessities. For instance, 62% of the respondents strongly agreed that, “*I have purchased items from online vendors even when I did not trust them*”. Results revealed that necessity and needs as well as limited options are the most concrete reasons behind patronage where trust is non-existent. Further, 29% strongly disagreed. This suggests that they are unwilling to let go of their trust on a vendor meeting their expectations and perceived values and by so doing would never purchase or repurchase from brands they distrust. A small portion (9%) of respondents were indifferent. These respondents make up customers who rely on logic, previous satisfaction and their knowledge of product and offering to decide on where they purchase items from. In this case, brand reputation, general perception, perceived value, and fulfilment have a higher influence on repurchase intentions than trust.

5.3.6 *Pay on delivery practice*

An emergent practice is that of ‘*Pay on delivery*’. This was prominent around 2007 to 2011. Customers made payment for goods and services they purchased online only on or after delivery is complete (Ayogu, 2017). Upon the arrival of goods, the customer can inspect the goods against the vendors description provided online. In some cases, customers make deposit payments which could be 10% of the cost price. This fee is used to confirm how genuine and serious a client is, and when delivery attempts are tried over an agreed number of times without completion of the transaction, the client loses the deposit.

These terms are usually described on the vendor’s website. The study sought to understand whether the ‘pay on delivery’ approach would instigate repurchase by balancing trust and risks between buyers and vendors. When presented with an evaluative statement stating that, “*I would repurchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a pay on delivery basis*”, 83% of the respondents strongly agreed, 4% disagreed, and 13% were indifferent. Qualitative insights reveal that online shoppers feel less vulnerable under the ‘pay on delivery practice’. This is because of previous experiences where actual products delivered were inconsistent with online descriptions. This is made worse by vendors that do not have any returns policies. Whilst purchases can be done online, the payment must be done offline. This is interesting because the literature always assumes that when shopping online, the payment is done before the goods are delivered (Liao and Yang, 2020). Yet, in the Delta state, the preference is to pay when the goods are delivered, and physically inspected.

It was also found that lengthy procedures and complex returns policies frustrate customers and discourage repurchase intentions. On the other hand, online vendors claim that they experience a lot of issues around extortion and robbery of delivery personnel in certain areas and this discourages them to implement the ‘*pay on delivery*’ mechanism. The literature suggests that ‘pay on delivery’ approach involves a lot of logistical issues and increases overall overheads (Ayogu, 2017). Those customers indifferent feel consider the ‘pay on delivery’ practice, as time wasting and, in some cases, unsafe (Ayogu, 2017). They prefer making payment online where a transaction is faster and safer, more protected and they do not need to dispense efforts going to the bank to withdraw monies for payment.

5.3.7 *Privacy*

The literature reveals the risks and concerns of privacy on online platforms (Wang et al, 2003). In this regard, respondents were presented with an evaluative statement stating that, “*I will repurchase goods from online vendors who store my private details and information*”, and 56%

strongly agreed, 18% strongly disagreed, and 26% were indifferent. Further investigation reveals that Nigerian consumers are mainly indifferent to vendors storing their information. They are interested to know why a vendor stores their personal information.

As a matter of fact, they consider the storage of this information as convenient during repurchase and useful towards after sales follow up. This encourages loyalty to a brand because consumers are known by name, and easily identifiable. It makes them feel important. Contrary to the perception that storing personal information is detrimental, and that consumers are more careful and reluctant to have their personal information accessible to public (Xu *et al.*, 2011), insights from the study suggest otherwise. This is illustrated by 56% that strongly agreed with the evaluative statement. Consumers are also very happy to receive promotional and new offerings and for this to happen, online vendors need to possess certain personal information. However, this is not suggesting that Nigerian consumers are unaware of the lack of privacy by some online vendors.

The results reveal that customers appreciate phone calls and other direct means of communication from vendors. This takes place only if customer information is held by the vendors. In the UK, the GDPR have policies ensuring that businesses and online vendors re-request permission to retain private information of their customers every year. This is not the case in Nigeria. Direct means of communication offer Nigerian businesses with key insights into their consumers' behaviour and interests helping them account for and provide tailored services.

Insights from in-depth interviews reveal that when vendors meet customer preferences and use feedbacks, a feeling of empathy is created. This helps to build trust, and privacy issues become of less concern. Their repurchase intentions at this point is influenced by how vendors utilize customer information. This is also illustrated by 83% of the respondents who strongly agreed that, "*politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour*". Only 4% disagreed, and 14% indifferent.

The literature suggests that consumers are inclined to protect their privacy (Liao, Liu, and Chen, 2011). However, when asked about their willingness to partake in surveys when requested by online vendors and businesses, 45% of the respondents indicated that they would immediately take part in the survey, while 39% indicated that they would postpone the survey till a later date and their final participation is difficult to determine. Further, 14% indicated that

they were totally uninterested in participating in surveys, whilst 2% indicated that participation depends on either the level of satisfaction they gain or until goods are used.

Insights from interviews with managers and representatives of online vendors reveal that very few employ tools and online trackers on their websites. It was learnt that these tracking tools are sophisticated and there is a lack of capacity to evaluate and utilize the information generated. Yet, online cookies and trackers are a prominent practice within online businesses in developed countries (Xu *et al.*, 2011). In fact, cookies generate rich data that influences major business decisions around customer satisfaction and help to increase sales and customer repurchase intention (Xu *et al.*, 2011). Yet, most Nigerian online vendors do not employ this tactic. This can be because of differences in the national cultures, and individual cultures within Nigeria. For instance, if consumers in the Delta state get to know that tracking devices are used, then they may stop visiting those websites. This is because of an embedded fear of the unknown within the Nigerian culture (Lambert, Passmore, and Joshanloo, 2019; Mello, Oladipo, Paoloni, and Worrell2019).

Within the Nigerian context, it was found that privacy of information is dependent upon social status. For example, affluent customers purchase niche, exclusive products, and services, and expect that their privacy is treated with utmost confidentiality. Their repurchase intention is influenced by this. This is consistent with the literature in that privacy concerns reflect strongly around a customer's considerations for loss of privacy (Hoffman, 1994). However, identity theft and similar concerns around online shopping is on the low in Nigeria unlike in developed countries (Udo, 2011). Therefore, Nigerian customers are less worried about identity theft. Yet, this is not the case with consumers in western society.

5.3.8 System availability and functionality

The literature suggests that web designers are concerned with sophistication, functionality bandwidths as well higher data hosting and processing capacity (Turban and Gehrke, 2000). On the contrary, consumers find ease of use, navigation, online support, and communication essential to engage in online shopping activities (Turban and Gehrke, 2000). Consistent with this, it was found that Nigerian consumers are more concerned about their overall satisfaction, and the quality of goods and services they purchase. When presented with an evaluative statement stating that, "*I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website*", 91% of the respondents strongly agreed, only 1% disagreed, and 8% were indifferent. The literature suggests that first time purchases are more

likely influenced by consumer perceptions on quality and expectations (Moliner *et al.*, 2007). Referrals and opinions of fellow customers are also a major factor (Gefen, 2000). Results reveal that subsequent purchases depend on such expectations and perceptions of value and quality. It was found that customer fulfilment rather than system availability and functionality were major factors. System availability on the other hand plays a different role on its influence within the Nigerian online environment.

It was also found that websites and online applications are often unavailable because of infrastructural and network issues. This is unlike in western society where the network infrastructure is advanced, and there are high internet penetration rates (Pandita, 2017; Umezuruike, Oludele, Kuyoro, and Izang, 2015). For example, a customer who receives fulfilment and finds a system functional enough to conduct his/her online transaction is likely to repurchase. However, if on the date of repurchase, such a system is unavailable, and the customer must find an alternative option whose system is available. Here, such a customer is left with no option but to patronize another vendor. Customer repurchase in this case has been positively influenced by system functionality, and but negatively influenced by system availability. This in turn has a detrimental effect on sales and brand reputation. Therefore, system availability and functionality can be a source of competitive advantage (Delone and McLean, 2004).

The functionality of websites and online shopping outlets play a more prominent role in consumer selection between a set of online vendors. Once a decision is made, customer repurchase intention is influenced by product characteristics and service delivery rather than system availability and functionality. Competition amongst prominent online businesses such as Jumia and Konga is noticed by the pace at which websites and other online mediums are upgraded and innovated. Thus, system quality and performance related attributes distinguish online vendors. Therefore, the importance of system availability and functionality cannot be overlooked (Udo, 2011).

Online vendors continuously search for ways to provide more efficient services to their customers by maintaining flexible delivery options (Chao-Min et al, 2009). Same day delivery, self-scheduled pickups as well as drop boxes are now in practice within the Nigerian online business environment. It was found that 96% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that, “*I will repurchase from brands with excellent delivery systems*”. With rising concerns for speed and flexibility in delivery methods, companies like Gokada now handle fast

and flexible delivery services on behalf of online vendors. This helps to make the process more efficient and reliable. In the Delta state, this means ordering online, and payment being made when goods are delivered.

The findings suggest that despite a low prevalence of e-commerce in the country, online vendors must pay attention to the quality and efficiency of their websites. They do this expecting that the interaction from a customer's first visit would positively influence product trial and purchase intentions. Customers do not rely on system functionality and availability alone for repurchase intentions. However, the extent to which local online vendors in Nigeria mirror their websites and platforms in line with big global brands is quite limited because of high levels of sophistication required. There is a need to produce online platforms that are more user friendly. It was found that repurchase intentions are influenced by the interaction between consumers.

It was also found that consumers consider online support such as real time chat boxes and 24-hour customer care lines as important. These are important to avoid confusion and deal with customer queries when the system fails. In fact, approaches that deliver personalised services are preferred. This is illustrated by 92% of the respondents who strongly agreed with the statement that, "*I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries*". Respondents confirm that online support encourages repurchase behaviour.

The literature suggests that online support depends on overall performance of the vendor's representative (Chen *et al.*, 2012). Thus, poor service would result in the termination of transactions, and ultimately affecting repurchase intentions. Hitherto, system availability and functionality can instigate repurchase intentions. However, the extent to which this occurs is dependent on the frequency of other influencers on customer repurchase intentions.

5.3.9 Fulfilment, Ease of use and enjoyment derived from using online platforms

Consistent with the literature, it was found that fulfilment is experienced when online vendors deliver the desired product or service exactly as promised without breaking the psychological contract that took place now of purchase (Riska *et al.*, 2016). It was also found that consumers experience fulfilment more whilst using an online website or platform than purchasing such goods or services in person. The literature suggests that the levels of trust may fluctuate because of fluctuating levels of fulfilment (Molla and Licker, 2001). For fulfilment to be complete, Nigerian consumers not only expect enjoyment and user-friendly platforms, but the actual product or service offering must be consistent with the vendor's promise and

descriptions. Continuously reducing levels of fulfilment directly leads to low levels of trust which negatively influences repurchase intentions (Malhorta *et al.*, 2004; Yang, 2012). Contrary to the literature, 52% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that, “*I would repurchase from an online vendor that provides quality shopping experience despite poor quality goods and services*”. Further, 7% were indifferent whilst 41% agreed. The 52% of respondents who repurchase despite poor quality goods do so because of limited or no other options. Another reason for this is the ease and enjoyment derived from using the online platform. This helps to manage consumer expectations.

Continuous failure by an online business to deliver products meeting customers’ expectations ultimately results in a complete lack of trust and poor reputation (Suh and Han, 2003). This forces customers to shift patronage and any intentions to repurchase. Results reveal that effective communication with their clientele is important to investigate customer repurchase intention. For instance, a respondent from a private tutor provision firm, pointed out that they maintain constant and direct communication with customers through phone calls, text messages, and interactions with customers on other mobile applications. It was found that this practice engaged customers with the service, and enhanced transparency in service delivery.

While most Nigerian online businesses make after sales follow ups, a few engage their customers more frequently through diverse mediums of communication. Results suggest that after sales follow up, referrals, and up to date communication supports customer repurchase. Some of this communication is done through social media interactions. It was found that 33% of the respondents were indifferent about the influence of after sales follow up on their repurchase intentions. This represents consumers who are reluctant to participate in surveys and those who participate when vendors have failed to meet their expectations. This is not surprising because of low levels of participation in online surveys. Therefore, there is a need to employ more personalised approaches.

5.3 Applicability of general influencers

The results reveal that influencers have an impact on customer repurchase intentions. However, there were also some influencers that were relevant to the Nigerian context. For instance, respondents were asked to rate all general influencers on a scale of 1 – 8 where 1 represents least applicable and 8 most applicable influencer of their repurchase intentions. It was found that 80% of the respondents under normal circumstances would be more influenced by brand reputation, quality of service, trust, and privacy. Some respondents repurchase intentions are

more influenced by reduced perceived value and satisfaction, ease of use as well as fulfilment and other socio-economic factors. Socio-economic factors include need/necessity, promotional offers, and lowest prices. These factors may include those new determinant factors present in Nigeria that influence customer repurchase intentions. There is a silence in the literature about these socio-economic factors (Adebayo and Beton Kalmaz, 2020).

Privacy concerns ranked highest with 53%, followed by ease of use and trust with 43% and 40% respectively. Privacy concerns and issues associated with loss of information, identity theft and online financial fraud within online businesses is low. This indicates that Nigerian customers have an indifferent perception to trust and privacy. This is not to imply that Nigerian customers have no regards for their private information being safe when they purchase goods online.

Another contradictory revelation is the overall ranking of brand reputation and perceived value which score 25% and 37% respectively. Nigerian customers appeared to be more influenced by brand reputation and perceived value. Prior findings show their tendency to bigger and more reliable businesses. The issue of trust is addressed when customers purchased products from brands, they thought were reliable. As a result, Nigerian businesses invest a lot of time and resources on creating a good public image to help manage consumer distrust. Therefore, the high scores on trust obtained are interpreted as a reflection of Nigerian customers' reliance on trusted brands.

It emerged that repurchase intention is influenced by trust nurtured through good brand reputation. It was found that customers are reluctant to try new brands. This is interpreted as continued use of trusted brands (McKnight and Choudhury, 2002). However, some respondents reported that they purchase goods from online vendors despite not trusting them. This supports the claim that: i) Nigerian customers are willing to set trust because of necessity needs, ii) Online vendors are right in their assumption that when Nigerian customers receive personalised experience, empathy derived from feeling understood occupies the place of trust, and iii) trust within the context of this research is an out-birth from a combination of a series of matched perceived expectations and the reputation vis a vis efficiency of overall product and service performance of the brand repurchased (Pavlou and Fygenson, 2006).

Global businesses invest huge amounts of money on websites and online platforms with sophisticated features usually focusing on engagement, interaction, ease of use and accessibility (Turban and Gehrke, 2000). The same is the case in Nigeria where there has been

a recent wave in the increase in online businesses and activities in general. However, results reveal that while online vendors understand the importance of having sound websites and online platforms, they also design their platforms with customers' interests at heart. Vendors claim that most of their customers require human interface with less automation on their websites, and service delivery platforms. For this reason, they limit the amount of resources they spend on sophisticated websites and online platforms.

The findings reveal that quality of online platforms had a rating of 33%. This suggests that overall influence on customer repurchase intention is not as applicable in Nigeria. Customers are less interested in the quality of websites; they are more interested in how easy a website would help them conduct their shopping activity. Online vendors prefer telephone lines available for online shopping. This is often used to interact with customers when they face problems on the website. Pertaining to the fulfilment Nigerian customers derive from using a business' website or other online platforms, evidence obtained from this research suggest very little to almost no significance of fulfilment to customer repurchase intentions in Nigeria.

The average most applicable overall influence score of 19% for enjoyment, and 27% on fulfilment was obtained. This suggests that these factors single-handedly do not completely influence customer repurchase intentions. High levels of fulfilment derived from using an online platform can increase levels of perceived value. This can result in negative repurchase intentions if not matched by online vendors. When perceived value is continuously unmatched, brand reputation is weakened, and satisfaction is not derived. Therefore, levels of fulfilment fluctuate because of levels of perceived values measured by perceptions on trust for a vendor's brand reputation.

Most of the respondents rank enjoyment as the least applicable factor among all general influencers. Fulfilment, enjoyment, and quality of online platforms rely on the levels of trust, perceived value, and brand reputation for them to have any influence on the repurchase intentions. In addition to this, evidence gathered points towards the existence of interactions between general factors and new determinants that influence customer repurchase intentions. Thorough understanding of these interactions would provide online vendors with insight on what factors might specifically influence repurchase intentions of their respective customer base. But before exploring such interactions, it is important to introduce such determinant factors that have been found to influence customer repurchase intentions within the context of this study.

5.4 Contextually based influencers: Nigeria only

In order to assist online vendors in Nigeria in developing strategies that can increase their customers' intentions to repurchase, a test was carried out to investigate the extent to which new determinant factors identified in the literature (Hsu, Chang and Chuang, 2015), influence customer repurchase intentions in Nigeria. These factors appear to have a more significant influence on customer repurchase intentions especially within Nigeria because irrespective of changes in scenarios and circumstances, they remain equally influential to customers repurchase intentions within this research context. Unlike general influencers whose levels fluctuate due to rising or falling levels of other influencers in the category (Alalwan, Baabdullah, Rana, Tamilmani, and Dwivedi, 2018), the effect of the new determinant factors in Nigeria remain significant. Evidence from this study points to the following factors as 'Nigerian only' or relevant new determinants of customer repurchase intentions and following thereafter is an exploration into how these aforementioned factors interact with general influencers of customer repurchase intentions. These interactions would be considered with the impact of socio-economic factors and players within the business ecosystem in Nigeria. These new determinant factors include:

- Previous experience and satisfaction
- Characteristics and performance of purchased product or service
- Available support and contact
- Situational factors

5.4.1 Previous experience and satisfaction PES

The researcher's initial assumptions were that customers had a general perception of distrust when shopping on websites and online platforms of Nigerian businesses. It was found that customers rely on personal judgement and evaluation skills when making first time purchases as well as referrals from trusted personal individuals and networks (Gefen, 2000). Some Nigerian customers are happy to take risks provided there is a possibility of their needs being met (Udo, 2011).

After receiving purchased products or service, Nigerian customers measure satisfaction based on how much the purchase cost them, options they had to forgo, overall ease of use of process and how much effort they spent (Ayo, 2006). When satisfaction is achieved, such customers repurchase can be counted on. However, the quality or extent to which businesses take

advantage of ease of use, after sales support and other influencers explored earlier would determine how they influence their customers overall repurchase intentions.

For respondents in this study, the most applicable influencer of their repurchase intentions is the level of satisfaction derived from previous experiences. With the highest representation of applicability, previous experience, and satisfaction scores 58% when matched across product characteristics, brand reputation, ease of use, pricing strategy and available support. Consistent with Udo (2011), Nigerian customers disregard opinions on brand image and reputation, sophistication of product and services when they have good knowledge from a personal experience. That is why it comes as no surprise results show their indifference to reviews and ratings influencing their repurchase intentions. In most service and merchandizing industries, quality of service is a differentiator that helps organizations account for competitive advantage and overall business growth (Davis, 1989). Customer repurchase intention is therefore of importance to businesses. In a nutshell, securing a customer's complete repurchase means such a customer has no need for competitors' offerings (Kim *et al.*, 2012).

Nigerian customers have brands they have experienced high levels of satisfaction. This has prompted to buy different classes of products and services. However, customer repurchase intentions remain mostly influenced by previous experiences and satisfaction. Based on these perceptions, customers distrust lower quality websites and online platforms. For instance, big brands in Nigeria such as Dangote group and Nestle are known to not have the best looking or most sophisticated online platforms but continue to retain customer repurchases. Repurchases occur because the customers are satisfied. Regardless of the nature of purchase for which knowledge on repurchase intention is useful, satisfied customers in receipt of personalised experience have a positively influenced repurchase intention. Whether Nigerian customers are buying goods and services online or directly in person, satisfaction from previous experience influences repurchases.

5.4.2 Characteristics and performance of purchased product or service

When Nigerian customers purchase products and services online, the characteristics and performance of actual products as well as quality of said services influences their repurchase intentions (Teas and Agarwal, 2000). As a result of a low prevalence of online shopping activities in Nigeria in comparison to more developed countries, certain innovations in product designs as well as commercial applications of internet and smart living require a lot more attention. Customers have unsettled and varied levels of perceived values and expectations

either because of limited knowledge and experience or there is insufficient third-party information on the product or service.

This information is useful to online businesses focused on selling new and innovative solutions to daily life problems. The hurdle for their business moving forward is to attract new prospective customers. The key thing is to deliver on promises. That way repurchases can occur. Also, when purchasing internet plans, telecommunication subscriptions, technological solutions as well as other related expenses, Nigerian customers with little knowledge on the matter rely on the functionality of the associated systems. The performance of the system is crucial. It comes as no surprise that online service providers strive to deliver personalized experiences to their buyers and business clients.

Considering this, companies providing tech solutions invest in state-of-the-art systems that engages with clients. The intention is to offer customised and tailored improvements to their packages. This is contrary to earlier findings where online vendors desist from using over-sophisticated websites. Online and technological support, product specifications, performance, and durability as well as system functionality, ease of use and innovativeness collectively influence whether repurchase can be expected. Repurchase intention in this case is more readily determined by grades, specifications, upgrade levels which all relate to product characteristics and performance.

5.4.3 Available support and contact

The ranking results placed 'available support and contact' in second place when matched across other influencers of customer repurchase intentions. Whether products and services are purchased online or in person, providing ample means of customer contact and available support directly influences repurchase. Online vendors who took part in this research also confirm that when levels of support supersede client's expectations, not only can repurchase intentions be counted on, but frequency of repurchase increases as a result of improving levels of available support and contact (Xia, Pan, Zhou, and Zhang, 2020). As a result of these provisions, Nigerian customers feel more comfortable about repurchasing because of reduced levels of risks.

Because risk is the state of being open to a chance of loss (Youn and Shin, 2020), available contact and support during the process of purchasing goods and services considerably reduces uncertainty. The results suggest that Nigerian customers prefer different contact methods. Most of the time, these kinds of support usually require human interface and through more direct

means of communications. As expected, this adds to the cost of doing business in Nigeria. Lower levels of risks felt by customers are a result of support available. This encourages repurchase intentions. Consistent with the literature, support and customer contacts positively influence repurchase intentions, and encourages business growth and development (Lee et al, 2009; Chen et al, 2002).

The results reveal that the most preferred means of communication include telephone, mobile phone, landlines, and through notifications on mobile applications where applicable. There is significant use of email campaigns and social media outlets to communicate with customers. The selection of contact method depends on the clientele. Regardless, respondents pointed out that most of their customers prefer and appreciate being contacted directly via notifications and other mobile applications.

5.4.4 Situational Factors, Consumer Traits and Attitude

The literature suggests that situational and demographic conditions play a more centred role in the way they influence customer repurchase intentions (Sarkis *et al.*, 2012). Situational factors such as gender and age, prevalence of internet and smartphone usage, online shopping frequency and behaviours, lifestyle, and standard of living, as well as purchasing power of customers are important considerations. Irrespective of online vendors' strategies and efforts towards increasing repurchase intentions, these situational factors determine the overall outlook on purchase as well as repurchase intentions (Malhorta *et al.*, 2004). This is not only because people must live within their means but also because exogenous factors affect standards of living. In this sense, different lifestyles affect repurchase intentions for different kinds of products and services (Sarkis et al., 2012).

The demographic distribution in Nigeria shows 49% and 51% of the entire population to be females and males respectively. Of the 185million people in Nigeria, 51% are young between 0 and 19 years old. Secondary data reveal that 17.5% of Nigerians are between 35 and 60 years old, while 20% fall between 20 and 35 years of age (). The gender distribution suggests equal representation and patronage for products and services differentiated on a gender basis. On the other hand, most of the country's population is relatively young. This explains the need for more ease of use and lower levels of sophistication on websites and online platforms. Given that the young people engage more with technological developments, then there is even greater need to engage with the online platforms to attract customers.

Despite the prevalence of online shopping, use of smartphones and mobile applications in Nigeria, there is still a wide gap between areas where the implementation of technology is high and areas completely lacking such means and applications. Out of the 185million people in Nigeria, only 23million people own and use smartphones daily (Ayo et al., 2007). There are however 84 million internet users, and these engage with online activities or business daily. Despite spending hours online daily, majority of customers who took part in this research claim they purchase goods online once every month. 16% of customers shop online multiple times weekly. These results illustrate that there is a huge potential market for Nigerian online businesses.

Furthermore, Nigeria has a potential low yet rising cumulative purchasing power ratio. It is estimated at 102.2 LCU per international dollars (World bank figures, 2019). In fact, the country's purchasing power ratio increases at an average annual rate of 9.85% (World Bank, 2019). Furthermore, there is a wide marginal differentiation between social classes in Nigeria – that is between first class, middle class, and lower-class citizens. Therefore, purchasing power is clearly differentiated. For example, middle- or lower-class citizens might need to deprive themselves of certain options when purchasing goods from exclusive brands. However, of customer satisfaction and other influencers being active, their repurchase remains unlikely because of low purchasing power (Vijayarathy, 2004). Purchasing power is determined by disposable income and social status of a customer.

5.5. Interaction between influencers

The results reveal that there are interactions between the extent to which general influencers and new determinants of repurchase intentions. These relationships are related to the effects of environmental and demographic conditions and their reaction regarding customer repurchase intention differs across different business sectors and industries (Pavlou, 2003). To identify and test the implications of these interactions, the most applicable general influencers and new determinants of customer repurchase intentions were matched across changing demographic and situational factors as well as across different selected industry classes. The intention was to reveal how changing conditions appear to affect the extent to which explored influencers really affect customer repurchase intentions.

Privacy, trust, and ease of use have been identified as the most applicable general influencers of customer repurchase intentions in Nigeria. On the other hand, satisfaction gained from previous experiences, available support, product characteristics and performance make up most

applicable new determinants of customer repurchase intentions in Nigeria. The exogenous factors were used in testing include consumer attitude, demography and prevalence of IT and average wealth. Pertaining to consumer attitude, it was found that general shopping patterns and frequency as well as reception of Nigerian consumers are changing.

On the other hand, demographics such as age, gender affect purchase intentions on diverse classes of products and services, access to internet and prevalence of technological advancement to smart living in the region. Lastly and most importantly average wealth in this discussion relates to the general income, wealth distribution, standards of living and purchasing power ratio of consumers in Nigeria and how these factors shape the influencers of customer repurchase intentions of this research. For discovering these interactions, selected business sectors include general everyday consumer goods such as groceries, bills, transport to mention a few, fashion and specialized products and services such as travel and hospitality, gadgets and equipment and software services.

Most Nigerian shoppers have relatively low purchasing power when compared to consumers in developed countries. Coupled with low earnings and most masses being members of low-income families who only buy from local vendors they trust, there is a massive distribution towards what classes of goods are purchased online and through traditional means. For instance, there is hardly or almost an insignificant trend to purchasing groceries, personal goods, and toiletries online. Most of the consumers purchase such goods through traditional means and in person. Therefore, it makes sense that online quality, privacy, and trust might have little influence on repurchase intentions of these customers.

Also, more than half the population have no access to the internet. For instance, secondary data sets revealed that over 70% of the country's population is not connected to smartphone technology or smart living. Mobile telephone means of purchasing rank almost equal to the number of purchases conducted on websites and online platforms. Consumer attitude towards fashion is equally distributed as purchases are made both online and through traditional methods. There is still a patronage on local fashion designers who make clothing items and fashion from a set of raw materials and those who sell already made and finished outfits.

5.5.1 Interaction between Privacy and Trust with exogenous factors

The results revealed that 78% of respondents in this research, own and use smartphones daily. However, secondary data sets reveal that only 23million people in Nigeria own smartphones which is less than 30% of the entire population. It is assumed that most subjects of this research

belong to middle- and upper-class status in the society and for this reason privacy makes up the most applicable influencer of their repurchase intentions. Findings reveal a slight twist to the stance on privacy and trust characterised by changes in personal situations and circumstances as well as changes in lifestyle.

Evidence supports the view that members of upper class, wealthy and affluent pay interests on privacy and trust and the handling of their information. can deter their repurchase intentions instantly. While lower middle class and poorer consumers pay little attention to privacy and trust, they tend to purchase and repurchase because of availability and ease of use. Further, they tend to buy out of necessity. More than half of the population of Nigeria purchase goods and services through traditional means, directly from vendors.

Under traditional methods, risks levels pertaining to privacy breach and trust are minimal (Ayo et al, 2007). Therefore, perceived value and expectations are less influential in determining their repurchase intentions. Rather, repurchase intentions are more readily influenced by satisfaction, ease of access and product availability, and not perceived value. Whereas this appears to have a different implication when goods and services are purchased through websites or online platforms. Within the fashion industry, due to apparently even distribution between online shopping and traditional methods, there is a balanced influence by privacy on customer repurchase intention. On the other hand, groceries and everyday consumer goods, privacy remains less prominent in influencing customer repurchase intentions.

With the repurchase intentions for specialised goods and services, privacy levels are considered very crucial to individuals or organisations. In this context, repurchase is considerably influenced by the security of private information. Further, trust and consumer expectations are also important considerations. Most times, these specialised goods and services are purchased or where applicable monitored through online platforms where access is provided to a buyer or customer. With rising adoption of the internet to the provision of daily business and personal solutions in Nigeria, privacy concerns are now becoming important.

Major changes in general income and wealth status resulting in lifestyle changes and improvements in standard of living also account for an increase or decrease on the impact of privacy on repurchase intentions (Sarkis et al, 2012). It was found that 89% of low-income consumers remain undisturbed by privacy issues and preferences. However, with changes in wealth, they show more concern for privacy concerns. This is interpreted to mean that poorer or low-income customers in Nigeria believe that they have nothing to lose from privacy breach

or hacking. Whereas, as income increases, consumers become more responsive to the protection of their privacy within the online environment.

5.5.2 Interaction between Ease of use and Satisfaction from previous experience and exogenous factors

It is easy to expect and imagine that with increasing levels of satisfaction derived from previous experience, repurchase intentions are likely to occur on both the online and offline platforms. However, why people buy, how they purchase, how much portion of their income, efforts dispensed, options forgone and frequency of need for such a product or service collectively determine the levels of satisfaction (Yang, 2012). This research was able to identify that when different individuals purchase the same item with equal specifications and performance efficiency, they both feel different levels of satisfaction borne because of the interaction between the factors mentioned herein. Customer repurchase intentions therefore falls on different distribution of classes of customers and their levels of satisfactions (Hume, 2008; Sarkis *et al.*, 2012).

When customers of different social classes in Nigeria purchase fashion related items or specialised goods and services, they feel different levels of satisfaction. Lower class customers might have to give away considerable portions of their earnings and forgo other necessary items to buy a product and as a result arguably feel a higher sense of satisfaction. This could be because of their commitment or long-time anticipation of owning such a product or item. Despite these high levels of satisfaction, consumers repurchase intention might be delayed or unachievable because of low disposable income. Therefore, even when repurchase intention is counted on, exogenous factors can delay or completely nullify customers' ability to repurchase products and services.

As stated earlier about most Nigerian consumers depend on traditional means for purchase and repurchase of products and services. In instances where such customers enjoy the benefits and convenience of online shopping, they experience multiple levels of satisfaction. The exogenous factors here positively influence such customers repurchase intention. In this case, satisfaction from previous experience is considered as a more reliable and efficient measure of repurchase intention.

Due to increasing online retailing activities, big vendors such as Konga in partnerships with local restaurants and chefs sell food and meal deals online in Nigeria. There is an emerging target market of working-class single individuals and working-class families who use these

online facilities. Satisfaction derived from making use of this service and the extent to which their needs are met determines repurchase intentions. However, lower income families who despite patronizing such service one time and being completely satisfied are unlikely to repurchase because of exogenous factors. In fact, they may consider some products as a luxury treat whilst upper class individuals perceive such a business meeting a genuine necessity, providing convenience, and saving them time.

5.5.3 Product characteristic, Service performance – Interaction with Exogenous factors

Findings of this research suggest that product characteristics and quality of service performance rely on consumer attitude, income levels and demography in the way they influence customer repurchase intentions in Nigeria. Further investigation through controlled situations during interviews sessions reveal that the actual product, that is the material, the way it looks, feels or appears or when purchasing a service, its overall implementation and performance efficiency is evaluated across exogenous situations of the buyer. Whether this occurs unconsciously or as a calculated evaluation process, repurchase intention is strongly affected by how they rate or perceive purchased products in line with their situational conditions.

For example, repurchase of a product whose performance attracts high maintenance or running costs unknown to the middle-class buyer at inception is completely unknown or unlikely. This is not just because such costs are not accounted for in the shopping pattern or attitude, but, the general income and standard of life is not consistent with the repurchase intentions. Upper class consumers rate product characteristics highly and because of their high standards, they expect and rely on prime quality in the actual product they purchase or quality of service. Situational factors around their lifestyle support their need to repurchase such products and services so long as their expectations on the product quality is constantly met. Also, with respect to groceries and daily consumer products and services, a majority of which occurs through traditional means as results have revealed, product characteristics are considerably known, and expectations contained due to necessity needs. Here, exogenous factors play a weaker role in influencing customer repurchase which is driven by need. Therefore, the original purchase of this class of product is completely guided and based on personal exogenous and situational factors.

5.5.4 Available support and exogenous factors

Whether products and services are purchased online or through traditional means, findings of this study reveal that support to customers guarantees repurchase intentions (Chen *et al.*, 2012). In some cases, exorbitant and unforeseen circumstances affect customers' ability to repurchase

(Udo, 2011). The results reveal that in the absence of a customer support mechanism, Nigerian customers tend to seek new alternatives.

Whether the goods are for daily use, or specialised products and services, exogenous factors do not directly affect repurchase intentions. Therefore, there is a need of customer support systems to help encourage repurchase intentions. Nigerian online shoppers confirm that life circumstances such as unavailable funds or low income can affect customer repurchases. However, repurchase intentions are more encouraged by customer support systems. The literature suggests that exogenous and demographic factors can only delay, hinder or alter repurchase and repurchase frequency but cannot alter the influence of available support on customer repurchase intentions (Malhorta et al., 2004).

5.5.5 An emergent model of consumer repurchases intentions

Figure 5.1 presents, an emergent model of consumer repurchases intentions. At the intersection of exogenic factors, theoretical influencers, contextually based influencers, and repurchase intentions, are some strategies that can be adopted by online vendors to compete more effectively. The strategies include, 1) maintain global theoretical views, 2) develop localised theoretical views, 3) review and adapt influencers, 4) maintain globalised marketing strategies, and 5) develop localised marketing strategies.

Figure 5. 1: Emergent model of consumer repurchase intentions

Source: Author's own construction

5.5.5.1 Proposition 1: maintain global theoretical views

It is proposed that where Nigerian consumers maintain global attitudes, and westernised views of consumption, existing theoretical influencers of consumer repurchase intentions must be used as a resource to develop marketing strategies. This will help the online vendors to be in synch with global trends, and consumption behaviours, as depicted in the literature, and in most accounts of consumer repurchase intentions.

5.5.5.2 Proposition 2: develop localised theoretical views

It is proposed that where Nigerian consumers are more inclined towards local attitudes, and local views of consumption, online vendors must develop localised views of influencers on consumer repurchase intentions. These localised understandings must be used as a resource to develop effective marketing strategies. This will help the online vendors to be in synch with local trends, and consumption behaviours that can be transformed into consumer repurchase intentions.

5.5.5.3 Proposition 3: review and adapt influencers

It is proposed that online vendors must first develop an understanding of existing theoretical understandings of influencers on consumer repurchase intentions. However, these influencers must not be understood in isolation, but be reviewed and adapted to ensure that they are in synch with local understandings. This will help online vendors to identify meaningful influencers, as well as other influences that often go unreported in most accounts of consumer repurchase intentions.

5.5.5.4 Proposition 4: maintain globalised marketing strategies

It is proposed that where Nigerian consumers maintain global attitudes, and westernised views of consumption, existing theoretical influencers of consumer repurchase intentions must be used as a resource to develop marketing strategies. Further, vendors must utilise globalised marketing techniques as depicted in the literature, as these have already been tried and tested, and help to encourage consumer repurchase intentions.

5.5.5.5 Proposition 5: develop localised marketing strategies

It is proposed that where Nigerian consumers are more inclined towards local attitudes, and local views of consumption, online vendors must develop localised views of influencers on consumer repurchase intentions. Further, localised understandings of consumer repurchase intentions must be used to develop marketing strategies that are relevant.

5.6 Chapter summary

This chapter discussed the results of the study within the context of the literature. Both primary and secondary data sets were used to discuss the demographics of the Nigerian consumer. The impact of different factors on purchase intentions were discussed within the context of primary data sets, both qualitative and quantitative. An outcome of the study was the development of a contextually based model that can assist online vendors in Nigeria to develop marketing strategies that can increase their customers' intentions to repurchase. The next chapter draws conclusions, outlines the study contributions, and makes some recommendations.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Introduction

This chapter first makes a summary of the study and states the main conclusions. It is then followed by a discussion how each of the objectives, as stated in chapter 1, were achieved. Theoretical and managerial contributions of the study are also outlined. Recommendations are then made, and study limitations acknowledged. Areas of future research are also outlined.

6.2 Summary and Main Conclusions

This part summarises the research and presents the main conclusions.

6.2.1 Summary of the Research

This study was conducted because of gaps in knowledge in the literature surrounding consumer repurchase intentions. The literature also revealed that there is a direct relationship between consumers repurchase intentions and online businesses growth rate. In response to the rising online business activity, and the need to understand more deeply, about the factors that affect customers' intentions to repurchase, a study was then conducted to examine the influencers of online shoppers repurchase intentions within the context of consumers in Nigeria. This was extended to also consider the impact of active exogenous factors on consumer repurchase intentions.

The study adopted a mixed methods approach, with the intention of obtaining insights that help to answer the research questions. The quantitative data sets were generated from a survey with 100 respondents. This helped to generate some insights on the attitude and perceptions of Nigerian consumers. As a follow up to insights obtained from the quantitative element of the study, participants were convened to help explore some of the emergent issues and help establish a deeper understanding of the survey results. This unveiled the demographic dynamics in Nigeria and their implications on online repurchase intentions. Further, insights from the interview discussions deepened understanding of the impact of social media platforms on repurchase intentions. This also helped to reveal localised understandings factors that influence consumer repurchase intentions. Some of the emergent factors, were contrary to what has been outlined in the literature in chapter 2. Some of the factors confirmed what has been outlined

in the literature. Contextually nested factors that affect consumer repurchase intentions also emerged.

Semi-structured interviews with industry experts, and online vendors were also conducted. These helped to provide deeper insights about issues surrounding online businesses in Nigeria. Transcripts from these interviews were analysed using content and thematic analysis. This helped to deepen the researcher's understanding of online shopping within the Nigerian context. The data sets were analysed sequentially with the intention of obtaining richer and deeper understandings of factors that influence repurchase intentions. Relationships between the theoretically identified influencers on repurchase intentions were tested. Further, the interaction of the existing factors and emergent factors were also tested for their impact on exogenous factors. From the analysis of all the data sets, contextually bound factors that influence consumer repurchase intentions were identified.

The study has ascertained the factors influencing consumer's intentions to repurchase goods and services that are sold via the online and other associated e-commerce platforms. Some of these factors were found to be applicable within the Nigerian online shopping environment. Results are in support of the view that privacy concerns and trust are the strongest general influencers on online consumer repurchase intentions. Therefore, online marketing strategies must focus on addressing the privacy and trust concerns as reported by respondents. This will help to promote online traffic and improved sales. It also emerged that exogenous and situational factors are interconnected with the factors that influence repurchase intentions.

The study also unveiled new determinant factors have on consumer repurchase intentions that are applicable within the Nigerian context. Within this, it was found that consumer satisfaction from previous experience, and the availability of customer support systems are the most influential factors on consumer repurchase intentions in Nigeria. The results reveal that these factors are not directly affected by the effects of exogenous factors. It is concluded that online retailers in Nigeria must ensure that adequate and continuous support is availed to customers. Further, online retailers must continuously monitor and improve on levels of satisfaction derived by shoppers. These factors are of strategic importance, and as such, must be used as a strategic resource to ensure business success.

The findings have not only shown a dynamic nature in the extent to which influencers of customer repurchase intentions are exhibited within the Nigerian online shopping context, but they have established an in-depth understanding of why consumer repurchase intention must

be accorded periodic review by researchers. It also emerged that there is a dearth of studies that focus on individual influencers and their roles within online shopping activity in Nigeria. This can be attributed to low internet penetration. However, online shopping activity is on the increase. Therefore, there is a need for online vendors to review their marketing strategies to be in synch with changing consumer trends. There is greater need for marketers in Nigeria to capitalise on positive online repurchase intentions.

6.2.2 Achieving the Aim and Objectives

This section discusses how each of the research objectives were achieved. The study's aim was to examine the factors that influence consumers' intentions and propose a framework that can help managers to develop more effective marketing strategies. This study focused on consumer repurchase intentions within Nigeria's online retailing environment. The aim was achieved by adopting a mixed methods approach. Within this, a sequential approach of data collection and analysis was used. Firstly, the secondary data was collected and analysed. This was then followed by the collection and analysis of survey data. Finally, qualitative data was collected and analysed. At each stage, the data collection and analysis were guided by the research aim and objectives. Gaining insights from multiple data sets helped to deepen understandings of online repurchase intention within the Nigerian context. Five objectives, as outlined in chapter 1, were used to guide the study. Each is discussed here in turn.

6.2.2.1 Objective number one: literature review

The first objective was "*To critically review the literature surrounding customer repurchase intention*". The intention was to identify gaps in knowledge that would help to position the current study more strongly within ongoing academic debates. Insights to address this objective were obtained from peer reviewed journal articles, books, and other related materials, as illustrated by the list of references, and associated in-text references in chapter 2. It was found that several models and theories have been developed to help understand online customer repurchase behaviour. For instance, the TAM model explores variables like trust, enjoyment, e-service quality amongst others (Davis, 1989; Bae and Han, 2020). However, TAM has its own downside. For instance, important factors such as customer satisfaction, customer traits, internet literacy, situational factors, and customer traits, are all missing. It was learnt that contextual understandings of the existing models are missing. Further, it was also found that there is a dearth of studies on customer repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context. In summary, this objective was met by the literature discussed in chapter 2.

6.2.2.2 Objective number two: determinants of customer, repurchase intentions

The second objective was “*To analyse the determinants of customer, repurchase intentions within the Nigerian context*”. The determinants of consumer repurchase intentions were identified in chapter 2. Using primary data sets, an analysis of these determinants was conducted as outlined in chapter 4. It was also found that within the Nigerian context, the key determinants that influence customer repurchase intentions, within the online environment, include satisfaction from previous experiences, available support, privacy concerns, levels of trust and perceived reliability. It was also found that these influencers are interconnected with exogenous and circumstantial factors. Thus, exogenous factors were found to be contextually nested, and had greater impact on customer repurchase intentions. Insights that helped to address this objective were obtained from primary data sets, both qualitative and quantitative. These data sets are as presented in chapter 4. Following from the results obtained, this research has achieved the second objective.

6.2.2.3 Objective number three: role of social media on customer repurchase intention

The third objective was “*To determine the role of social media on customer repurchase intention*”. In the quantitative study, it was found that 83% of the respondents agreed that social platforms and tools influence consumer repurchases on the online platforms. Further, 70% agreed that fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media. Further results revealed that 65% of the respondents agree that social media platform promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting.

It was also found that the influence of social media is positively correlated with privacy and trust. This is illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.509**. This is significant at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. Once again, the strength of the association was weak. It was also found that there is a weak positive association between influence of social media and brand reputation. This is illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.452**, and is significant at the 0.01 level, 2-tailed. The results also revealed a very weak correlation between influence of social media and system availability, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of 0.370**, at the 0.01 level, 2 tailed. Further results reveal a non-existent relationship between influence of social media and factors for online repurchases. With a p value of .866, the null hypothesis was accepted. Finally, results also revealed a negative very weak correlation between influence of social media and other factors for online repurchases, as illustrated by a correlation coefficient of -0.220**, 2 tailed. These results were reinforced by insights from the qualitative study. It was

found that both traditional medias, including “word of mouth” and social media, are avenues that are used by the respondents’ organisations for marketing purposes. However, some customers are moved by what they see on social media whilst some are not moved at all. Whilst there is an increasing trend towards the use of online shopping and social media to engage with customers, managers must also continue to use traditional avenues because some customers do not easily adapt to innovations.

Results of secondary data analysis also revealed that as the number of internet users increases, the sales volumes of Jumia, one of the leading online retailers in Nigeria, also increases. The results suggest that as the number of internet users in Nigeria increase, there is also a corresponding increase in the total labour force, and internet subscribers. Similarly, as the number of social network users worldwide increases, there is a corresponding increase in the number of internet users in Nigeria, total labour force in Nigeria, and internet subscribers. Further, as Nigeria’s GDP per capita increases, there is a corresponding increase in the GDP, the number of internet users, and the number of internet subscribers. This provides an opportunity to online businesses, and thus reinforces earlier results of a positive correlation between the number of internet users and the sales revenues of Jumia, one of the leading online retailers in Nigeria. This is also interpreted as an opportunity for businesses to encourage online purchases. Following from the results obtained, and as outlined in chapter 4, this research has achieved the third objective.

6.2.2.4 Objective number four: knowledge of customer repurchase intention

This objective was designed “*To evaluate how the knowledge of customer repurchase intention can enhance company sales*”. It was found that there is a growing trend of online sales. However, it is not everyone who visits the website that buys. Others “*stumble*” and “*go*”. Therefore, managers must ensure that no one “*stumbles*” by making the online purchasing process simple. Because of fraud, first time users are always sceptical of online shopping. However, once trusted relations have been established, online purchases occur. It was found that brand reputation influences customer repurchases. The findings suggest that a positive reputation leads to other referrals, repurchases, and improved sales. Here, their reputation is built around the quality of service that they provide. In this sense, brand reputation is a strategic resource for customer repurchases. Other respondents suggested that repurchases can be improved by personalisation of the customer experience within the online platforms. In this way, customers feel valued and wanted, and establish a sense of a “*personalised feel*”. It also gives the customers a sense of belonging, and thus mostly likely to result in customer

repurchases and increased sales. Thus, the knowledge of customer repurchase intentions obtained through the different data sets culminated in a development of a framework, and some recommendations that can help to increase the company sales (see chapters 4, 5, and 6). Following from the results obtained, and as outlined in chapter 4, this research has achieved the fourth objective.

6.2.2.5 Objective number five: proposed framework

The fifth objective was “*To propose a framework that can help managers to develop more effective marketing strategies within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention*”. This was designed to make theoretical and managerial contributions to the area of customer repurchase intentions. An outcome of the study was the development of a framework that can help managers to develop more effective marketing strategies within the context of online shopping and customer repurchase intention. Figure 5.1 presents, an emergent model of consumer repurchases intentions. It is arguing that at the intersection of exogenic factors, theoretical influencers, contextually based influencers, and repurchase intentions, are some strategies that can be adopted by online vendors to compete more effectively. Following from this, four propositions are made. Firstly, that where Nigerian consumers maintain global attitudes, and westernised views of consumption, existing theoretical influencers of consumer repurchase intentions must be used as a resource to develop marketing strategies. Secondly, where Nigerian consumers are more inclined towards local attitudes, and local views of consumption, online vendors must develop localised views of influencers on consumer repurchase intentions. These localised understandings must be used as a resource to develop effective marketing strategies. This will help the online vendors to be in synch with local trends, and consumption behaviours that can be transformed into consumer repurchase intentions. Thirdly, online vendors must first develop an understanding of existing theoretical understandings of influencers on consumer repurchase intentions. This will help online vendors to identify meaningful influencers, as well as other influences that often go unreported in most accounts of consumer repurchase intentions. Fourthly, that where Nigerian consumers maintain global attitudes, and westernised views of consumption, existing theoretical influencers of consumer repurchase intentions must be used as a resource to develop marketing strategies. This will help to encourage consumer repurchase intentions. Finally, that where Nigerian consumers are more inclined towards local attitudes, and local views of consumption, online vendors must develop localised views of influencers on consumer repurchase intentions. Further, localised understandings of consumer repurchase intentions must be used to develop

marketing strategies that are relevant. Considering this, this research has achieved the fifth objective. The proposed framework is as illustrated in figure 5.1 in chapter 5 and as shown below in figure 6.1.

Figure 6. 2: Emergent model of consumer repurchase intentions

Source: Author’s own construction

6.2.2.6 Outcome of hypothesis testing

In chapter 2, hypothesis statements that were informed by the literature were generated. This study collected a data set that was used to test the same hypothesis, but within the context of online repurchasing intentions in Nigeria. The outcome of the hypothesis testing is as illustrated in table 6.1. The results found are mixed, with some supported and others not supported. This suggests that there are some contextual differences with the current study and studies conducted in other countries. Therefore, managers must develop localised understandings of factors that influence consumer repurchase intentions within the online environment.

Table 6. 1: Outcome of hypothesis testing

Alternative Hypothesis	N	P-value (sig.)	Correlation co-efficient	Direction of Association/ relationship	Strength of Association/ relationship	Decision
H1: Perceived value influences customer online repurchase behavior	100	.000	.541**	Positive	Weak	Accept
H2: Perceived ease of use influences customer online repurchase behaviour.	100	.301	-.105	Negative	None	Reject
H3: Brand reputation influences online repurchase intentions	100	.762	-.031	Negative	None	Reject
H4: Privacy concerns influence customer repurchase intention	100	.026	-.233*	Negative	Very weak	Accept
H5: Trust may largely influence online repurchase behaviour.	100	.006	-.271**	Negative	Very weak	Accept
H6: Perceived usefulness of the website may influence online repurchase intentions.	100	.310	-.103	Negative	None	Reject
H7: Enjoyment prompts customer repurchase intention	100	.977	-.003	Negative	None	Reject
H8: Consumer fulfilment influence online repurchase intentions	100	.620	.050	Positive	None	Reject
H9: System availability and functionality influences customer repurchase intention.	100	.000	.390**	Positive	Very weak	Accept
H10: Other factors influences repurchase intention (efficient delivery, contact etc)	100	.028	-.220*	Negative	Very weak	Accept

Considering this, this research has tested the hypothesis that were generated in chapter 2. The study is consistent with previous literature in some parts. For instance, the literature suggests that perceived value influences customer online repurchase behaviour (Salehzadeh and Pool, 2017; Dam, 2020). Others are contented that privacy concerns influence customer repurchase intention (Mathur, 2019; Tawalbeh, Muheidat, Tawalbeh, and Quwaider, 2020). Previous studies have also found that trust influence online purchase behaviour (Bulut and Karabulut, 2018; Ventre and Kolbe, 2020). The study findings are consistent with the literature, at least for this part. Contrary to the literature (Grover, Kar, Janssen, and Ilavarasan, 2019; Sheppard and Vibert, 2019), it was found that perceived ease of use does not influence customer online purchase behaviour in the Delta state. This is explained by different cultural and demographics. Similarly, the results contradict the literature that suggests that brand reputation influences online repurchase intentions. These contradictions, and others, are significant because they go on to demonstrate the importance of contextual understandings of customer online repurchase intentions. Therefore, understandings of the TAM model must be adapted and modified to different contextual situations. This will help the model to be more relevant.

6.3 Contributions of the Research

This section outlines the theoretical and managerial contributions of the study.

6.3.1 Theoretical Contributions

The study makes six theoretical contributions as outlined in this section.

6.3.1.1 Proposed model of consumer repurchase intentions

The proposed model of consumer repurchase intention, as illustrated in Figure 5.1 presents, contributes to theoretical debates in this area. The model depicts exogenic factors, as being located at the intersection of theoretical influencers and contextually based influencers. Yet, in the literature, the exogenic factors are theoretically understood, much to the neglect of contextual understandings as revealed by insights from this study. This takes the debate on consumer repurchase intentions in a new direction that can help online vendors in Nigeria to develop more effective marketing strategies. The strategic marketing positions that emerge are 1) maintain global strategic marketing theoretical views, 2) develop localised strategic marketing theoretical views, 3) review and adapt purchase intention influencers, 4) maintain globalised marketing strategies, and 5) develop localised marketing strategies.

6.3.1.2 Revisiting theoretical understandings of consumer repurchase intentions

This study makes contributions to the empirical literature on customer repurchase intentions. It generates a list of new determinants of customer repurchase intentions that are relevant to the Nigerian context (Udo, 2011). This challenge existing preconceived ideas and theoretical understandings of consumer repurchase intentions. The findings from the study suggests that there is a need to revisit existing theories in this domain with the intention of generating theoretical understandings that are relevant and usable in the Nigerian context.

Although there is rising interest from scholars and businesses on customer repurchase intentions, there is still a dearth of studies that focus on the effect of exogenous factors. The focus on exogenous factors shifts the debate on consumer repurchase intentions into a new direction and helps marketers to rethink their strategies. For instance, it has always been assumed in the literature that social media reviews and ratings play a major influence on customer repurchase intention (Ayo, 2006; Udo, 2011). However, this was not the case with Nigerian consumers. In fact, it emerged that Nigerian customers pay little attention or reliance on information from review sites. Further, it was found that social media platforms have little influence on Nigerian customers repurchase intentions. Although Nigerian consumers spend time interacting on social media platforms, they engage less with the online environment to make purchases.

The results revealed that privacy and trust are the most influential factors to customer repurchase intentions compared to other influencers. However, when exogenous factors are introduced, the need/necessity becomes a major factor, and not trust and privacy concerns. Therefore, as living standards change, the factors that influence consumer repurchase intentions also change. The interaction between general influencers of consumer repurchase intentions, as identified in the literature, and the contextually based determinants of customer repurchase intentions, sets research in this area in a new direction. Therefore, marketers must pay attention to both factors that are applicable on a global scale, and those that are applicable in specific contexts. This suggests that there is a need to rethink our theoretical understandings of consumer repurchase intentions. Therefore, contextual understandings of exogenous factors must be an inseparable part of any theorisation on consumer repurchase intentions. This is a potential area that future research can focus on.

6.3.1.3 International business and investors

The study also makes contributions to our understanding of international business. Multinational corporations that have a presence in Nigeria can benefit from insights from this study and learn how they must adapt their marketing strategies if they are to grow and be sustainable in the Nigerian market. Insights from this study can help prospective international businesses and investors to succeed in the Nigerian market. This will help then to develop contextually relevant marketing strategies, as well as use local knowledge systems as a resource that can help to enhance their business performance and sustainability.

6.3.1.4 Significance to public policy bodies and local investment institutions

The findings from this research are important for public policy making and investment institutions within Nigeria in a few ways. Firstly, the demographic dynamics illustrated in this research can be used as a resource to help increase revenue generation, and this consequently contributes to Nigeria's GDP. Secondly, information in this study can be used to enhance the performance of SMEs, as well support local online businesses and other entrepreneurial ventures. Thirdly, local investors can also use the information provided herein to aid investing into and empowering local businesses to effectively use the marketing strategies proposed in this study, with the intention of helping local businesses to be competitive in a globalised business environment. This will also help local businesses to use a wealth of the local knowledge systems to their advantage when powerful international brands encroach onto their market. Hence, the proposed marketing strategies can be used as a resource that can help the local businesses to compete more effectively. In this sense, managers of local brands can thus

make informed online marketing decisions that will help to encourage customer repurchase intentions.

6.3.1.5 Online vendors and local businesses in Nigeria

This research has provided insights into the key influencers of customer repurchase intentions within the online shopping environment. Online businesses in Nigeria can use insights from this study as a resource to increase sales by developing targeted strategies that impact on customer repurchases. Scholars suggest that maintaining and managing repurchase intentions of an existing and faithful customer is more efficient to online businesses than securing a new customer (Jiang and Wang, 2006). Thus, findings of this study can help local businesses to retain their customers. This is important for business growth purposes in a competitive and liberalised business environment.

Local understandings of exogenous factors can be used to develop targeted marketing strategies that can impact on customer repurchase intentions. The exogeneous factors can be used to identify and classify customers whose repurchase intentions are more likely within a given context. This can help to monitor and observe trends, as well as adapt marketing strategies to ensure competitiveness in an ever-changing business environment. The demographic information and situational factors can help to inform online businesses about the untapped potential for new market segments, thereby helping the businesses to be more competitive.

From the proposed model as outlined in figure 5.1, managers can be better informed about what the local customers' needs and preferences rather than relying on preconceived perceptions on what influences customers repurchase intentions (Semeijn *et al.*, 2005). In fact, this will help businesses to provide tailored online, and personalised experiences. In this sense, an understanding of the interaction between general influencers and contextually developed determinants of customer repurchase intention can help local businesses organise resources more meaningfully and develop marketing strategies that will produce a positive impact on customer repurchase intentions.

Whilst the internet provides opportunities for marketing and sales growth, there is a need for Nigerian businesses to draw insights from this study and develop targeted and effective marketing strategies. In fact, insights from this study can help to establish customer repurchases. This is vital for business growth, competitiveness, and sustainability within the context of global brands that are encroaching on the Nigerian market.

6.3.1.6 Periodic surveys on consumer attitudes and effect of Influencers of customer repurchase intentions

Given the ever-changing business environment and evolving consumer perceptions towards online shopping activities, it is recommended that online vendors must periodic surveys to assess changes in consumer repurchase intentions. Unlike traditional consumer and market research surveys, this study recommends that Nigerian online businesses structure base surveys around the influence of technology acceptance models (TAM factors) and the new determinants of customer repurchase intentions, as outlined in this study. This will help businesses to make relevant and informed decisions.

The results suggest that TAM factors play a healthy role in influencing customer repurchase intentions in Nigeria. Therefore, online vendors must gather timely data on significant interactions between TAM factors, new determinants, and exogenous conditions within their respective industries. The results reveal that by preference, Nigerian customers have a variety of brands that they associate with, and this helps them to determine their purchases. The standards on which these judgments are made are dependent on a given context, time and situation.

6.3.2 Managerial Contributions

Online vendors must understand that consumers sometimes do not make choices solely to maximise their expected utility as stated by rational choices theory. Therefore, there is a need for managers to anticipate unexpected behaviours and be prepared to adjust their strategies to connect with factors affecting consumer repurchase intentions. For instance, there is a need for managers in the Delta state to understand that consumers use social media for social interaction purposes, and not necessarily to transact. As such, there is a need for managers to be proactive, and engage with the customers on the social media platforms. The intention is to build relationships and trust, and then direct the potential customers to the physical stores for their purchases. This approach can be adapted to suit different groups of customers. The results reveal that this is an approach that can help to increase the company sales.

Given that value derived resides not in the purchase but in the consumption experience, Nigerian online vendors must aspire to continually gather data to inform them on properly maximising influencers of customer repurchase intentions for increased sales and online traffic. It is recommended that online vendors employ the expertise of behavioural scientists in conducting and analysing results from these periodic surveys. This is because of the serious questions being raised by behavioural law and economic experts regarding rational choice

theory, suggesting that rational choice theory does not completely describe how consumers behave. This has been highlighted by the contextually based results from Nigeria. In this sense, managers must draw insights from the contextually based factors to make informed decisions. This entails engaging in period research with the intention of gathering information that will help to sharpen their strategies, as well as make informed decisions.

Managers must pay attention to both factors that are applicable on a global scale, and those that are applicable in specific contexts. There is a need for marketing managers to rethink theoretical understandings of consumer repurchase intentions. Here, managers must draw insights from contextual understandings of exogenous factors in making decisions associated with customer repurchase intentions. This will help to increase the company sales within the online environment.

6.4 Recommendations

The results suggest that there is a need for knowledge of customer repurchase intentions to be perceived as a resource that can help online vendors and other businesses in Nigeria to compete more effectively, generate sales, and achieve business growth. These recommendations are meant to help managers in their decision making at a practical level.

6.4.1 Adopt a localised model of click and collect

Nigerian customers who took part in this research have shown a keenness for the click and collect models. Some respondents claim to have generated maximum levels of satisfaction from the ease of using click and collect services from other countries. As such, they expressed a willingness to engage with click and collect within the Nigerian shopping environment. It is proposed that managers must develop localised understandings of the click and collect model.

Previous research suggests that the ‘click and collect’ models seamlessly merge digital and physical consumer channels (Tubridy, 2017). By coordinating the efforts of e-commerce and physical stores (traditional methods) time and expense associated with transporting an item to the customer is reduced. It must be pointed out that the “click and collect” model is widely used in Europe and is gaining increasing attention from North American retail giants. Click and collect has significant advantages for both Nigerian customers and online vendors.

Nigerian online shoppers benefit from added convenience, reduced levels of perceived risks and increased levels of trust. Online vendors benefit in terms of reduced delivery costs. This is because with click and collect, customers assume responsibility of getting purchased items from shop to home. Also, click and collect models involve different approaches and delivery

or pick up of items can take different forms (Bell and Howell, 2017). The most common form involves where items are paid for online and picked up by customer in store, or items are reserved online but customers make payments and pick the items up in the shop. When items are paid for online, collection can be made through a holding service centre, designated store outlets or a centralized hub or collection of hubs solely designated for click and collect customers.

6.4.2 Conduct periodic surveys of consumer repurchase intentions

Secondly, periodic consumer and market surveys must be conducted to ascertain the influencers of customer repurchase intentions within the Nigerian online environment.

6.4.3 Enhance and localise the human interface in the click and collect model

It emerged that Nigerian customers prefer the human interface and support when making purchases online. This provides an opportunity for organisations to implement the click and collect model. In a sense, this would help to improve the penetration of e-commerce and online shopping. This would also mean that some elements of the traditional shopping models are maintained. To ensure the effective implementation of the click and collect model in Nigeria, there must be opportunities for customers to make reservations within the online platforms, and then they visit the physical stores to inspect and collect their purchases. However, a drawback here are internet access and affordability of data bundles. These contextually based barriers affect repurchases. As such, the human interface in this context, must be informed by local understandings.

6.4.4 Form strategic retail locations with internet access

Because of limited internet access in some areas of Nigeria, it is suggested that online vendors must identify retail outlets in strategic locations, and work in partnership to ensure the success of the click and collect model. Within these strategic retail locations internet access is provided. This must be secure and guarantee customers their privacy and confidentiality. This will help to build trust within the online shopping environment. Such strategic locations must have continual access to the internet. In this sense, click and collect stores can provide the basic access to making use of online platforms, thereby encouraging online purchases. At these strategic locations, trained personnel must be made available to help deal with customer queries on the spot. This human interface will help to build consumer trust and confidence.

6.4.5 Develop targeted marketing strategies

Though the implementation of the click and collect models is costly, this will be offset by the associated benefits of the model. For instance, the click and collect scheme will help online

businesses in accounting purposes, tracking stocks, maintaining sales records, and customer profiles. This can help managers to develop targeted marketing strategies using the customer information collected. This is reinforced by the fact that retail giants such as Argos, confirm that transactions from click and collect purchases account for one third of their annual revenue (Tubridy, 2017). Argos is always innovating on ways to combine digital and human interfaces to achieve best results. In fact, the click and collect model has been in practiced by Argos over the last 15 years and they continue to improve on its offerings through the inclusions of services for more value-added experience (Tubridy, 2017).

6.4.6 Form strategic partnerships/ alliances

Despite the demonstrable gains in sales and traffic as well as significance to brand reputation and sustainability, several North American retailers who have implemented the click and collect models have experienced difficulties around logistical factors. Mostly occurring problems include having too many separate distribution networks for online and store as well as click and collect, voluminous and difficult to manage inventory systems, real time correlation between availability of items online and in click and collect store. Lastly, considerably higher than expected expenses associated with customers picking up purchased items in store.

Nonetheless, as with every progressive or innovative solutions, there would always be challenges to successful implementation. Online vendors in Nigeria must pay close attention and monitor steps taken to limit the impact of challenges outlined above. It is proposed that they must develop localised understandings of the click and collect model. Within this context, forming strategic alliances with delivery companies, and other members of the supply chain, will help in managing logistical problems and ensure that the click and collect model is implemented effectively.

6.5 Limitations of the Research

1. The first notable limitation is that of sample size. The sample size would have been much larger had enough resources been available to help with the data collection. However, a sample size of 100 respondents was large enough to provide some insights in this study area. Though this was limited, it was complemented by data sets from interviews and secondary data sets. Regardless, the small sample size for the quantitative part of the study might have affected the results of hypothesis testing.

2. There were high expectations that the research sample size will be a lot higher but the low level of computer literacy in this location affected the number of respondents that may have been reached.
3. This being a doctoral study was limited by time. This kind of study would have benefited if it spanned over a prolonged period and tracking groups of online shoppers. However, given the time limit of a doctoral study, this was not possible.
4. Another limitation was limited financial resources. The study was self-sponsored, meaning that some secondary data sets that needed to be accessed after paying some subscription fees were not accessed. However, secondary data sets used were those available in the public domain, and those that could be accessed via the university's library system. For the primary data, the qualitative part may be subjective by the very nature of qualitative data sets. However, these were complemented by a survey of 100 respondents. Regardless, had resources been available, the sample size for the survey would have been increased to over 500 respondents to help reduce the sampling error.
5. Limited resources also meant that the researcher had to conduct both face to face in noisy business areas and telephonic interviews where there were issues with recording equipment. Therefore, it was not always possible to capture all that was said by the respondents. However, shorthand was used where necessary to help document important issues discussed, and these were then developed into more detailed and corpus notes immediately after the interview. The intention was to record them as freshly as possible so that important details were not lost or forgotten.
6. The researcher assumed that the respondents gave their honest opinions about the subject matter under investigation. However, there are always possibilities that some respondents may not share honest opinions. Hence, this interferes with the quality and generalisability of the results. Conscious of limitations like these, the researcher used a mixed methods approach to help enhance the quality of the results.
7. Customer repurchase intention is a phenomenon that changes over time and as a result needs a prolonged engagement in the field. However, this was not possible because of the time limit of a doctoral study.
8. Whilst using many methods in a single study helps the research to be enriched by the benefits of triangulation (Denscombe, 2014), it is also important to acknowledge the limitations of using many methods in a single study. There is little concentration or

focus on any specific method, and this may affect analytical depth given the limited word count of a doctoral study.

9. Although the use of in-depth interviews is one of the most successful ways to collect rich qualitative data (Denscombe, 2014), the researcher was unable to meet all the interviewees in person due to diverse geographical locations. Therefore, in order to pre-qualify candidates for this study, the telephone was used. In fact, two in-depth interviews were conducted telephonically, and only verbal communication could be assessed. The facial expressions or body language could not be used to enrich the qualitative findings. Regardless, both the physical and telephonic interviews helped to reach the intended respondents at least cost.

6.6 Direction for Future Studies

Throughout the course of this research, several important concepts and areas that need further studies have been identified. In this section, study areas that might help understandings in the customer repurchase intentions area within the Nigerian context are proposed. These are informed by gaps in knowledge and issues that have been identified in this study. These suggestions are meant to inform academic researchers of areas that might need further research to help inform scholarly debates, and managerial practice.

6.6.1 Study 1

First and foremost, it is important for future research works and studies to draw insights from a much larger sample size but using research instruments like the ones used in this study. This will help to reduce the sampling errors and generate results that can be more generalisable. Such studies must also extend the demographic distribution in terms of age and income of the respondents. This is because Nigeria has an almost even distribution between urban and rural dwellers, it is easy for research data to be retrieved mainly from a concentrated demography of respondent without properly accounting for a vast majority of the population.

6.6.2 Study 2

More studies are needed that focus on ‘pay on delivery’ and ‘click and collect’ practices within the Nigerian context. Future studies can pay attention to specific industries to obtain deep understandings, as such insights might help online vendors to implement click and collect models more effectively. The emphasis of current studies in this area on global brands and international markets. Therefore, there is a need for studies that focus on the Nigerian context.

6.6.3 Study 3

Thirdly, future research must focus on the impact of exogenous factors conditions and situational factors, as outlined in this study, on consumer repurchase intentions. Due to limited academic literature focused on Nigeria's exogenous factors, this research spent vital time trying to generate information on exogenous factors and their effects. It is important for future research to focus on this issue in order to contribute to empirical literature on the subject.

6.6.4 Study 4

There is a need for future studies to use the identified local factors of consumer repurchase intentions and see if they are relevant to other online shopping experiences in other sectors within Nigeria. Further, this will also help to test the proposed model of consumer repurchase intentions.

6.6.5 Study 5

Given the complexity of factors that affect consumer repurchase intentions, and conflicting results between the literature and some of the current study's findings, there is a need for future studies that examine these influencers individually and in greater depth.

6.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter has revisited the research objectives, and then outlined how each of the objectives was achieved. The chapter also summarises the whole thesis, and outlines the theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions of the study. The chapter also acknowledges the limitations of the study. Further, research areas for future studies are proposed. Recommendations are also made.

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APPENDIX 1: Customer Repurchase Intention Model

Davis (1989) Technology Acceptance Model TAM

Source: Davis, 1989

APPENDIX 2: Research Instruments

Appendix 2.1: Survey questionnaire

INVESTIGATING DETERMINANTS OF CUSTOMER REPURCHASE INTENTION IN INTERNET SHOPPERS IN NIGERIA

The purpose of this research is to collect primary information about the experiences and opinions of online shoppers when it comes to repurchasing items online in Nigeria.

Participation in this questionnaire is completely voluntary. All information provided as well as privacy of respondents remain confidential.

Email address *

What category below describes your age? *

- 18 - 25 years
- 26 - 35 years
- 35 - 50 years
- Over 50 years

Do you own a smartphone? *

- Yes
- No
- Other smart devices (Tablets, smartwatches e.t.c)

How much time do you spend online everyday? *

- Less than an hour
- 1 - 2 hours
- 3 - 5 hours
- Over 5 hours

How often do you shop online? *

- Once a day
- Multiple times daily
- Once weekly
- Once monthly

through social media platforms and mobile apps you use frequently? *

- Very often
- Occasionally
- Never

Influence of social media *

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither Disagree nor agree Agree Strongly agree

Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online	<input type="radio"/>				
Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product	<input type="radio"/>				
Fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms	<input type="radio"/>				

reviews from other customers on social media platforms

Social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting

Perceived value *

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither disagree nor agree Agree Strongly Agree

When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted on

When purchased goods and services do not meet perceived expectations, consumers are likely to

consumers are likely to repurchase with the same brand

When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria I return to purchase more	<input type="radio"/>				
--	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Privacy and trust *

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither disagree nor agree Agree Strongly agree

I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses	<input type="radio"/>				
--	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details	<input type="radio"/>				
---	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and	<input type="radio"/>				
---	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

cookies and
online
trackers of
consumer
behavior

I would
purchase
more goods
online in
Nigeria only
on a 'Pay on
delivery basis'

I have bought
items from
online
vendors even
when I did not
trust them

Brand reputation *

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither disagree nor agree Agree Strongly agree

I am
encouraged
to repurchase
goods and
services from
brands with
good
reputation
despite the
trust issues in
the Nigerian
online
shopping
space

I repurchase
from brands
who deliver
quality service

from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors

When spending huge amounts online, I purchase from trusted brands rather than cheaper options or discounted vendors

I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy

System availability and functionality *

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither disagree nor agree Agree Strongly agree

I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods

rather than
one with a
better website

I am more
likely to
repurchase
goods from
websites that
offer very
good delivery

I will
repurchase
from online
vendors who
respond
promptly to
online queries

I would
repurchase
from an online
vendor that
provides
quality
shopping
experience
despite poor
quality goods

I am keen on
receiving
aftersales
follow up as it
will make me
repurchase
items online

After completing an online shopping, you are prompted to take part in a quick customer survey, which of the following best describes your usual action? *

- Immediately take part in survey
- Postpone survey for a later date
- Uninterested in completing survey
- Other:

On a scale of 1 - 8 with 1 being the least applicable and 8 most applicable, which of these factors most influences your decision to repurchase products and services online *

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Trust	<input type="radio"/>							
Ease of use	<input type="radio"/>							
Fulfillment derived from using website	<input type="radio"/>							
Enjoyment derived from using website	<input type="radio"/>							
Perceived value	<input type="radio"/>							
Brand reputation	<input type="radio"/>							
Online platform functionality	<input type="radio"/>							
Privacy	<input type="radio"/>							

On a scale of 1 - 6 with 1 being the least applicable and 6 most applicable, which of these factors most influences your decision to repurchase products and services online *

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Product characteristics	<input type="radio"/>					
Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	<input type="radio"/>					
Brand reputation and status	<input type="radio"/>					
Ease of use of website, delivery and returns	<input type="radio"/>					

On a scale of 1 - 6 with 1 being the least applicable and 6 most applicable, which of these factors most influences your decision to repurchase products and services online *

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Product characteristics	<input type="radio"/>					
Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	<input type="radio"/>					
Brand reputation and status	<input type="radio"/>					
Ease of use of website, delivery and returns	<input type="radio"/>					
Pricing strategy	<input type="radio"/>					
Available support, contact and responsiveness	<input type="radio"/>					

Thank You for your time and Participation

Appendix 2.2: Semi-structured interview guide

INTERVIEW

INVESTIGATING DETERMINANTS OF CUSTOMER REPURCHASE INTENTION IN INTERNET SHOPPERS IN NIGERIA

1. My name is Nneka Alex-Onyeagwu and I am a student currently undertaking a DBA program at the University of the West of Scotland.
2. The aim of this interview is to investigate existing influencers of customer repurchase intention in Nigeria and to create new ones.
3. Your Participation in this interview is completely voluntary and you can opt out at any time. All information provided is confidential and will not be shared but some of the answers can be used in the thesis to support some important points.

Date _____ Company _____ Position _____

Question 1 – Could you please introduce yourself briefly?

Question 2 – How long have you been an online business/vendor in Nigeria?

Question 3 – Can you please give me an estimate on your website traffic per day? How many visitors do you have?

Question 4 – How many purchases through online shopping are you able to record daily?

Question 5 – when it comes to online purchases, what do you believe mostly influences your customers to repurchase?

Question 6 – In your opinion, how would you describe the stance on trust customers have towards online shopping activity in general?

Question 7 – is your brand reputation a major influencer of your customers' repurchase intention?

Question 8 – Do you think social media plays a major role in influencing the repurchase intentions of your customers?

Question 9 – What channels of support do you currently have in resolving your customers' issues? Give me an example, how many issues are raised/resolved daily?

Question 10 – speaking of reaching your customers, what mediums of contact do customers in Nigeria most prefer?

Question 11 – How willing are your customers to partake in surveys and market research?

Question 12 – Lastly, do you have any plans for most of the population which is yet to be penetrated by the application of the internet to online shopping?

Thank you for participating.

APPENDIX 3: Ethical Approval and Considerations

08/03/2018

Dear Nneka Alex-Onyeagwu,

Your application 4668: INVESTIGATING DETERMINANTS OF CUSTOMER REPURCHASE INTENTION IN INTERNET SHOPPERS IN NIGERIA, submission 2256, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

INVESTIGATING DETERMINANTS OF CUSTOMER REPURCHASE INTENTION IN INTERNET SHOPPERS IN NIGERIA

Project summary

The purpose of this research is to analyse existing influencers and discover new factors that influence customer repurchase intentions with regards online shopping in Nigeria.

This questionnaire will try to gather information of the degree to which each new and existing determinant instigate customers to repurchase items on ecommerce platforms in Nigeria. This study will include information that the participant believe encourages them to repurchase items online.

Why have you been asked to participate?

The researcher chose the participants for the study mainly because of the positions they hold in their companies. You have been asked to participate because for the purpose of data collection you fit the requirements of the general consumer demography for this research.

You were chosen because the researcher believes that you will have first-hand knowledge of the information needed for the study. The researcher hopes to get answers to the research questions from the data collected from the participants.

Your participation is voluntary, and you may leave the session at any time you like.

Your participation will be part of the information for this a study. If you agree to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign the consent form. A copy of this form and the consent form will be given to you to keep for your records.

To do for participant

The researcher will be conducting interviews at company premises so the participant will not need to worry about logistics issues and security problems. Several prepared questions will be asked, and the participant will be expected to provide true and accurate responses to the questions asked. Some participants will be sent questionnaires via email addresses provided and will be expected to complete such questionnaires as quickly and as accurately as possible. Participants may decline to answer any of the questions asked and may decide to back out of the study if they wish to.

Time Commitment

Each interview conducted duration is aimed at 60 minutes. The interviews will be done at the convenience of the interviewees. The questionnaire can be completed within 60 minutes but the respondents will be given about 7 days to return the completed questionnaires.

Rights of Participants

The participants may decide not to partake in the study at any time without explanation. The participant has the right to ask that any data already supplied be withdrawn. The participant has the right to omit or refuse to answer any questions asked.

The participant has the right to have any questions about the study answered, unless answering the question asked would interfere with the outcome of the study. If the participants have any questions after reading this form, they should ask the researcher before the study begins.

Confidentiality of Participants Personal Information

Personal information about the participants will remain strictly confidential and will be anonymised. Information about the participants will only be accessible to the researcher and the Director of Studies (DOS). Information about the participants will be kept separate from the data collected and participants will only be known by code names assigned to them. Data collected in this study will not be transferred to other researchers.

The study results will be published and can be made accessible to the participants. There are no known benefits or risks for the participants in this research. The participants should feel free to express any concerns they may have regarding participating in this study. The participant may ask to be excluded from the study at any time and any data already collected can be destroyed if the participant so requests.

Project risks

The research requires to filling out a questionnaire which will be kept for later analysis. We do not think that there are any significant risks associated with this study but if you feel there is any, please let us know and you are free to stop the process. Besides that, if you believe that any question is inappropriate, and you feel uncomfortable; please feel free to withdraw the process at any time.

We will completely respect your decision.

How we protect your privacy

All the information you provide will be confidential.

The questionnaires will not include any personal information that can identify you, maintaining the anonymity promised.

Your personal details from the consent form and the questionnaire will be kept in secure places by the researcher. All the information and documentation will be destroyed at the end of this study.

Provision for is something goes wrong

The address of the ethics committee will be provided. If something goes wrong during the study and the participants want to participate in the study or are not comfortable with a situation, they will be directed to the ethics committee.

Summarily, signing below, you are agreeing that you have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet, questions about your participation in this study have been satisfactorily answered, you are taking part in the research voluntarily, you understand the risks and benefits of the study and anonymised data may be shared in public research repositories.

YOU WILL BE OFFERED A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

If you require any further information about this research, then please contact:

Alex- Onyeagwu Nneka, University of the West of Scotland.

Tel: XXXXXXXXXX

APPENDIX 4: Questionnaires- Answers Per Question

Age

What is your age category?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 - 25 years old	32	32.0	32.0	32.0
	26 - 35 years old	46	46.0	46.0	78.0
	36 - 50 years old	19	19.0	19.0	97.0
	51 years old and above	3	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Smartphone

Do you own a smartphone?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	78	78.0	78.0	78.0
	No	22	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Time spent

How much time do you spend online every day?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than an hour	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	1-2 hours	31	31.0	31.0	32.0
	3-5 hours	40	40.0	40.0	72.0
	6 hours and above	28	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

How often do you shop online?

How often do you shop online?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Once a day	5	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Multiple times a day	36	36.0	36.0	41.0
	Once a week	16	16.0	16.0	57.0
	Once a month	43	43.0	43.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Buy product and services advertised on social media and mobile apps

How often do you buy products and services advertised through social media and mobile apps?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very often	17	17.0	17.0	17.0
	Occasionally	70	70.0	70.0	87.0
	Never	13	13.0	13.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Social media platforms customer repurchases

Social media platforms and tools influence how you repurchase goods and services online					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	5	5.0	5.0	7.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	10	10.0	10.0	17.0
	Agree	47	47.0	47.0	64.0
	Strongly agree	36	36.0	36.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Review of products

Ratings and review of products I purchase influence my repurchase of that particular product

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Disagree	4	4.0	4.0	5.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	16	16.0	16.0	21.0
	Agree	47	47.0	47.0	68.0
	Strongly agree	32	32.0	32.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms

Fulfilled and satisfied customers repurchase a particular product despite poor reviews from other customers on social media platforms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	6	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Disagree	5	5.0	5.0	11.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	19	19.0	19.0	30.0
	Agree	39	39.0	39.0	69.0
	Strongly agree	31	31.0	31.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Social media platforms, transparency and trust

Social media platforms promote transparency and flow of information making consumers empowered and trusting

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	8	8.0	8.0	10.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	25	25.0	25.0	35.0
	Agree	40	40.0	40.0	75.0
	Strongly agree	25	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Consumer's expectations and satisfaction

When an actual product or service meets a consumer's expectations and satisfaction is met, repurchase can be counted

		on			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	9	9.0	9.0	10.0
	Agree	49	49.0	49.0	59.0
	Strongly agree	41	41.0	41.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

When purchased goods and services do not meet perceived expectations, consumers are likely to repurchase with the same brand.

When purchased goods and services do not meet perceived expectations, consumers are likely to repurchase with the

		same brand			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	22	22.0	22.0	22.0
	Disagree	26	26.0	26.0	48.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	10	10.0	10.0	58.0
	Agree	23	23.0	23.0	81.0
	Strongly agree	19	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more

When I feel fulfilled shopping on a website in Nigeria, I return to purchase more

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neither Disagree nor agree	13	13.0	13.0	13.0
	Agree	64	64.0	64.0	77.0
	Strongly agree	23	23.0	23.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses

I find it easy trusting Nigerian online businesses

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Strongly disagree	14	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Disagree	22	22.0	22.0	36.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	18	18.0	18.0	54.0
	Agree	34	34.0	34.0	88.0
	Strongly agree	12	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details

I will repurchase goods from any online vendor that keeps my personal details

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	9	9.0	9.0	9.0
	Disagree	9	9.0	9.0	18.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	25	25.0	25.0	43.0
	Agree	36	36.0	36.0	79.0
	Strongly agree	21	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour

Politely requesting a feedback or survey is a more trustworthy form of generating data than cookies and online trackers of consumer behaviour

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	15	15.0	15.0	18.0
	Agree	57	57.0	57.0	75.0
	Strongly agree	25	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a 'Pay on delivery basis

I would purchase more goods online in Nigeria only on a 'Pay on delivery basis'

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	13	13.0	13.0	17.0
	Agree	51	51.0	51.0	68.0

Strongly agree	32	32.0	32.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I have bought items from online vendors even when I did not trust them

I have bought items from online vendors even when I did not trust them

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	18	18.0	18.0	18.0
	Disagree	11	11.0	11.0	29.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	8	8.0	8.0	37.0
	Agree	42	42.0	42.0	79.0
	Strongly agree	21	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Brand Reputation

I am encouraged to repurchase goods and services from brands with good reputation despite the trust issues in the

Nigerian online shopping space

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	18	18.0	18.0	21.0
	Agree	54	54.0	54.0	75.0
	Strongly agree	25	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other online vendors.

I repurchase from brands who deliver quality service and meet expectations despite prices and promotions from other

online vendors

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	10	10.0	10.0	11.0
	Agree	57	57.0	57.0	68.0
	Strongly agree	32	32.0	32.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

When spending huge amounts online, I purchase from trusted brands rather than cheaper options or discounted vendors

When spending huge amounts online, I purchase from trusted brands rather than cheaper options or discounted

		vendors			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Disagree	3	3.0	3.0	4.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	4	4.0	4.0	8.0
	Agree	54	54.0	54.0	62.0
	Strongly agree	38	38.0	38.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy

I am encouraged to repurchase from brands with simple and straight forward returns policy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neither Disagree nor agree	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Agree	57	57.0	57.0	60.0
	Strongly agree	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

System availability and functionality

I will repurchase from an online vendor with better quality of goods rather than one with a better website

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	8	8.0	8.0	9.0
	Agree	53	53.0	53.0	62.0
	Strongly agree	38	38.0	38.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I am more likely to repurchase goods from websites that offer very good delivery

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	3	3.0	3.0	4.0
	Agree	41	41.0	41.0	45.0
	Strongly agree	55	55.0	55.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I will repurchase from online vendors who respond promptly to online queries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	5	5.0	5.0	6.0
	Agree	58	58.0	58.0	64.0
	Strongly agree	36	36.0	36.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I would repurchase from an online vendor that provides quality shopping experience despite poor quality goods

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Disagree	22	22.0	22.0	52.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	7	7.0	7.0	59.0
	Agree	23	23.0	23.0	82.0
	Strongly agree	18	18.0	18.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

I am keen on receiving aftersales follow up as it will make me repurchase items online

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	3.0
	Neither Disagree nor agree	33	33.0	33.0	36.0
	Agree	42	42.0	42.0	78.0
	Strongly agree	22	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Survey after online shopping

After completing an online shopping, you are prompted to take part in a quick customer survey, which of the following best describes your usual action?				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Immediately take part in survey	45	45.0	45.0	45.0
	Postpone survey for a later date	39	39.0	39.0	84.0
	Uninterested in completing survey	14	14.0	14.0	98.0
	Other	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Most influential factors for online repurchases

		Trust			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Little influential	1	1.0	1.0	2.0
	Moderately influential	1	1.0	1.0	3.0
	Influential	6	6.0	6.0	9.0
	Somehow Influential	14	14.0	14.0	23.0
	Very influential	37	37.0	37.0	60.0
	Extremely influential	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

		Ease of use			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Least influential	1	1.0	1.0	3.0
	Little influential	2	2.0	2.0	5.0
	Moderately influential	2	2.0	2.0	7.0
	Influential	8	8.0	8.0	15.0
	Somehow Influential	12	12.0	12.0	27.0
	Very influential	30	30.0	30.0	57.0
	Extremely influential	43	43.0	43.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0		

		Fulfilment derived from using website			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Least influential	12	12.0	12.0	16.0

	Little influential	1	1.0	1.0	17.0
	Moderately influential	4	4.0	4.0	21.0
	Influential	8	8.0	8.0	29.0
	Somehow Influential	11	11.0	11.0	40.0
	Very influential	33	33.0	33.0	73.0
	Extremely influential	27	27.0	27.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Enjoyment derived from using website

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Least influential	4	4.0	4.0	14.0
	Little influential	3	3.0	3.0	17.0
	Moderately influential	5	5.0	5.0	22.0
	Influential	8	8.0	8.0	30.0
	Somehow Influential	18	18.0	18.0	48.0
	Very influential	33	33.0	33.0	81.0
	Extremely influential	19	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Perceived value

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Little influential	2	2.0	2.0	4.0
	Moderately influential	2	2.0	2.0	6.0
	Influential	4	4.0	4.0	10.0
	Somehow Influential	20	20.0	20.0	30.0
	Very influential	34	34.0	34.0	64.0
	Extremely influential	36	36.0	36.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Brand reputation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Little influential	1	1.0	1.0	2.0
	Moderately influential	1	1.0	1.0	3.0
	Influential	6	6.0	6.0	9.0
	Somehow Influential	12	12.0	12.0	21.0
	Very influential	54	54.0	54.0	75.0

	Extremely influential	25	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

		Online platform functionality			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Little influential	6	6.0	6.0	9.0
	Moderately influential	5	5.0	5.0	14.0
	Influential	5	5.0	5.0	19.0
	Somehow Influential	13	13.0	13.0	32.0
	Very influential	34	34.0	34.0	66.0
	Extremely influential	34	34.0	34.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

		Privacy			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not influential at all	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Least influential	1	1.0	1.0	3.0
	Little influential	5	5.0	5.0	8.0
	Moderately influential	6	6.0	6.0	14.0
	Influential	4	4.0	4.0	18.0
	Somehow Influential	9	9.0	9.0	27.0
	Very influential	20	20.0	20.0	47.0
	Extremely influential	53	53.0	53.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0		

Other influential factors for online repurchases

		Product characteristics			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not applicable at all	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Moderately applicable	1	1.0	1.0	3.0
	Applicable	8	8.0	8.0	11.0
	Very applicable	49	49.0	49.0	60.0
	Extremely applicable	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Satisfaction and previous shopping experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not applicable at all	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Moderately applicable	1	1.0	1.0	2.0
	Applicable	5	5.0	5.0	7.0
	Very applicable	35	35.0	35.0	42.0
	Extremely applicable	58	58.0	58.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Brand reputation and status

Brand reputation and status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not applicable at all	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Least applicable	2	2.0	2.0	3.0
	Moderately applicable	4	4.0	4.0	7.0
	Applicable	19	19.0	19.0	26.0
	Very applicable	42	42.0	42.0	68.0
	Extremely applicable	32	32.0	32.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Ease of use of website, delivery and returns

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not applicable at all	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Least applicable	13	13.0	13.0	14.0
	Moderately applicable	2	2.0	2.0	16.0
	Applicable	8	8.0	8.0	24.0
	Very applicable	35	35.0	35.0	59.0
	Extremely applicable	41	41.0	41.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Pricing strategy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not applicable at all	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Least applicable	1	1.0	1.0	2.0
	Moderately applicable	12	12.0	12.0	14.0
	Applicable	11	11.0	11.0	25.0
	Very applicable	42	42.0	42.0	67.0
	Extremely applicable	33	33.0	33.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Available support, contact and responsiveness

Available support, contact and responsiveness

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not applicable at all	14	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Moderately applicable	1	1.0	1.0	15.0
	Applicable	5	5.0	5.0	20.0
	Very applicable	27	27.0	27.0	47.0
	Extremely applicable	53	53.0	53.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

APPENDIX 5: Tables for primary data

Correlations											
		CRI	Trust	Ease of use	Fulfillment derived from using website	Enjoyment derived from using website	Perceived value	Brand reputation	Online platform functionality	Privacy	
Spearman's rho	CRI	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.271**	-.105	.050	-.003	.270**	-.031	-.103	-.223*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.006	.301	.620	.977	.007	.762	.310	.026
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Trust	Trust	Correlation Coefficient	-.271**	1.000	.388**	.307**	-.230*	-.295**	-.036	.432**	.482**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.	.000	.002	.021	.003	.721	.000	.000
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Ease of use	Ease of use	Correlation Coefficient	-.105	.388**	1.000	.391**	.393**	.053	.104	.462**	.421**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.301	.000	.	.000	.000	.603	.305	.000	.000
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Fulfillment derived from using website	Fulfillment derived from using website	Correlation Coefficient	.050	.307**	.391**	1.000	.672**	.029	.084	.486**	.445**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.620	.002	.000	.	.000	.777	.409	.000	.000
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Enjoyment derived from using website	Enjoyment derived from using website	Correlation Coefficient	-.003	.230*	.393**	.672**	1.000	.008	.123	.363**	.367**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.977	.021	.000	.000	.	.941	.223	.000	.000
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Perceived value	Perceived value	Correlation Coefficient	.270**	-.295**	.053	.029	.008	1.000	.199*	.040	-.046
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	.003	.603	.777	.941	.	.048	.696	.646
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Brand reputation	Brand reputation	Correlation Coefficient	-.031	-.036	.104	.084	.123	.199*	1.000	.072	.124
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.762	.721	.305	.409	.223	.048	.	.474	.219
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Online platform functionality	Online platform functionality	Correlation Coefficient	-.103	.432**	.462**	.486**	.363**	.040	.072	1.000	.584**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.310	.000	.000	.000	.000	.696	.474	.	.000
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Privacy	Privacy	Correlation Coefficient	-.223*	.482**	.421**	.445**	.367**	-.046	.124	.584**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.026	.000	.000	.000	.000	.646	.219	.000	.
		N	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlations						
		CRI	Product characteristics	Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	Available support, contact and responsiveness	
Spearman's rho	CRI	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.164	.027	-.155
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.103	.788	.123
		N	100	100	100	100
Product characteristics	Product characteristics	Correlation Coefficient	-.164	1.000	.010	.200*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.103	.	.924	.046
		N	100	100	100	100
Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	Satisfaction and previous shopping experience	Correlation Coefficient	.027	.010	1.000	.159
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.788	.924	.	.114
		N	100	100	100	100
Available support, contact and responsiveness	Available support, contact and responsiveness	Correlation Coefficient	-.155	.200*	.159	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.123	.046	.114	.
		N	100	100	100	100

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlations				
		CRI	Other Factors for Online Repurchases	
Spearman's rho	CRI	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.220*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.028
		N	100	100
Other Factors for Online Repurchases	Other Factors for Online Repurchases	Correlation Coefficient	-.220*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	.
		N	100	100

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).